

AN APPROACH FOR OBJECTIVE PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT OF
AUTOMATED VEHICLES WITH HUMAN BEHAVIOR AS A BENCHMARK

DI MANUEL SCHWARZ, MSC

University of the West of Scotland (UWS)
June 2023

Declaration

I hereby declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, this thesis is the result of my own work; furthermore, no portion of the work referred to in this thesis, in part or in whole, has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other university, or institute of learning.

 Personal details withheld.

Manuel Schwarz

June 2023

Abstract

The age of automated vehicles has begun and is expected to significantly shape the future of transport in the coming years. The rapid development of new technologies and methodologies has enabled considerable progress in the automotive industry recently. For legislators and consumers to accept new systems, their safety, reliability and robustness must be demonstrated on public road driving conditions. Due to the high complexity of covering countless traffic scenarios under a wide range of environmental conditions, the initial enthusiasm to achieve automated vehicles with full autonomous support has declined. One of the main reasons for the slow development progress are edge cases, which represent critical scenarios that rarely occur but must be considered for safety purposes.

Scenario-based testing of automated vehicles on closed proving grounds is one of the most established approaches in validation today, and it is used as part of the homologation process by certification organizations. The number of possible tests with this methodology is currently limited because the configuration, execution, and assessment of scenarios are extremely time-consuming and complex. Therefore, there is a risk of not being able to identify all safety-critical issues that may exist in a system. The literature lacks scalable testing methods that can increase test coverage while being more realistic to provide a robust performance assessment of automated vehicles.

The aim of this research is to develop a standardized and scalable solution for the objective performance assessment of an automated vehicle that will serve as additional input for public road transport approval decisions.

As a method to evaluate the performance of an automated vehicle in a safe and standardized way, this research used the detection of behavioral differences between human drivers and automated systems to identify safety-critical events and uncomfortable scenarios on public roads. A novel measuring device, which did not exist before, was developed for the purpose of detecting behavioral differences at the steering wheel. With this innovation, the steering movements of the driver can be detected independently without affecting the original steering wheel of the vehicle and, therefore the behavior of the automated system up to a safety-critical threshold limit. The theoretical framework, implemented concept, and performance assessment of a production vehicle with automated functions were validated by test drives on public roads. According to the results of this research, current automated functions lack safety, reliability and robustness under certain circumstances, resulting in dangerous scenarios within seconds. As the automated system was deactivated without prior warning, an identified scenario of this research could have led to a serious accident without immediate intervention by a human driver. Testing has demonstrated that the concept and theoretical framework developed are safe and can be used in a standardized manner on public roads. In addition, the test results show that a human driver is capable of de-escalating a scenario within seconds in order to avoid serious consequences.

There are currently limitations to the functions of automated vehicles under certain conditions, as not all traffic scenarios can be recognized and handled correctly. If a human driver does not intervene in the event of a problem immediately, or if the system cannot find a solution, this poses a potential safety risk for vehicle

passengers and other road users. Critical events and uncomfortable scenarios on public roads can be identified by continuously comparing behavioral differences between human and automated systems without mutual interference up to a defined safety-critical threshold. The developed concept can complement scenario-based testing in simulation environments and closed proving grounds since many scenarios can be validated with lower effort. The implications of this research for the field of automated vehicle testing show that better methods for validation are needed. If the systems do not have a high level of safety, reliability and robustness, it will not be feasible to distribute them, as legislators and consumers will not accept them.

Acknowledgments

I would like to take this opportunity to give special thanks to my Director of Studies, Luc Rolland, P.Eng (NL). M.A.Sc. PhD and Supervisor James Bruce Johnston. Both of them have supported me unconditionally throughout the entire journey and provided valuable input and constructive feedback. Despite certain difficulties due to COVID-19, the work progressed efficiently due to their high level of commitment and personal flexibility. The administrative team of the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) must also be mentioned here, as help was always provided quickly and unbureaucratically in all matters.

Another thank you goes to Dr. Kevin Keuther from the West Saxon University of Applied Sciences Zwickau, who provided valuable input for the completion of my PhD thesis during numerous workshops and personal meetings. He supervised all activities throughout the entire period and also proactively supported me with administrative and organizational issues.

A special thank you goes to Mag. Stefan Friedrich, PH.D. who, manages the entire study program at Ingenium Education. Without his active support, the study could not have been carried out in the form in which it was finally organized.

A significant contribution to the result of this research was made by my employer and my colleagues. Achieving the results described in the realization chapter would have been difficult without their help and contribution.

In addition, I would like to express my gratitude to my girlfriend for all of her support and motivation throughout the entire process. Without her high level of understanding, especially with regard to the time necessary for the implementation of this research, a successful thesis would not have been possible.

Last but not least, I would like to thank my family, especially my mother. Without her commitment, my career would not have been possible in the way it was these past years.

Table of Content

Part 1: Literature Review	10
Chapter 1 Safety Expectations for Automated Vehicles	11
1.1 Need for Better Safeguarding of ADAS/AD Systems.....	11
1.1.1 Current Statistics	11
1.1.2 Road Safety Issues.....	11
1.1.3 Crash Statistics.....	13
1.2 Transition to Automated Transportation.....	15
1.2.1 The Reality of the Current Rollout Status	15
1.2.2 History and Successful Implementation.....	16
1.2.3 Replacing a Human Driver.....	17
1.3 The Way to Automated Vehicles.....	19
1.3.1 Society of Automotive Engineers Framework.....	19
1.3.2 Relation Between Key Terms	21
1.3.3 Software Defined Vehicles.....	23
1.3.4 Step-by-Step Approach	24
1.4 Relationship between Human Behavior and Driving Performance.....	25
1.4.1 Human Factors	27
1.4.2 Human Decisions.....	28
1.4.3 Decision Making Models.....	29
Chapter 2 Road Safety	32
2.1.1 Safety Categories	34
2.1.2 Increasing Trust in Automated Vehicles	35
2.1.3 Human versus Machine	38
2.1.4 Driver Attention and Takeover	39
2.1.5 Regulations.....	39
Chapter 3 State-of-the-Art in System Development and Validation.....	41
3.1 Current State of Development.....	41
3.2 Challenges Caused by Unforeseen Scenarios	42
3.2.1 Edge Problems on Public Roads	42
3.2.2 Influencing Factors	44
3.3 Development Approaches	45
3.4 Testing Approaches	48
3.4.1 Classification of Testing Environments.....	48
3.4.2 Data Collection	49
3.4.3 Testing Tools: Virtual Vehicle and Virtual Environment	49
3.4.4 Testing Tools: Real Vehicle and Real Environment.....	50
3.5 Simulation Technology.....	51
3.5.1 Enabler for Scalability and Repeatability	51
3.5.2 System Models	52
3.5.3 Limitations	52
3.6 Real World Testing.....	53
3.6.1 Closed Testing Environments.....	53
3.6.2 Comparison of Testing Approaches.....	54
3.6.3 Automated Driving Requirements in the EU and USA.....	55
3.6.4 Confidence Level and Approval Trap.....	57
3.7 Critical Analysis and Summarization of Existing Literature.....	60
Part 2: Theoretical Framework Development and Concept Realization	62
Chapter 4 Theoretical Framework of the Shadow System	63
4.1 Aims and Objectives.....	63
4.2 Framework Outline Design and Interface	64
4.3 Theory Behind the Detection of Behavioral Differences	65
4.3.1 Human as a Benchmark	68
4.3.2 Vehicle as a Black Box	68
4.3.3 Safety Approach	69
4.3.4 Behavior Difference Visualization	69

4.4	Justification of the Selected Theory Approach.....	71
4.4.1	Implications of the Theory.....	72
4.4.2	Features of the Theory that Enables New Knowledge.....	73
4.5	Key Concept of the Shadow System.....	73
4.5.1	Overview.....	73
4.5.2	Shadow Steering Wheel	74
4.5.3	Shadow Pedal.....	75
4.5.4	Shadow Guard.....	75
4.5.5	Shadow Light.....	75
4.5.6	Shadow View.....	75
4.5.7	Shadow Sensor Deception	76
4.5.8	Shadow Eyes.....	76
4.5.9	Human Driver	76
4.5.10	Vehicle Configuration.....	76
4.5.11	On-Board Diagnostics Standard	76
4.5.12	Weather Conditions	76
4.5.13	Road Conditions	77
4.5.14	Route.....	77
4.5.15	Feedback.....	77
4.6	Introducing the Shadow Steering Wheel Component.....	78
4.6.1	Requirements and Use Cases.....	78
4.6.2	Design and Interfaces.....	79
4.6.3	Electronic Design.....	80
4.6.4	Implications of the Concept	81
4.7	Advantageous Differentiation to Existing Concepts and Knowledge.....	82
4.8	Drawbacks.....	89
4.9	Relation to Aims and Objectives	90
Chapter 5 Methodology.....		91
5.1	Theoretical Framework and Concept Realization	91
5.1.1	Justification of the Approach.....	91
5.1.2	Test Drive Workflow.....	91
5.2	Data Collection Structure	94
5.2.1	Master Data	94
5.2.2	Reference Data	97
5.2.3	Metadata.....	99
5.2.4	Measurement Data	100
5.2.5	Data Storage	101
5.3	Development of the Shadow Steering Wheel Measurement Device.....	102
5.3.1	Elements and Components of the Design	102
5.3.2	Realization.....	103
5.3.3	Circuit Diagram.....	106
5.3.4	Driver Hand Detection	106
5.3.5	Data Collection Box	107
5.3.6	Program Logic	108
5.3.7	Installation	110
5.3.8	Calibration	111
5.3.9	Recommended Improvements From the Last Implementation	113
5.4	Data Collection.....	114
5.4.1	Tool Review and Selection	114
5.4.2	Shadow Application as a Custom Development.....	115
5.4.3	Optional Data Logging.....	116
5.5	Test Drives	117
5.5.1	Assessment Structure.....	117
5.5.2	Context Information	118
5.5.3	Scenario Analysis and Assessment.....	118
5.5.4	Test Vehicle.....	120
5.5.5	Data Acquisition.....	121
5.6	Implications of the Selected Methodology	122
5.7	Ethical or Philosophical Considerations.....	123
Part 3: Validation of the Shadow System Framework and Gained Knowledge.....		124
Chapter 6 Results and Analysis.....		125

6.1 Public Road Test Results	125
6.1.1 Test Drive Execution.....	125
6.1.2 Scenario 1	125
6.1.3 Scenario 2	129
6.1.4 Scenario 3	134
6.1.5 Scenario 4	137
Chapter 7 Advancing Knowledge in Automated System Validation.....	140
7.1.2 Identified Safety-Relevant Gaps	141
7.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses of the Shadow Concept.....	142
7.1.4 Positioning of the Shadow Concept in the ADAS/AD Code of Practice	142
7.1.5 Use of the System on Public Roads	143
7.2 System Reliance and Reliability.....	144
7.3 Identification of Critical Aspects	146
Chapter 8 Impact of the Shadow Framework and Concept on Safety Assessment	147
8.1 Integrating Human Behavior into the Homologation Process	147
8.2 Delivering an Enhanced Validation Approach.....	148
8.3 Performance Assessment and Framework Validation	149

List of Figures

Figure 1: Comparison of the vehicle homologation for past versus future.....	4
Figure 2: Illustration of Uber crash analysis (National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB), 2018).....	5
Figure 3: Video still of a sleeping driver in the back seat while driving a Tesla with activated Autopilot function (Lambert, F., 2021).....	6
Figure 4: Video still of a construction site issue with a Tesla system (Tesla Raj, 2020).....	6
Figure 5: Video still with the incorrect navigation path of a Tesla system (Tesla Raj, 2020).....	7
Figure 6: Related topics for automated vehicles.....	12
Figure 7: Keyword cloud with the most important search terms.....	13
Figure 8: Illustration of the impression of autonomous driving (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).....	16
Figure 9: Illustration of the big picture framework for AI driverless cars (Eliot, L., 2018c).....	18
Figure 10: Illustration of the SAE framework for automated vehicles (Favarò, F., Eurich, S. and Nader, N., 2017).....	20
Figure 11: Illustration of an alternative framework for the SAE levels of automation (Loro, A., 2018).....	21
Figure 12: Illustration of the relationship between key terms (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017).....	22
Figure 13: Illustration of the different strategies of car manufacturers and technology companies (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).....	25
Figure 14: Illustration of the different sensor types in automated vehicles (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).....	26
Figure 15: Photograph of an iced vehicle due to bad weather conditions (Coelingh, E. and Nilsson, J., 2018).....	26
Figure 16: Illustration of different environments of decision making (Takemura, K., 2014).....	29
Figure 17: Illustration of a decision-making model in dynamic tasks (Qudrat-Ullah, H., 2014).....	31
Figure 18: Illustration of direct and indirect impacts of automated vehicles (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017).....	32
Figure 19: V-model of the ISO 26262 (Concas, F. et al., 2020).....	33
Figure 20: Illustration of an alternative workflow for the validation of safety (Takacs, A. et al., 2018).....	34
Figure 21: Marketing example for safety features (The Ford Motor Company, 2021).....	36
Figure 22: Photographs of a Tesla crash into an overturned truck (Stumpf, R., 2020).....	37
Figure 23: Photograph of conceptual misuses of today's automated vehicles (Rosenblatt, K., 2019).....	37
Figure 24: Standards and USA regulations for automated vehicles (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020).....	40
Figure 25: Photograph of an edge problem on public roads (Williams, C., 2016).....	43
Figure 26: Photograph of challenging light conditions on a public road (Williams, C., 2016).....	44
Figure 27: Illustration of traditional programming versus machine learning (David, J., 2019).....	46
Figure 28: Video still with ground truth labeling of the road targets (Ma, Y., Li, Z. and Sotelo, M. A., 2020).....	47
Figure 29: Illustration of different testing options for automated vehicles (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).....	48
Figure 30: Illustration of testing environments for automated vehicles (McQueen, B., 2019).....	48
Figure 31: Illustration of test scenario structure (Isermann, R., 2017).....	49
Figure 32: Screenshots of Udacity driving simulator (Chen, Y. et al., 2018).....	51
Figure 33: Photograph of Mcity for testing of automated vehicles on a closed proving ground (Khajepour, A., 2020).....	53
Figure 34: Illustration of scenario generation methods (Isermann, R., 2017).....	54
Figure 35: Illustration of automated driving requirements in the EU and USA (Winkle, T., Erbsmehl, C. and Bengler, K., 2018).....	56
Figure 36: Illustration of statistical calculation to ensure safety for automated vehicles (Kalra, N. and Paddock, S. M., 2016).....	58
Figure 37: Illustration of passenger car homologation regulations (Isermann, R., 2017).....	59
Figure 38: Illustration of the Shadow System theory.....	66
Figure 39: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with distance difference approach.....	67
Figure 40: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with correction force approach.....	68
Figure 41: Illustration of the behavior difference visualization for the Shadow System.....	70
Figure 42: Video still of public road testing with removed hands (42HOW, 2021).....	72
Figure 43: Illustration of the Shadow System framework components.....	74
Figure 44: Illustration of the general Shadow Steering Wheel concept.....	80

Figure 45: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with electronic design.	81
Figure 46: Illustration of a steering wheel actuation system of an automated vehicle (Wang, X., Guo, L. and Jia, Y., 2018b).	82
Figure 47: Illustration of driver intervention detection with a torque sensor (Schinkel, W. S., van der Sande, T. P. J. and Nijmeijer, H., 2020).	82
Figure 48: Illustration of human cooperative steering behavior model (Inga, J., Flad, M. and Hohmann, S., 2019).	83
Figure 49: Photograph of a test bench with driver feedback module (Huang, C. et al., 2020).	84
Figure 50: Illustration of a uncoupled steering system for testing an automated vehicle (Marcano, M. et al., 2020).	85
Figure 51: Illustration of a decoupled steering wheel with stationary and rim (Kerschbaum, P., Lorenz, L. and Bengler, K., 2014).	86
Figure 52: Illustration of steering interventions comparison for two traffic scenarios (Schneider, N., Purucker, C. and Neukum, A., 2015),	87
Figure 53: Illustration of a proposed system flow for unusual events identification (Wang, H., 2019).	88
Figure 54: Illustration of the data collection workflow for test drives.	93
Figure 55: Illustration of the Shadow System core domain model.	94
Figure 56: Illustration of the result storage structure.	102
Figure 57: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel of generation 4.	103
Figure 58: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel layers in version 2 of generation 4.	104
Figure 59: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel force sensor in version 2 of generation 4.	104
Figure 60: Plot of the acceleration and deceleration curve used for the Shadow Steering Wheel (desmos.com, 2020).	105
Figure 61: A rendered image of the integrated Pusher in the Handle component of the Shadow Steering Wheel.	106
Figure 62: Circuit diagram of the Shadow Steering Wheel component.	106
Figure 63: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel component with a hand detection sensor.	107
Figure 64: Photograph of the Data Collection Box.	108
Figure 65: Flow chart of the Shadow Steering Wheel program logic.	108
Figure 66: Software parameter of the Shadow Steering Wheel component.	109
Figure 67: JSON data package of the Shadow Steering Wheel.	110
Figure 68: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel realization in version 3 of generation 4.	110
Figure 69: Photograph of the flexible connectors for the Shadow Steering Wheel.	111
Figure 70: Illustration of the RPC7.6-Lt force sensor characteristic.	111
Figure 71: Illustration of the average operation area of a road in the EU.	112
Figure 72: Illustration of the Shadow Application software components.	116
Figure 73: Photograph of an Audi OBD interface (motor1.com, 2019).	116
Figure 74: Photograph of an Audi ACC configuration.	120
Figure 75: Illustration of the event location for scenario 1.	127
Figure 76: Scenario 1 with context information and sequence details.	128
Figure 77: Analysis of scenario 1 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.	129
Figure 78: Video still of scenario 2 with dynamic speed limitation.	131
Figure 79: Scenario 2 with context information and sequence details.	131
Figure 80: Analysis of scenario 2 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.	133
Figure 81: Scenario 3 with context information and sequence details.	135
Figure 82: Analysis of scenario 3 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.	136
Figure 83: Scenario 4 with context information and sequence details.	138
Figure 84: Analysis of scenario 4 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.	139
Figure 85: Illustration of the code of practice for ADAS/AD (Maurer, M., Gerdes, C. and Lenz, B., 2016).	143
Figure 86: Video still of a challenging traffic scenario with a truck overtaking a construction area.	146
Figure 87: Illustration of an extended homologation for passenger cars by the Shadow System framework.	148
Figure 88: Screenshot of the Dashboard view in the Shadow Application.	177
Figure 89: Screenshot of the Vehicle Selection view in the Shadow Application.	177
Figure 90: Screenshot of the Test Parameter view in the Shadow Application.	178
Figure 91: Screenshot of the Test Equipment view in the Shadow Application.	178
Figure 92: Screenshot of the Main view in the Shadow Application for the Shadow Steering Wheel component.	179

Figure 93: Screenshot of an OBD II example for the engine speed signal.	181
Figure 94: Screenshot of a DBC example for the engine speed signal.	181
Figure 95: Photograph of Kvaser Memorator Pro 2xhs data logger (kvaser.com, 2019).	182
Figure 96: Screenshot of Kvaser CanKing with engine revolutions per minute example.	183
Figure 97: Screenshot of an OBD example with CAN request message for engine speed signal.	184
Figure 98: Screenshot of an OBD II data logger configuration.	185
Figure 99: Screenshot of an OBD II data logger output.	185

List of Tables

Table 1: Safety systems grouped by technologies.....	14
Table 2: Annual impact by ADAS (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2019).	14
Table 3: Type of vehicle mapped to SAE level (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017). ...	23
Table 4: Critical event triggers and their threshold values (Singh, H. and Kathuria, A., 2021).	88
Table 5: Master data for a test drive.....	95
Table 6: Master data for a vehicle.	95
Table 7: Master data for vehicle configuration.	95
Table 8: Master data for driver.	96
Table 9: Logbook data structure.....	97
Table 10: Reference data for road conditions.	98
Table 11: Reference data for road type.....	98
Table 12: Reference data for weather conditions.	98
Table 13: Reference data for wind condition.....	98
Table 14: Reference data for a country.	98
Table 15: Reference data for ambient light.	98
Table 16: Reference data for traffic conditions.	99
Table 17: Reference data for driving style.....	99
Table 18: Reference data for road lane.....	99
Table 19: Results data for test drives.	99
Table 20: Measurement data overview.	100
Table 21: EU road parameter.....	112
Table 22: Steering wheel parameter.	113
Table 23: Shadow Steering Wheel threshold limits.....	113
Table 24: Attributes for the documentation of critical traffic events.	118
Table 25: Classifications for traffic scenarios.	119
Table 26: Details of the vehicle used for the test drives.....	120
Table 27: Audi settings for ACC (AG, A., 2018).	121
Table 28: Data capturing equipment used during test drives.....	121
Table 29: Metadata of scenario 1.....	126
Table 30: Metadata of scenario 2.....	129
Table 31: Raw data analysis for scenario 2.	133
Table 32: Metadata of scenario 3.....	134
Table 33: Metadata of scenario 4.....	137
Table 34: Electronic Components of the Shadow Steering Wheel	162
Table 35: OBD II data gathered by the Shadow Application.....	184

Abbreviations

AAA	American Automobile Association
ABS	Antilock Braking System
ACC	Adaptive Cruise Control
AD	Autonomous Driving
ADAS	Advanced Driver Assistance Systems
AEB	Automatic Emergency Braking
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Abbreviated Injury Scale
ALARP	As Low As Reasonably Practicable
ANN	Artificial Neural Networks
API	Application Programming Interface
AV	Autonomous Vehicles
BI	Business Intelligence
BSD	Blind Spot Detection
BSI	Blind Spot Intervention
BSW	Blind Spot Warning
CAN	Controller Area Network
CIB	Crash Imminent Braking
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DARPA	Defense Advanced Research Project Agency
DBC	CANdb-database-file with channel definition
DBS	Dynamic Brake Support
DC	Direct Current
DLC	Data Length Code
EBA	Emergency Brake Assistant
ELOS	Equivalent Level of Safety
FCW	Forward Collision Warning
FMVSS	Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards
FSD	Full Self-Driving
GDPR	General Data Protection Guidelines
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GUID	Globally Unique Identifier
HAP	Highway Autopilot
HIL	Hardware in the Loop
IATA	International Air Transport Association

ISO	International Organization for Standardization
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LCA	Lane Centering Assist
LCM	Lane Change/Merge Warning
LDW	Lane Departure Warning
LKA	Lane Keeping Assist
MAIS	Maximum Abbreviated Injury Scale
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NHTSA	National Highway Traffic Safety Administration
OBD	On-Board Diagnostics
ODD	Operational Design Domain
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OOTB	Out-of-the-Box
OTA	Over-the-Air
PAEB	Pedestrian Automatic Emergency Braking
PDOV	Property-Damage-Only Vehicles
RAB	Rear Automatic Braking
RAPEX	Rapid Exchange of Information
RCA	Root Cause Analysis
RCTA	Rear Cross Traffic Alert
RvAB	Reverse Automatic Braking
SA	Shadow Application
SAE	Society for Automotive Engineers
SBW	Steer-by-Wire
SDV	Self-Driving Vehicles
SE	Shadow Eyes
SIL	Software in the Loop
SG	Shadow Guard
SL	Shadow Light
SS	Shadow System
SSD	Shadow Sensor Deception
SSW	Shadow Steering Wheel
SP	Shadow Pedal
SV	Shadow View
TORT	Takeover Reaction Time
TOT	Takeover Time
TOR	Takeover Request
TÜV	Technischer Überwachungsverein

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UFO	Ultra Flat Overrunable
UI	User Interface
UWP	Universal Windows Platform
V2I	Vehicle to Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle to Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle to Everything
VAL	Automatic Light Vehicle
VIL	Vehicle in the Loop
WHO	World Health Organization

Glossary and Terms

Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS)

ADAS are support functions that assist the driver while driving and thus increase safety and comfort. Features such as an Emergency Brake Assistant (EBA) aim to actively reduce traffic accidents by automatically triggering braking maneuvers when a hazard is detected. When using ADAS functionality, the primary responsibility lies with the human driver, who must be able to intervene in case of a problem.

Autonomous Driving (AD)

A vehicle that can operate autonomously through the use of existing hardware and software. In the Society for Automotive Engineers (SAE) framework, this corresponds to vehicles at levels 3 to 5. For vehicles at levels 3 and 4, the Operational Design Domain (ODD) can be restricted to certain regions and environmental conditions.

Autonomous Vehicle (AV)

These types of vehicles sense the environment and can operate without a human driver in all conditions. Level 5 is based on the SAE framework for driving automation.

Corner Case

Also known as wicked problems or edge cases are circumstances that were not taken into account during the design and implementation of hardware or software components and led to problems in reality.

Driving Tasks

This term includes all activities that are necessary for the execution of a drive, such as the lateral or longitudinal movements of the vehicle; furthermore, it includes observation of the environment, planning of the next maneuvers, and activation of external signals for the environment, like turn indicators.

Durability

In terms of durability, it's the ability to last for a long time under expected conditions. The term is used to describe a type of quality and reliability associated with long-lasting items that do not break under stress. A commercial airliner that can be reused over several decades despite the stresses of multiple launches and landing is an example of such an aircraft.

Event

An event describes the occurrence of a certain condition that appears during a drive with a vehicle and is characterized by a unique point in time. An event is a time point in a scenario, where a scenario describes a longer period of time. An example of an event is an emergency break in a scenario where a pedestrian crosses the road.

Homologation

The homologation of a vehicle describes the approval procedure for a specific country or market. The approval of a vehicle and the certificate issued by the government allows it to be operated on public roads under the defined general conditions. In the literature, the terms type approval or vehicle certification are often used as synonyms.

Human Behavior

An individual's driving behavior during a journey is described by this term. People learn continuously in the course of their lives, and when events occur, they make decisions on the basis of their experiences. Human behavior is composed of a number of physical and emotional factors, such as social and intellectual, and is shaped by culture, personal values, ethics, etc. (Shinar, D., 2017).

Self-Driving Vehicles (SDV)

This term is usually used in the literature as a synonym for Autonomous Vehicles (AV) or Autonomous Driving (AD) vehicles. All terms have one common goal. Vehicles of this class can safely perform a journey from A to B without human intervention. Another term that is often used in this context in the literature is "driverless" vehicles. These terms are synonymous in regard to this research. Advanced technologies and new sensor types are needed to realize such systems. According to the international SAE framework, these types of automated driving systems apply to SAE levels 3 to level 5.

Operational Design Domain (ODD)

The ODD describes the area of application of an ADAS function or AD vehicle. This limitation intends to ensure that a system is only used in the designated framework conditions, such as weather conditions or road types (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). Use outside this area can lead to serious safety implications.

Reliability

Reliability is the probability that a product, service, or system will operate without failure in a given environment for a specified period. In terms of reliability, the most important components are probability, intended function, satisfaction, specific time period, and specified conditions.

Robustness

A system's ability to adapt to changing environments without being affected by them. System robustness ensures that functions are delivered under varying operating conditions without needing to be altered.

SAE J3016

SAE International is a global association of technical experts in the aerospace and automotive industry. It defined the standard J3016 to clarify and communicate the different types of automation levels. The framework is split into six levels: It starts with level 0 (no automation), which comprises regular cars, and leads up to the final level, level 5, which refers to vehicles with full autonomy (McQueen, B., 2019). The details of the framework are described in Section 1.3.

Safety

According to International Organization for Standardization (ISO) 26262, “safety” means that the operation of a system under the defined conditions can be carried out without danger as long as no inappropriate conditions occur. In this context, a condition is considered safe by authorities and legislators only if a defined threshold value is not exceeded. When considering thresholds, the context for social, moral, or ethical reasons is also considered and included in the assessment of acceptability. In this research, the term is particularly associated with material or human damage that may occur to the driver or other road participants during a journey (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).

Scenario

A traffic scenario describes a specific case that occurred during the execution of a journey on the road and extends over a longer period of time. Usually, this is a few seconds, which are relevant before and after the occurrence of a certain event. The description of a scenario is primarily composed of static and dynamic object information. In the area of vehicle validation, scenario catalogs are tested to validate essential and frequently occurring cases.

Testing

The purpose of testing is to identify problems or characteristics in a product. Testing in the automotive industry involves a series of laboratory, virtual and field-based assessments of a full vehicle, system, or component to ensure it is safe, reliable, and compliant with safety regulations. Testing for automotive products is a requirement for accessing international markets, and manufacturers must demonstrate that they have conducted rigorous assessments of their products.

Validation

It is the process of confirming through objective evidence that the developed system effectively accomplishes its intended purpose and meets the needs of the end consumers, stakeholders, legislators, and other shareholders for which it was designed. The purpose of validation is to determine whether the right system has been constructed.

Verification

The verification process confirms that the system requirements have been met by providing objective evidence. As a result, the question arises as to whether the system was designed properly and sufficiently to address the requirements, in other words, whether it was built correctly.

Introduction

Mobility of the Future

The field of automated vehicles is advancing, and systems with higher automation support are getting closer to reality. Unfortunately, the number of traffic accidents caused by the use of new vehicles is increasing with their proliferation. The validation of a vehicle as part of the homologation process has never played such an important role as it does now, as driving activities are carried out independently by the system and the driver is relegated to the background. Certification organizations are the final authority before release to the public market and must perform validation to the best of their ability. Due to the complexity of the new systems, these organizations face significant challenges and reach the limits of meaningful validation with traditional testing methods.

Automation is gaining interest and trust since many people would like to drive from point A to point B without much interaction (Xu, J. and Howard, A., 2020). This technology has the potential to completely change the driving behavior of people because they would be able to perform different activities while driving; furthermore, independent driving would be possible for new groups such as the elderly, disabled people, or children without a driving license (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). In addition, the number of critical traffic accidents could be significantly reduced as automated vehicles prevent drunk driving, distractions caused by internal or external influences. Besides, the systems never get tired compared to a human driver (Kalra, N. and Paddock, S. M., 2016).

Today, the majority of traffic accidents are caused by human errors (e.g., distracted driving, speeding, drunk driving, reckless driving, rain, running red lights, etc.). Automated driving is expected to reduce the number of serious or fatal accidents drastically. Approximately 39,000 traffic-related deaths and 4.4 million injuries occurred only in the USA between 2015 and 2016 (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020). Moreover, according to a World Health Organization (WHO) statistic, since 2020, 1.35 million people have died in traffic accidents worldwide (World Health Organization, 2020). It is estimated that with the introduction of fully automated vehicles, road safety should significantly increase by 4 and 5 times, which would affect economic and social development globally (Liu, P., Zhang, Y. and He, Z., 2019).

Although these types of vehicles have been announced for approximately ten years, vehicles with Full Self-Driving (FSD) capabilities have not yet been fully implemented on our roads (Mcfarland, M., 2019). There are already some sectors, such as agriculture, aviation, military, warehouse transport, logistics and public transport, where the systems can be used successfully for selected use cases. In controlled environments, such as in a port like Hamburg, Self-Driving Vehicles (SDV) can be ideally used for loading and unloading ships (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). Another successful example of automated

systems under controlled conditions is the free shuttle rail service at Paris-Charles de Gaulle Airport. An Automatic Light Vehicle (VAL) program was initiated in 2000 to eliminate the need for a driver. In 2007, the operation of the €145 million project was launched with a route of 3.5 km and since its introduction there have been no critical incidents (Boulanger Jean-Louis, 2015). The concept of these automated 1D systems (longitudinal) is now also to be established in the automotive industry by adding a second dimension (lateral). In the aircraft industry, there have already been systems for years that perform various tasks such as take-off and landing procedures completely automatically in 3D space (including the vertical dimension). Due to the continuous development of autopilot functionalities, modern systems show very high safety, reliability and robustness. According to statistics from International Air Transport Association (IATA), the accident rate per million sectors flown for all aircraft types was 0.19 in the years 2010 to 2014 (International Air Transport Association, 2015).

Despite the legal challenges posed by the regulation of automated vehicles, there are other relevant reasons behind the lack of general roll-out. Development companies face a major challenge in developing safe road systems involving hardware and software components that utilize new technologies. Further, the homologation of vehicles by certification companies and approval by the legislator is also highly important in this context to ensure the safety of the systems when they are used on public roads. According to the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), the final approval of a vehicle before it can be released to the public road is a matter of concern (MIT Technology Review Insights, 2019). Moreover, many important areas, such as insurance challenges, social impact, safety, and system reliability need to be resolved before SDVs operate on the road (Bagloee, S. A. *et al.*, 2016).

Until the systems reach a level of maturity that enables complete autonomy, automotive manufacturers and certification companies must find a way to prove and ensure the safety of the systems. A key challenge in this context is the high and continuous performance of the systems under a variety of traffic scenarios. Automated vehicles must be able to operate with the same reliability under a wide variety of weather conditions, such as rain, snow, and fog. Additionally, their function must be guaranteed on the highway as well as in the city or cross-country regions. New development approaches, sensor technologies and software components such as AI have made enormous progress in recent years. Yet despite this, automated vehicles still have problems on the public road because the systems have not yet reached a level of maturity that completely avoids serious to fatal traffic accidents.

It is expected that by 2025, vehicles will reach a maturity level that enables independent acceleration, deceleration, and steering under different driving conditions and environments. Today's assistance systems are primarily designed for operation on highways, but the next-generation systems should be able to handle drives in urban areas or country road sites as well (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

Based on the results and findings of the last decade, the topic is more complex than initially anticipated. Even so, regardless of the broad nature of the topic and the challenges ahead, SDV could rapidly change mobility in the future, creating new ways to travel distances more efficiently, and conveniently. As the most

important factor for a successful introduction, safety requires the highest level of attention throughout the entire product lifecycle.

Barriers to Progression

Risks and Lack of Mitigation

The number of accidents with automated vehicles is increasing since drivers are putting more trust in the system and losing their attention to the road, even though the capabilities of automated vehicles have increased in the last decade. When it comes to a traffic scenario where the vehicle is not able to handle it correctly, human drivers are often not able to interfere within the required time. The risk at the moment is that automated vehicles today cannot handle all traffic scenarios. In the last few years, development companies have realized the high complexity of testing to ensure road safety minimum on the same level as that of a human driver. For this reason, there are no fully automated vehicles available on the market yet. A significant barrier in this context is that the number of traffic scenarios is theoretically infinite, and during the development phase, not everything can be tested in a reasonable time with an economic effort.

The issue of incomplete validation of automated vehicles during the development and homologation processes results in functional limitations or problems on public roads when approved vehicles are used. Without active intervention by a driver, safety-critical scenarios can cause serious accidents. Due to the complexity of the system and the environment as well as a large number of scenarios, they must prove their safety, reliability and robustness before vehicles with higher levels of automation are approved for operation on public roads. Safety is the most important aspect of automated vehicles, as a faulty decision by the system can lead to a fatal accident in the worst case.

Key Issues and Challenges

Replacing a human driver and his individual skills in road traffic is a challenging task as future automated systems must be able to fully capture traffic scenarios and correctly interpret the context. Based on this, actions must be correctly derived and preventive control commands must be carried out. Traditional automotive Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) and new technology companies like Uber and Waymo have been trying to solve the problem for many years (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020). Despite progress, it is still more complex than expected to guarantee road safety in different environmental conditions since automated vehicles allowing drivers to shift control to the system will require extensive safeguards (Takacs, A. et al., 2018). An enormous challenge lies in this aspect, especially when it comes to the development and validation processes of a vehicle for its official approval to begin operating on public roads. This process is known as vehicle homologation and is carried out by legislators or contracted companies such as Technischer Überwachungsverein (TÜV) in Germany, for example (Sjafrie, H., 2020).

In the past, the focus of testing was on the durability of mechanical parts through a certain number of test cases. With the transfer of driving tasks from the driver to the vehicle, the additional hardware and software

functionalities must now be tested against a variety of complex scenarios. The following Figure 1 shows the main differences in the acceptance process of a classic vehicle compared to that of a modern and future vehicle with automation.

Figure 1: Comparison of the vehicle homologation for past versus future.

Recent studies show serious gaps in the safety of AV compared to that of human drivers (Krömker, H., 2019). In addition, serious accidents involving automated vehicles are repeatedly being reported in the media; for example, a public website called Tesla Deaths collects all traffic accidents worldwide with Tesla vehicles and provides basic data about deaths and whether an automated function was the reason for the accident (TeslaDeaths.com, 2021). To avoid these, automated vehicles must be able to correctly detect any traffic scenario, interpret it correctly, and make the right decisions. All real traffic scenarios are different due to the many small details such as environment, weather conditions, position of objects and motion sequences. Even if scenarios are grouped together, the number of scenarios is not testable within a reasonable time and budget (Pek, C., Koschi, M. and Althoff, M., 2019). Since the safe driving distance of a human being is on average 800,000 km until a traffic accident occurs, this would be the minimum benchmark for automated vehicles (Jurgen, R. K., 2013).

At the moment, there is no fully automated vehicle available that can drive in any region worldwide within all different environmental and traffic conditions (Chmielewski, C., 2019). Due to the uniqueness of each real traffic scenario, it is difficult to develop systems with a safety level that is on par with a human (Leitner, A., 2019).

Incorrect System Behavior and Usage

The motivation of this research is to support certification organizations in the safe introduction of automated vehicles in order to identify problems in the systems at an early stage and thus avoid traffic accidents.

Traditional vehicle manufacturing companies are competing to get automated vehicles on the road. New

players such as Google, Uber, and Aptiv are trying to find their place in the field of future mobility by applying their technologies and services; for example, the company GM Cruise is aggressively competing against Waymo to be the first on the market with a fully automated vehicle. As a result of the hype, many companies are rushing into the market to increase their market share without paying enough attention to safety. They are neglecting the performance of functions, leading to significant deviations from the representation of marketing compared to reality; for example, Tesla introduced an Autopilot function on October 9, 2014, and consumers struggled with the limited capabilities in the initial version. The term "Autopilot" of the semi-autonomous system was misleading, and the function led to several accidents (Eliot, L., 2018a). On May 7, 2016, while the Autopilot function was active, a vehicle driver died in a fatal crash when it did not detect the highway crossing tractor-trailer correctly (Yadron, D. and Tynan, D., 2016). Another tragic accident occurred with one of Uber's automated test engineers in 2018 during a nighttime test drive. Figure 2 shows an illustration of the scenario, where the vehicle did not sense a crossing pedestrian on time, and the driver was not actively looking at the street since she was engaged on her mobile phone; consequently, the vehicle hit the pedestrian at about 70 km/h, leading to the pedestrian's death (National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB), 2018). In the case of the traffic accident involving Uber's development vehicle, a combination of two problems occurred. First, the crossing pedestrian was not detected in time by the automated system, and second, the human driver was distracted at the time of the occurrence. Regardless of the failure of the automated system and the test driver, the underlying error was the incorrect behavior of the pedestrian. A crossing should not have taken place because, at the time of the event the Uber vehicle was heading in his direction and the cyclist would have had to wait. Such a circumstance may occur during operations and must be better safeguarded by appropriate measures in the future.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 2: Illustration of Uber crash analysis (National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB), 2018).

The increased conceptual misuse of automated systems by irresponsible drivers in combination with the lack of driver awareness is a new issue. There are many videos on the internet showing hazardous misuse scenarios of these systems. One such example is shown in Figure 3, where an individual is driving in a vehicle with the Autopilot function activated on the highway and is simulating sleeping in the back seat.

Figure 3: Video still of a sleeping driver in the back seat while driving a Tesla with activated Autopilot function (Lambert, F., 2021).

Such behavior is irresponsible and endangers not only all vehicle passengers but also other road participants. Vehicle manufacturers such as Tesla explicitly point to the restriction and correct use of the systems. In the distant future, it should be possible for drivers to sleep while driving. But, until that time comes, vehicle safety must still be significantly increased (Eliot, L., 2018b).

In a video, author Steven Loveday of the website InsideEVs.com shows more examples of an automated vehicle facing serious problems while driving on public roads (Loveday, S., 2021). Figure 4 shows a scenario extracted from the video where the automated vehicle steers directly into a road construction zone, as can be seen from the steering wheel position.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 4: Video still of a construction site issue with a Tesla system (Tesla Raj, 2020).

In the video (time: 06:08 seconds), the driver has corrected the steering wheel to avoid a collision with the construction site. When taking a closer look at the video, the vehicle's navigation path is shown. The incorrect navigation path of the vehicle is well visible in Figure 5. It seems that the vehicle has recognized the barriers, but the navigation path was not correctly calculated. In the described scenario, nothing unfortunate happened because the driver took over at the right moment. But in a worst-case scenario, the same scenario with roadworks in the restricted area and no interference from the driver could lead to a fatal accident with injured or even dead people (Loveday, S., 2021). This is just an example of the many issues automated vehicles face at the moment.

Figure 5: Video still with the incorrect navigation path of a Tesla system (Tesla Raj, 2020).

The problems presented and the consequences resulting from them in the case of an accident are a good motivation to make a contribution to the homologation of automated vehicles. Early identification of problems during the homologation process should prevent future serious traffic accidents on public roads.

From an epistemological point of view, automated vehicles today have not yet reached the maturity level to be operated fully autonomously and therefore need a robust fallback mechanism to intervene quickly and effectively in case of a problem. The increasing number of accidents on public roads where automated vehicles are the cause underlining the problem with the reliability of today's systems.

From an ontological position, systems cannot be fully trusted at this time. Based on the problems with production vehicles, it is obvious that there are weaknesses and gaps in the current homologation process. Due to the high complexity of the systems and the multitude of potential traffic scenarios, current methods are not sufficient to ensure safe operation on public roads. Additional or improved testing methods as part of the homologation process must identify as many problems as possible at an early stage to prevent problems during operation. The safety, reliability and robustness of automated vehicles must at least be equivalent to that of a human driver to reduce the number of traffic accidents.

Outcome and Direction

By addressing the barriers to progression, the overall objective of this research is to support certification organizations to assess the performance of automated vehicles in a standardized and scalable way; thus delivering a safer, more reliability and robust alternative to existing validation approaches. With a generic design, the solution should allow the use of the method on different vehicle types, make and models. This also includes vehicles like trucks. Critical scenarios, which have been identified on public roads, are to be used as the basis for an assessment. A human driver's objective sense of safety should also be considered. This research does not analyze Root Cause Analysis (RCA) for safety-critical scenarios identified in the validation method, nor does it analyze the reasons behind the driver's uncomfortable feelings. Human drivers using the system must be trained and made aware of the potential issues with automated vehicles.

Moreover, the methodology, hardware, and software available are not designed to be used in public fleets or by public drivers; furthermore, the system's availability should only be used in safe environments and under controlled circumstances to avoid any kind of safety-critical issues.

Research Approach and Hypothesis

The best option to validate vehicles is to perform testing on public roads because it has the highest option of realism. At this time, automated vehicles cannot be tested on public roads in a safe and reliable way as part of the homologation process to demonstrate their safety, reliability, and robustness. Today, the validation of automated vehicles as part of the homologation process is mainly carried out on closed proving grounds and in laboratory environments. Due to complex setups of test facilities for artificial simulation of defined scenarios, only a limited number of tests can be executed.

In order to complete the homologation process, a solution is required for the safe validation of automated vehicles and the acceptance of the associated new technology by drivers. Therefore, real traffic scenarios can be used to objectively assess the performance of the systems. This is vitally important because any automated system will be required to at least match, if not surpass, human driver performance; indeed, humans can drive hundreds of thousands of kilometers without an accident in a wide variety of traffic environments and complex road conditions. By using National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) statistics for 2021, DaSilva (2023) calculated that there were 5,250,837 crashes in the USA for a distance traveled of 4,671,925,632,000 km. Human drivers have a crash rate of 0.000181%, which indicates that per mile, human drivers are 99.999819% crash-free. This presents remarkable reliability for safety if one considers all the different traffic scenarios and environmental conditions. Based on these facts, a human driver can be assumed to be an excellent benchmark for acceptance, since automated vehicles must have at least the same level of safety to be accepted by legislators and customers. Based on this idea, the following hypothesis emerges and will be tested: By comparing the driving behavior of humans and automated vehicles, can critical traffic scenarios can be identified on public roads?

Contributions to Knowledge to Achieve the Outcome

The contribution to the automotive safety community is a holistic validation framework for a standardized and safe assessment of automated vehicles on public roads with independent measurement components.

The result is a generic approach that may be used for all levels of automation, starting from simple assistance functions to full AV; furthermore, a new testing method for automated vehicles provides a reliable and accurate assessment of the system performance based on human behavior as part of the homologation process on public roads in a standardized, scalable and safe way.

Furthermore, the result is a custom-developed measurement device for steering actions which enables the detection of critical and uncomfortable traffic scenarios based on the deviation of control actions between humans and machines.

The original contribution of this research is a safe validation method to identify safety-critical events and record the well-being of the driver on public roads. The objective analysis and assessment of critical traffic scenarios identified when using automated functions in a production vehicle on public roads offer an additional contribution to the future validation of automated vehicles.

Academically, the underlying framework derived from the above provides a foundation for the development of further components to measure behavioral differences. As a consequence, this research unlocks the way to the standardized collection of data during test drives and provides a solid starting point for conducting long-term studies to collect statistical evaluations based on different vehicles and environmental conditions.

Outline

This research is divided into three parts. A review of the current literature is conducted in Chapter 1 of the first part in order to identify the requirements and expectations for automated vehicles. Chapter 2 discusses the topic of road safety and the challenges associated with its development and validation. A review of the state-of-the-art methods for validating automated vehicles and their advantages and disadvantages is presented in Chapter 3. The second part of this research presents a theoretical framework based on identified gaps in the literature. This framework addresses the gaps in the validation of automated vehicles in the context of homologation. The foundation of the newly developed SS, which is based on the comparison of behavioral differences between a human driver and an automated system, is explained in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 describes the implementation of this concept using the SSW component for the independent detection of behavioral differences in steering movements up to a safety-critical level. In the third part of the research, the implemented method is validated. In Chapter 6, four different traffic scenarios are described, which were identified during test drives with a production vehicle on public roads using the SSW component. Based on the recorded data, Chapter 7 discusses the new findings regarding the safety, robustness and reliability of a production vehicle with automated functions. Furthermore, the advantages, disadvantages and implications of the SS and the validated SSW component are explained in Chapter 8. At the end of the research, the conclusion summarizes the significance of the work and its contribution to knowledge. In addition, suggestions for further research activities and optimization potentials for the SS and the SSW component are provided.

Part 1:
Literature Review

Chapter 1

Safety Expectations for Automated Vehicles

1.1 Need for Better Safeguarding of ADAS/AD Systems

1.1.1 Current Statistics

There is an increasing number of accidents caused by the use of automated vehicles. In recent years, various assistance functions such as LKA or ACC have become well-established on the market, but statistics also show that there are problems with these systems. Systems are approved for the commercial market which do not operate correctly under certain conditions or traffic scenarios, causing accidents. In a study released by the American Automobile Association (AAA) organization, researchers discovered that on average, problems with ADAS occurred every 12.87 km throughout 4,000 km of public road driving (American Automobile Association, Inc., 2020). Due to low reliability of the systems, scenarios can quickly end in disaster if the driver is briefly distracted or overly confident in the safety of the automated system. For the topics of road safety and future capacity needs, there is already a large amount of research available. This is not surprising since the topic of ADAS/AD has generated a great interest among many people, as an analysis of 100,000 posts on various social media has shown. Since the first announcement of automated vehicles by Google in 2010, the number of posts on this topic has doubled per year (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018); however, current data shows that better safeguarding of systems is necessary to make the use of automated systems safer in the future (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2022).

A comprehensive overview of the current state of the development and safety validation of automated vehicles, including its associated findings and challenges, with a particular focus on the validation of the systems during the homologation process, is needed to elucidate gaps in knowledge and indicate a pathway to a new solution. The most important theories and hypotheses in the field are analyzed, compared and critically evaluated. The gaps and weaknesses of current approaches are identified and presented. The findings are used as the foundation for developing a new methodology to assess the performance of automated systems in terms of safety, robustness, and driver comfort in an optimized and scalable way.

1.1.2 Road Safety Issues

In previous research, Cavoli et al. (2017) created an overview of the frequency of topics for automated vehicles. In the first three positions of Figure 6, the topics of Road Safety, Legal & Regulatory Issues, and Public Acceptability/Perceptions/Expectations appear as most relevant.

Figure 6: Related topics for automated vehicles.

In the context of this research, the focus is on Road Safety. The keywords in Figure 7 were primarily used to identify relevant literature sources during the research. The selection of the search terms was carried out successively on the basis of listed keywords in relevant journals and papers, which play a significant role in the field of road safety. In order to focus on the most important terms, a weighting based on frequency was introduced. The frequency and associated relevance of a search term are shown in the following graphic by means of size. These five search terms, along with their synonyms, received the highest weight:

- Automated vehicles
- Safety
- Critical events
- Testing methodology
- Public road testing

Figure 7: Keyword cloud with the most important search terms.

One of the main objectives and motivations for automated vehicles is to reduce traffic accidents, according to authors such as Herrmann, Brenner and Stadler (2016), Smith (2019), and Denton (2020). According to some experts, equipping vehicles with intelligent driver assistance or completely autonomous functionalities should ultimately lead to a 90% drop in road accident rates, a 60% reduction of carbon dioxide emissions (due to efficient trajectory planning), and savings of more than 1 billion hours per day for commuters around the world (Takacs, A. *et al.*, 2018). Automated vehicles can provide a huge reduction in serious accidents according to traffic statistics. In 2019, about 39,000 people died in the USA only (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020). Worldwide, the number is much higher. Of course, with automated vehicles, existing drivers are looking forward to being able to drive from point A to B without any interactions. This is also an immense opportunity for the industry to grow the mobility sector because with automated chauffeurs, new groups such as the elderly or people without a driving license could have access to mobility (Liu, P., Zhang, Y. and He, Z., 2019).

1.1.3 Crash Statistics

The USA Department of Transportation's NHTSA released in 2019 a report with statistics on traffic crashes involving automated technologies in passenger vehicles. The analysis includes data from 2011 to 2015 in the USA. In the report, different safety systems such as Lane Departure Warning (LDW), Lane Keeping Assist (LKA), and Lane Centering Assist (LCA) are grouped into one technology group called "Lane Keeping" because all three systems are related to the proper positioning of the vehicle in a lane. This approach allows a good comparison of the different groups to avoid accidents. Subsequently, the frequency of accidents in which the individual systems were active can be used to draw conclusions about the robustness and maturity of the systems. Higher accident values for a group indicate that this type of system was unable to prevent an accident and, therefore still has potential for future optimization (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2019). The following table shows the different groups of the range:

Table 1: Safety systems grouped by technologies.

	Collision Avoidance Technology Groups	Safety Systems
1	Forward Collision Prevention	Forward Collision Warning (FCW) Crash Imminent Braking (CIB) Dynamic Brake Support (DBS)
2	Lane Keeping	Lane Departure Warning (LDW) Lane Keeping Assist (LKA) Lane Centering Assist (LCA)
3	Blind Zone Detection	Blind Spot Detection (BSD) Blind Spot Intervention (BSI) Lane Change/Merge Warning (LCM)
4	Forward Pedestrian Impact	Pedestrian Automatic Emergency Braking (PAEB)
5	Backing	Rear Automatic Braking (RAB) Reverse Automatic Braking (RvAB) Rear Cross Traffic Alert (RCTA)

Table 2 lists the crashes, fatalities, Maximum Abbreviated Injury Scale (MAIS 1-5), Property-Damage-Only Vehicles (PDOV), and costs to society by the categories previously described. The MAIS rating system describes the maximum injury severity of a vehicle accident using the Abbreviated Injury Scale (AIS) levels. MAIS 0 means no injury, and the highest level describes one or more severely injured persons.

Table 2: Annual impact by advanced driver-assistance systems (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2019).

	Safety Systems	Crashes	Fatalities	MAIS 1-5 Injuries	PDOVs	Societal Costs (2017 \$)
1	FCW/DBS/CIB	1,703,541 29.4%	1,275 3.8%	883,386 31.5%	2,641,884 36.3%	\$132.45 B
2	LDW /LKA/LCA	1,126,397 19.4%	14,844 44.3%	479,939 17.1%	863,213 11.9%	\$232.17 B 30.4%
3	BSW/BSI/LCM	503,070 8.7%	542 1.6%	188,304 6.7%	860,726 11.8%	\$31.72 B 4.2%
4	PAEB	111,641	4,106	104,066	6,985	\$61.29 B

		1.9%	12.3%	3.7%	0.1%	8.0%
5	RAB/RvAB/RCTA	148,533	74	35,268	231,317	\$5.63 B
		2.6%	0.2%	1.3%	3.2%	0.7%
	Combined	3,593,182	20,841	1,690,963	4,604,125	\$463.26 B
		62.0%	62.2%	60.3%	63.3%	60.7%

The table shows that during the five-year period (2011 to 2015) under review, there were an average of 5.8 million traffic crashes in the USA. These crashes resulted in an average of 33,477 fatalities, 2.81 million MAIS 1-5 injuries, and 7.28 million PDOVs per year. The annual cost to society of crashes was \$763 billion. These statistics show the extent of traffic accidents in the USA alone and the enormous potential that a reduction of accidents with the help of automated vehicles can have for society. At the same time, the figures also show that automated systems do not operate flawlessly. The example of the LDW/LKA/LCA safety systems alone shows that these automated functions were used in 1,703,541 crashes.

The safety, robustness and reliability of the systems are underlined by current statistics from 2022. The NHTSA reports that a total of 392 accidents were recorded in the USA between July 1, 2021 and May 15, 2022 (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, 2022). The statistics partially take into account assistance and self-driving systems.

1.2 Transition to Automated Transportation

1.2.1 *The Reality of the Current Rollout Status*

In the last decade, there were several marketing announcements that fully automated capabilities would soon be available, or that tests were already available for selected drivers. There is a slight difference between what was expected in reality and what is available. McFarland from CNN Business (2019) published an article that summarized the promises and the reality in the last few years because a lot of companies that had already announced vehicles equipped with enhanced automation functions a few years ago failed to deliver on those promises. In reality, there are only vehicles with driver assistance functions, while some brands provide the first functions for partial automation in production use; however, reaching full automation is a different challenge because new technologies and methodologies are required; furthermore, experts like Thomas Sedran, head of Volkswagen commercial vehicles, mentioned in an interview with Reuters that full AV will never happen globally (Denton, T., 2020). Sedran based his prediction on the technological and legal challenges; however, these may be solved in the future if one considers the progress made in recent years. Sedran's claim must be viewed very skeptically because there are too many factors influencing the breakthrough of automated systems, and currently no one can really say whether it will happen or not. At present, the prospect of fully automated vehicles appearing on the road is a long-term achievement. Bradley and Preston (2020) even say that it may not even happen in the next few decades because a worldwide

rollout is a tremendous challenge. A similar view is expressed by Greene (2021), who considers fully automated vehicles to be unrealistic in the near future.

With more vehicles equipped with automated functions, the risk of accidents is potentially increasing. Higher automation brings higher risk because it enables humans to do different activities while driving (Akamatsu, M., 2019). The result of this freedom is that people lose their attention on the road, and they are not capable of taking over in case of a critical scenario (Young, M. S. and Stanton, N. A., 2023); furthermore, when thinking about elderly people or children using the vehicles, a fallback scenario where the passenger takes over the vehicle control would not be an option (Wadhwa, V. and Salkever, A., 2017).

Development companies work on different concepts to solve these issues, for example, with remote agents taking over in a scenario where the vehicle is not capable of operating correctly anymore (Maurer, M. *et al.*, 2016). This solution could help in scenarios where the automated vehicle was able to stop itself in a safe way. This would not be an option for time-critical scenarios; for instance, the Uber scenario described before, where a human driver needs to act within milliseconds. This circumstance is a clear indication that automated vehicles need to be capable of acting in a safe way in a critical scenario. As stated by Bradley and Preston (2020), safety is the highest objective.

1.2.2 *History and Successful Implementation*

The development of AV is not a new topic since the first ideas with electromagnetic wire buried underground were born in the 1940s. The technology was intended to steer vehicles automatically on highways, for example as illustrated in Figure 8. In the next few years, companies like Daimler AG came up with futuristic driverless concepts for autonomous systems (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 8: Illustration of the impression of autonomous driving (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).

In the early days, research and development companies figured out that several new sensor types such as camera, radar, lidar are required to track environmental activities and calculate real-time actions. The

Defense Advanced Research Project Agency (DARPA) achieved the first real success with fully automated vehicles in the urban challenge on a desert course in 2007 (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

In the last decade, the major vehicle manufacturing companies announced that there would be vehicles performing driving tasks under specified environments without human interaction, but the driver would still be able to override actions.

The complete autonomy of a system has already been applied to Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) for years. These systems can operate autonomously without a crew on board and are capable of performing all phases of a flight from takeoff to landing on their own. Usually, there is the possibility to take control of these systems by remote control and perform manual navigation and operation (Jha, A. R., 2017). Similar concepts exist in the automotive industry for automated vehicles. The key difference in application is the time factor, as vehicles require very rapid intervention when a critical problem occurs (Maurer, M., Gerdes, C. and Lenz, B., 2016).

1.2.3 Replacing a Human Driver

The automotive industry is trying to replace the human driver with an automated system to increase road safety and make daily traveling more efficient (International Transport Forum, 2015). Although this is a way to open mobility services to a broader range of people, it also brings a broad spectrum of existing and new challenges (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). Replacing a human driver with an automated system remains a complex open problem since humans can perfectly solve all traffic scenarios in general under all different environmental conditions. A human driver captures the environment through their eyes, a function similar to a camera, and derives actions through their brain, based on existing knowledge. The resulting action is performed via hands and feet.

Development companies such as OEMs, Tier suppliers (T1-3), and software vendors try to replace human know-how with sensors and software. Based on Michon's (1985) behavioral model, three different levels of information are necessary for the replication of human driving behavior. In his model, he divides them into operational, tactical and strategic levels. This fundamental method has been realized by Eliot (2018c), who describes a framework for AV based on the three levels of Michon's model, to show the different components required for such a system. From Eliot's point of view, these three AI components are essential to replicate a human driver:

- Tactical AI: This element deals with moment-to-moment decisions based on a virtual model and creates an action plan.
- Strategic AI: With this type of component, it is a larger aspect to determine and decide what a vehicle must do.
- Self-aware AI: For the continuous assessments of decisions, this component is used for self-monitoring to ensure that the system is working correctly.

The framework is based on the idea that AI is required to solve the overall statement. His framework consists of five core components required to replace the capabilities of a human driver:

- Sensor capture
- Sensor fusion
- Virtual world model
- System action plan
- Controls activation

Figure 9 shows the entire framework from the acquisition of data using various hardware sensors, through the three different AI components, as well as the final control activations. The representation also shows the sequential dependency between individual components; however, currently, the AI models are not sufficient to implement Eliot's (2018c) model.

Figure 9: Illustration of the big picture framework for AI driverless cars (Eliot, L., 2018c).

A similar model is described by Concas et al. for the generic architecture of automated vehicles (Concas, F. et al., 2020). In their opinion, complex machine learning models also form the basis of automated vehicles, similar to the framework of Eliot. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) are used for the development of an algorithm, which creates complex connections between the different layers based on training data. From Concas et al. point of view, ANN-based systems are black boxes. Due to the complexity of the architecture and the number of layers, it is very difficult, and even impossible, to understand the final decision. This also makes it difficult to debug and eventually resolve errors in the systems.

The use of AI-based systems has made enormous progress in recent years, as the automotive industry envisions it as a key to developing vehicles with higher automation levels (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and

Stadler, R., 2018). A pioneer in the field is the company called Uber. The company has been working on the development of automated vehicles for years. In 2020, however, Uber discontinued this program until further notice. One conclusion drawn by experts like Gwyn (2021) in this context is that the complexity of developing and validating the systems is underestimated; however, regardless of the progress, there are still various problems that need to be solved before vehicles can have reliability and dependability of a human driver. Replacing the human driver poses a number of major challenges for engineers since humans have the ability to solve complex scenarios quickly. As such, with the use of automated systems, the automated system must be able to correctly recognize the environment, make fast decisions based on this, and then perform the appropriate actions (Takacs, A. et al., 2018).

1.3 The Way to Automated Vehicles

1.3.1 Society of Automotive Engineers Framework

The SAE organization has provided one of the best-known definitions for automated driving vehicles. The classification of vehicles into six levels has become the de facto standard in the literature and is used as a reference in most works. Figure 10 shows a representation of this classification that can be found in the work of Favarò et al. (2017). Level 0 of the framework classifies classic vehicles that have no assistance or automated functions. Here, all tasks for the execution of a journey must be carried out by the human driver. At the highest level, level 5 classifies automated vehicles that are completely autonomous and can be operated without any interaction with a human. This type of vehicle must be able to safely perform all traffic scenarios in all environmental conditions. In addition, since this type of vehicle does not require a human driver, it is possible to completely redesign the interior of the vehicle as well (Sjafrie, H., 2020). Since there is no longer a classic driver, the steering wheel and pedals, as well as all other vehicle controls, become superfluous.

The framework is basically divided into two main categories. In the first category, which goes from level 0 to 2, the environment is actively observed by the human driver during a journey. If a problem occurs, the driver can intervene at any time. In the second category, which ranges from level 3 to 5, the environment is monitored by the system. The driver moves into the background and, in the case of level 3 vehicles, only has to be able to intervene in absolutely exceptional cases. At level 4, the vehicle does not require a human driver, but it must be usable in a defined operating environment, such as on a highway (Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A., 2017). The last and highest level of automation refers to fully automated vehicles. These types of vehicles represent the ultimate goal and have the potential to permanently change the mobility of the future.

Figure 10: Illustration of the SAE framework for automated vehicles (Favarò, F., Eurich, S. and Nader, N., 2017).

Critical voices towards the SAE framework can be found in the literature, for example Loro (2018). A level-by-level view as in the SAE can partly be misleading for the end consumers since a vehicle can provide functions at different levels. An alternative framework, proposed by Loro (2018), performs the classification based on two dimensions. On the horizontal axis, the role of the human is divided into three categories: monitor, standby, and passenger. This subdivision enables a clear assignment of tasks to a driver and his responsibilities. On the y-axis, the operating environment is described on the basis of a 10-level scale. On the first level, the ODD is very limited, as it is, for example, in the case of a train journey. The track sections are always the same and the environmental conditions influence the operation only in absolutely exceptional cases. On the highest level of the y-axis is the unrestricted use of the system, which is expressed by the value 10. Systems supporting this value and supporting the role of "Passengers" in human activity can be classified as fully automated vehicles. This representation can be equated with level 5 of the SAE framework. Figure 11 shows the structure of his model.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 11: Illustration of an alternative framework for the SAE levels of automation (Loro, A., 2018).

Loro's proposal includes 30 different classification options compared to the existing six levels of the SAE framework. A classification of the x-axis can be done very easily. For the values on the y-axis, the stiffening becomes more complex, similar to the SAE Framework, since an exact delimitation of the individual ODDs is necessary. In reality, this can often lead to very complex and mixed representations.

Whether a separation of functionalities based on levels or a matrix is understandable for end consumers in reality must be questioned very critically. The many differentiation possibilities can lead to confusion, as drivers are unlikely to be able to determine the boundaries accurately and, in the worst case, this can lead to misinterpretation. This distinction is likely to be very difficult, especially in Loro's proposal, because the ODD is divided into ten different levels, increasing the potential for incorrect assignment by the end consumer. In the worst case, this ends in an accident if the driver believes that the automated vehicle can solve the critical scenario on its own. From this point of view, there should only be two options. First, the driver must actively control the vehicle and is only assisted by the system to increase safety. In the second option, the vehicle must perform all driving activities independently, and the driver never has to intervene and therefore does not need any driving expertise.

1.3.2 Relation Between Key Terms

As there is a great deal of confusion between the different terms in the literature, it is essential to discuss the different relations between the terms used in the literature. Engholm et al. (2017) have shown the connection of frequently used terms in an illustration, which is shown in Figure 12. The blue circle shows the different levels of automation. In addition, the green circle shows data communication types. This form of representation provides an excellent delineation, as it looks beyond the classic stages of the SAE framework.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 12: Illustration of the relationship between key terms (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017).

Connected Vehicle. The authors refer to a connected vehicle when the vehicle connects to other vehicles or infrastructure. In the literature, there are three terms that are frequently used in this context. Vehicle to Vehicle (V2V) communication deals with the exchange of data between vehicles (Jurgen, R. K., 2013). Vehicle to Infrastructure (V2I) exchanges data with fixed existing infrastructure systems (Sjafrie, H., 2020). This can be, for example, a traffic light system to inform a vehicle about the condition of a poorly visible intersection at an early stage. The last term, Vehicle to Everything (V2X) covers all remaining communication types such as external services (Eliot, L., 2018a). An example would be a video streaming service like Netflix to view a movie while driving.

Cooperative Vehicle. The term cooperative vehicle is another form of classification in which a vehicle exchanges data with other vehicles or infrastructure to enhance the safety and performance of other systems; for example, the notification of a traffic accident to the following vehicles would be sent to the vehicles early about the impending problem.

Finally, the authors Engholm et al. (2017) have also drawn a comparison with the SAE levels already mentioned to show the classification of different vehicle types. Table 3 shows their form of presentation, which clearly delineates the different terms. If the term "driverless" is used, for example, it always refers to a vehicle that can be operated without a human driver. This classification is particularly helpful as it maps the SAE levels with the terms.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Table 3: Type of vehicle mapped to society of automotive engineers level (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017).

Technology Approach. There are basically two thrust directions that are being followed in the market for the development of automated vehicles, according to Takacs (2018). The first approach is based on the camera-first approach, which is followed by companies such as Tesla, Mobileye and Almotive. Here, information extraction from the video streams is used to obtain all relevant data necessary for controlling the vehicle. This approach is similar to human capabilities (Schaub, A., 2018). A major challenge in the use of these systems is the handling of bad weather conditions like rain or snow, as well as difficult light conditions like at night.

The second approach, the lidar-first approach, has been adopted since the beginning by companies like Waymo, Uber, and Drive.ai. Here, 3D point clouds are used to accurately determine the distance of objects (Bagloee, S. A. et al., 2016). There are many opinions in the literature as described by Hairong (2019), Shaoshan et al. (2018) and Plaza (2018) that contrast one approach with the other and vice versa. In the next few years, it will become clear in which direction the companies will go, as both systems clearly present a set of drawbacks that need to be overcome.

1.3.3 Software Defined Vehicles

The quantity of software in modern vehicles is already considerable and is predicted to be the next evolution of the automotive industry, mainly driven by the introduction of automated vehicles. According to Herrmann, Brenner and Stadler (2018), this trend will continue in the coming years. The authors further forecast that the volume of software in a vehicle will double every 18 months in the future. In this approach, cars will exchange safety-related information such as obstacles or accidents via V2V or V2I communication to increase road safety (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). This assumption shows the need to establish new processes for the development, validation, and monitoring of automated vehicles. The establishment of a sustainable and continuous process for monitoring vehicles will presumably play a key role in the future to ensure acceptance by legislators and consumers. Only if the systems have a high level of safety and reliability will mass market penetration be possible. Regardless of the benefits and additional safety aspects of V2V and V2I technologies, this approach will not solve today's challenges in autonomous vehicle development and validation because it must always be assumed that automated vehicles must also be capable of operating offline should V2X communication not be available or have a temporary malfunction. These new communication technologies with the vehicle must also be validated as part of the

homologation process to ensure that the system responds correctly in the case of an accident report, for example.

1.3.4 Step-by-Step Approach

Traditional vehicle manufacturers try to develop and bring automated vehicles to the market through a conservative step-by-step approach. As mentioned in Section 1.2.2, the development of automated vehicles began around the 1940s. Pioneers in the field recognized the potential of such systems early on. Due to technical challenges, it has taken several decades for sensor and hardware technologies to reach a level that is closer to the goal of a level 5 vehicle (Eliot, L., 2018a).

There are basically two different approaches to reaching the final goal of automated vehicles. Traditional manufacturers try to approach the challenge step by step by successively introducing individual functions; and with the findings, they can expand the capabilities of the functions (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). An example is the ACC function which continuously measures the distance to the target vehicle and adjusts the vehicle's speed according to the vehicle ahead by accelerating or braking maneuvers. This function was first introduced by manufacturers in the premium segment and has become established in the mass market with enormous success in recent years. By introducing new functions, manufacturers are trying to achieve a safe rollout of automated vehicles over time.

A completely different approach was taken by technology companies like Waymo over 10 years ago (Maurer, M. *et al.*, 2016). Waymo's original approach is to directly develop a level 5 vehicle, skipping all upstream stages. According to Waymo, different approaches and technologies, as well as software solutions, are required to achieve level 5 vehicles compared to solutions used for level 1 to 4 vehicles (Coppola, P. and Esztergár-Kiss, D., 2019).

In 2016, Frazzoli (2018) presented at the ETH Zurich the comparison of strategies of vehicle manufacturers and technology companies. This comparison is represented in Figure 13. This figure shows the presence of a danger zone, where drivers are overconfident in the system, and as such, they do not dedicate the attention required for the level of automation of the vehicle. The figure also shows the different approaches taken by technology and vehicle manufacturers; whilst the former wish to start on level 5 to reach the final objective; although they are offering services in level 4 because of current limitations. On the other hand, vehicle manufacturers have been working to develop vehicles with automated functions as an add-on.

Figure 13: Illustration of the different strategies of car manufacturers and technology companies (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

1.4 Relationship between Human Behavior and Driving Performance

Human capabilities are unique since we learn over time and can adapt and apply our know-how in a flexible and fast way to a multitude of new scenarios. The brain is the center of understanding, knowledge, and decisions. Through the continuous accumulation of experience and transformation into knowledge, the human brain is able to learn from the past and derive improvements for the future. The image information captured by the eyes is processed by the brain and, as a result passed on to the human actuators like hands, arms, legs, feet, eyes and head so as to move and perform the necessary actions in a traffic scenario. A driver captures 99% of the information necessary to complete a drive safely through the eyes (Takacs, A. et al., 2018).

In order to replicate the accuracy of a human, the CEO of Nvidia, Jen-Hsun Huang, argued that an accuracy of 99.999999% is required by automated vehicles to cover most traffic scenarios (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). It is expected for machines to perform with accuracy at least equal to that of human drivers; in fact, they are supposed to be two times safer to be accepted and allowed on public roads (Liu, P., Zhang, Y. and He, Z., 2019). Further, they must navigate any traffic scenario under changing environmental conditions; e.g., snow, rain, fog, ice (Pek, C., Koschi, M. and Althoff, M., 2019).

Automated vehicle development companies are trying to replicate the sensing capabilities of a human through various types of sensors. 3D video and IR cameras are used to capture image information. It is possible to detect objects at a distance of more than 50 meters using lidar or laser scanners. Distances are determined by different mid-range and long-range radar sensors. Ultrasound sensors are used to measure precise distances in the immediate surroundings of the vehicle. Figure 14 shows a typical sensor configuration for automated vehicles. The schematic diagram is a representation published by Audi (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 14: Illustration of the different sensor types in automated vehicles (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

Each sensor technology has its advantages and disadvantages. Through a combination, one tries to achieve the best possible detection of the environment. Each manufacturer uses different configurations, which differ in the number of individual sensors and positioning. Experts and companies are not in complete agreement regarding the necessary sensor technology. Most manufacturers, with the exception of Tesla, see lidar sensors as a fixed component for achieving higher levels of automation. Tesla recently announced that it would dispense with a radar sensor for measuring distance in new models. The manufacturer completely relies on a camera-based system. Experts like Hairong (2019) believe that such an approach is a major challenge in difficult environmental conditions such as snow, fog, or rain. In the worst case, there can be no lanes at all. These restrictions make positioning a vehicle considerably more difficult (Getahun, T. *et al.*, 2018). An example of challenging conditions is shown in Figure 15 below, where the camera is completely covered by snow and ice (Coelingh, E. and Nilsson, J., 2018).

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 15: Photograph of an iced vehicle due to bad weather conditions (Coelingh, E. and Nilsson, J., 2018).

The discussions about which technologies will be required to achieve level 4 and level 5 vehicles are extensive and multi-layered. To exclude Tesla's approach in principle is critical, as humans rely on visual input for 99% of their driving (Takacs, A. *et al.*, 2018). Only 1% is covered by acoustic warning perception. This fact should theoretically enable successful implementation.

1.4.1 Human Factors

Over the past decades, human drivers have developed a driving style that enables them to navigate worldwide in all environmental conditions. Despite this, as mentioned in Section 1.1.3 there are a large number of traffic accidents that can be attributed to human error. According to Mueller, Cicchino and Zuby (2020), 94% of accidents today are caused by human driver error. These problems are mainly related to speeding, driving under the influence of alcohol or drugs, and distraction by external factors such as cell phones. If these cases are subtracted from statistics, human error amounts to a relatively small percentage.

When developing automated vehicles with AI components, the systems may learn based on historical data recorded in reality. At the moment, however, it is unsure whether this is an adequate option. Experts such as McFarland (2019) see significant difficulties in bringing automated vehicles to the mass market without a technological breakthrough. There are already approaches like reinforcement learning, which, according to Shaoshan et al. (2018), use a similar pattern as a human to learn new knowledge, which according to Hamilton (2016), decision-making may be based on two different cognitive models. Hamilton (2016) describes these as follows:

System 1 Model

This model corresponds to the primal instinct and is executed automatically without long deliberations.

Necessary decisions can be processed in parallel with the human mind. The results are a rough estimate of the correct decision based on the information acquired initially.

System 2 Model

The second model is a type of decision-making that humans have developed over time. This system is much slower than system 1 and allows only serial processing of information; however, it allows humans to maintain control over the decision. This system also draws on the existing experiences of each individual.

If the two systems are applied to a real example, the following distinction can be made. Imagine a scenario where a deer suddenly jumps out onto the road. System 1 of the cognitive model signals an immediate evasive or braking maneuver to avoid a potential accident. Only moments later will system 2 come into play. This system detects a wide variety of environmental factors, such as oncoming traffic, road conditions, and the animal's movements, and then evaluates which option is the best option in the current scenario-based on the human driver's experience. This behavior mirrors the controlled decision made possible by the second system.

Human decision-making goes one step further, according to Kurzweil (2012). Decisions can be made by nesting them across multiple levels. This possibility makes the human decision system extremely powerful and provides the basis for solving very complex tasks in a very short time.

Via rolling movements of the eyes, the current environment is detected in advance and processed by the brain. Based on the current scenario and experience of the driver, decisions are then made, which are

subsequently executed by steering movements using the hands or pedal actuation via the feet (Eliot, L., 2018c).

Researchers have invested a significant amount of effort to better understand human behavior. Thousands of people have been surveyed on their daily behavior in a wide variety of large-scale studies. Unfortunately, the validity of the results is still limited since the data collection is too imprecise (Cook, D. J. and Krishnan, N. C., 2015). A similar picture exists with a person's behavior while driving. The following factors, according to Eliot (2018c) influence behavior significantly:

- Speed style
- Lane changing style
- Braking style
- Distance style
- Risk style

Chen (2018) describes two other factors that today's automated systems only consider to a limited extent. Humans apply many basic assumptions, such as traffic rules, while driving; conversely, machine systems must learn these rules and the corresponding behavior from scratch; furthermore, in today's automated systems, decisions are made based on the information currently available, constructed mostly from recently acquired sensory information. In contrast, a human brings in memories from the past, which can make decisions more precise.

1.4.2 Human Decisions

On the road, human drivers do not use vehicles appropriately. Every country has a clear set of rules for regulating traffic, which every road participant must follow. But, human drivers adapt their driving behavior to the current scenario-based on their experience. In this context, the term "language of the road" is often used. Drivers of different vehicles communicate with each other using various gestures such as hand or head movements. A similar form of communication is described by Xia et al. (2021) used to communicate with individual pedestrians or groups. These gestures often lead to the violation of basic traffic rules, but in reality, such coordination serves to safely resolve a traffic scenario.

In the context of the development and validation of automated systems, human behavior is a major challenge, since the systems must also take misbehavior into account in the best possible way. This can be, for example, a child suddenly running across the street at a red light, or a pedestrian crossing a street and overlooking another vehicle, as happened, for example, in the case of the UBER accident. When certifying vehicles, such special cases must also be considered, as they can occur under real traffic conditions. Another problem is caused by the arbitrary and extensive behavioral characteristics of human drivers. As long as there is a mixed operation between human drivers and automated vehicles, the systems must be able to safely handle traffic maneuvers regardless of the rules of the road (Wang, X. *et al.*, 2018).

1.4.3 Decision Making Models

In addition to the human behavior outlined in the previous section, it is important to have a basic understanding of how a human makes a decision and what factors influence this decision. Figure 16 shows a decision tree from Takemura (2014), which divides a decision into three main categories.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 16: Illustration of different environments of decision making (Takemura, K., 2014).

In the following lines, the individual categories of the decision tree shown in Figure 16 are explained in more detail and the relevant criteria for a selection are defined.

Decision Under Certainty

In the first main category, a human makes a decision based on available facts and existing experience. There is a high degree of certainty on the part of the decision maker, based on sufficient information and the associated certainty, to be able to assess the condition correctly. The decision maker knows the various alternatives and necessary conditions to achieve a particular outcome. In this type of decisions, measurable and reliable information is available to support the decision and provide certainty (Takemura, K., 2014). The consequences of the decision are usually known. The relationship between cause and effect is known and the future outcome is easily predictable under certain conditions (Rosenfeld, A. and Kraus, S., 2018). As a rule, such prerequisites and conditions are present in routine and repetitive decisions.

In the context of driving, for example, this could be the explicit decision not to reduce speed in bad road conditions such as ice or snow. The driver is aware of the consequences of increased risk, as this is known because of driving training and possibly existing experience.

Decision Under Risk

The second category concerns the explicit decision while the individual is exposed to risk (Bradley, R., 2017). The term risk refers to a combination of frequency and probability of occurrence of a particular hazard, which can be triggered by external or internal events. In addition, risk encompasses the extent and consequences in the case of such occurrences. This includes the threat of damage, injury, or other negative effects. Preventive measures are used as part of risk management to identify external and internal vulnerabilities and to develop options for avoidance or action in any case (Fischhoff, B., 2012); for example, this type of decision occurs when a deer unexpectedly appears in the roadway. As described in Section 1.4.1, the initial response is executed intuitively by system 1 of the cognitive model. The following decision, which is executed by system 2, can be controlled by humans. The human driver behind the wheel can make the decision to avoid the impact on the obstacle by means of an evasive or braking maneuver. But due to

environmental conditions, such as icy roads, the decision could also be to explicitly not perform emergency braking or an avoidance maneuver in order to prevent the vehicle from slipping. A loss of control of the vehicle could lead to a serious accident and have far-reaching consequences for the driver or passengers. In this example, a frontal collision would be the better option from the human's point of view. The same scenario with a human instead of an animal would be much more difficult, as ethical aspects would have to be considered.

Decision Under Uncertainty

In the last main category, a person is not fully aware of what decision to make in a current scenario. There are two subcategories in this category. Human life is characterized by uncertainty, in which a decision must be made without knowing the consequences for the performer or others (Bradley, R., 2017). On the one hand, a decision may be necessary under ambiguity; thus, a purely fact-based decision cannot be made because there are multiple ways in which the scenario can be perceived. The term ambiguity is used in the decision-making process when multiple choices of actions are available and effects or outcomes are not known until a decision is made (Arend, R. J., 2020). The second option concerns decisions that are made under ignorance. This may be due to a lack of experience or because the outcome of the decision cannot be estimated. Ignorance is a particularly strong form of uncertainty. It is usually applied when someone is unable to make a meaningful decision due to a lack of knowledge (Giang, P. H., 2014). In reality, there may also be a mix of options. Takamura (2014) refers to this type of decision-making as "multi-attribute decision-making." With this type of decision-making, the multi-layer model is employed, as described by Kurzweil (2012).

Another aspect of decision-making concerns the weighing of the available attributes. Usually, there are always several options when making a decision (Hamilton, R., 2016). Considering the example of the deer on the roadway from earlier, one attribute category could be safety. This, in turn, can be broken down into different individual attributes such as one's own safety, the safety of other road participants, or the safety of the animal. According to Qudrat-Ullah (2014), the dynamics in which the decision has to be made also play an important role. Figure 17 shows the model established by the author for decision-making in dynamic tasks.

Figure 17: Illustration of a decision-making model in dynamic tasks (Qudrat-Ullah, H., 2014).

As input for a strategic decision, Qudrat-Ullah establishes three factors in her model. On the one hand, the existing knowledge, supported by facilitators and the learning method determines a decision. Applied to the example with the crossing deer, for example, a similar scenario from the past can play an essential role. In addition, other empirical values, such as behavior in poor road conditions, can also be a decisive factor in a decision. The result of a decision led to a continuous learning extension taking into account the previous decisions and performed tasks; for example, if an emergency braking of a vehicle is performed on an icy road and the vehicle starts to skid, this knowledge will be taken into account in future decision processes.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Chapter 2

Road Safety

2.1 Validation and Safeguarding of Automated Vehicles

Regardless of all the achievements in the development of automated vehicles in the last years, validation and safeguarding of the system is the most important topic for the successful introduction of this technology. Without acceptable safety, legislators and consumers would not accept the systems, which could subsequently lead to problems in further development activities. As described by Pek et al. (2019), automated vehicles must always be able to navigate safely under all conditions. Their view is that all traffic scenarios are different, and even if one would group them into clusters, a considerable number of scenarios for a meaningful validation must be tested. Most of the current functions in automated vehicles used on the market today are in the active safety area. They support the driver while driving and intervene when a critical scenario has been detected and the driver is unable to handle it independently or in time. This includes functions such as Emergency Brake Assist (EBA), Blind Spot Warning (BSW), and LKA (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

In a study by Engholm et al. (2017), the graph which is shown in Figure 18 illustrates the influence of different disciplines in automated vehicles. The horizontal axis shows the time frame, and the vertical axis shows the spatial resolution. In this illustration, the topic of safety is shown in the lower-left area. The consequence of an unsuccessfully resolved problem can range from material damage to personal injury. This direct impact is the reason for the high relevance of the topic and the associated safeguarding of the vehicles through sustainable test methods so that problems are detected as early as possible in the overall life cycle.

Figure 18: Illustration of direct and indirect impacts of automated vehicles (Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I., 2017).

The ISO 26262 international standard for safety has defined a framework, shown in Figure 19, which serves as the best practice for securing automated vehicles. The framework is divided into 12 areas and from a

general definition of terms at the top, and it covers the entire life cycle of a vehicle. In the center of the model, areas 4 to 6 represent the V-model of the overall development process. Within areas 5 and 6, there is a subordinate V-model for the development of hardware and software respectively.

Figure 19: V-model of the ISO 26262 (Concas, F. et al., 2020).

Existing models such as the established V-model or international standards such as ISO 26262 are not sufficient, according to Takacs et al. (2018). The authors propose an alternative workflow to better address the new requirements related to the safety of automated vehicles. Figure 20 shows their proposal, which builds on the laws and standards that are continuously aligned with the system and safety requirements during development. The functional requirements derived from these are also synchronized with the technical solutions to ensure consistency. For the validation of the functional requirements, they propose to perform drives on public roads. A scenario-based approach is used for hardware and software validation. For technical validation, fault injection scenarios are executed. The broadly based test approach with different methods and continuous comparison of the results with the different safety requirements is to achieve a better assurance in contrast to the stage-based V-model approach of ISO 26262. The approach of Takacs et al. (2018) seems to be a good alternative to the traditional V-model from the automotive industry, but it also has weaknesses in connection with the continuous provision of new software updates, which are necessary through the use of Over the Air (OTA) updates.

Figure 20: Illustration of an alternative workflow for the validation of safety (Takacs, A. et al., 2018).

2.2 Safety Categories

For automated vehicles, Maurer (2016) explains three types of safety categories that are fundamentally relevant and applicable:

Non-Safety-Relevant

In this type of system, an error does not have any dangerous effects on the human being and his environment. Machine learning systems are already increasingly being used in this area today. An example of this would be general route optimization during a drive. A system can continuously adjust the route based on all known road information such as congestion and accidents. If a less than ideal decision is made, this has no effect on the human or his environment. It usually only leads to an increase in travel time or distance.

Safety-Relevant

The second category includes systems that can be considered safety-relevant, since, in the event of an occurrence, it may be dangerous to people or their environment.

a) Decision-Making Support System. In this type of system, the decision-maker has the choice to accept and implement the system's suggestions. A faulty suggestion will only lead to a problem if the decision-maker accepts the recommendation due to a lack of experience. An example in this context could be the initiation of an emergency-braking event suggested by the system; however, based on the driver's experience in a specific traffic scenario, this could be ignored because the scenario can be resolved without taking the suggested action. Emergency braking could possibly even resolve a secondary accident caused by a rear-ending vehicle or increase criticality in bad weather conditions such as rain or snow.

b) Monitoring and Diagnosis. If a system fails to warn the driver and the problem is not detected otherwise, this can have serious consequences for the person or their environment. An example of this would be the UBER traffic accident, where the automated vehicle failed to detect the pedestrian in time and warn the driver accordingly. Problems in this category can go from a harmless scenario to a dangerous event within seconds.

Safety-Critical

In this category, a failure of the system directly results in harm to people or the environment.

a) Supervised/Correctable Automation. If a decision is executed by a system without additional confirmation and subsequently leads directly to an error that causes harm to people or their environment, this problem is classified in this category. In supervised systems, the driver has the opportunity to correct the system's decision and thus return the vehicle to safe operation; for example, an automated lane change of a vehicle would fall into this category if the action is aborted during execution by the driver and the vehicle is steered back into the original lane. A possible cause for this could be, for example, a vehicle that was not correctly detected by the automated system approaching quickly.

b) Unsupervised/Non-Correctable Automation. This type of safety problem is the most critical variant since no correction is possible if it occurs. The consequence is an immediate danger for the driver or their environment. An example of this could be the incorrect execution of a steering movement in the higher speed range on a highway. If a vehicle were to perform a stronger steering movement toward a guard rail at 130 km/h abruptly, the vehicle would crash into it within milliseconds. Due to the high speed, it would usually not be possible for a driver to prevent this scenario.

2.3 Increasing Trust in Automated Vehicles

There is a general assumption that automated vehicles are safer than those driven by humans (Tiulkin, B. and Kulabukhova, N., 2018). In the literature, there are numerous concerns from experts, such as Maurer et al. (2016) and Chikaraishi et al. (2020), who view the topic of safety skeptically and point out concerns about the potentially dangerous acceptance of the vehicles by consumers. Hardly anyone would be willing to use a system that has obvious problems and that, in the worst case, could even lead to a traffic accident (McQueen, B., 2019).

There are many reports in today's literature and in published traffic statistics about the success and positive effects that have been achieved through the introduction of assistance systems in recent years. A very illustrative example of this is the emergency brake assist, which constantly monitors the current traffic scenario and initiates Automatic Emergency Braking (AEB) in a critical scenario. This function will become standard for all new vehicles in the upcoming years, as airbags and Antilock Braking Systems (ABS) are now. A report from the European Commission on Road Safety estimates the positive effects of different ADAS levels on road safety. With active LKA functions, in which the automated system makes slight corrections to prevent accidents, the reduction in accidents is estimated at 20-30% (Cleij, D., 2021). Through these publications and corresponding marketing activities, as shown in Figure 21, consumer confidence is increasing.

Figure 21: Marketing example for safety features (The Ford Motor Company, 2021).

All the technological advances and new functions are a major contribution to increased road safety and form the basis for future achievements to reach higher levels of automation; however, one aspect that is lost when the new functions become mainstream is the communication and awareness of the limitations of the functionalities (McQueen, B., 2019). Most of today's systems are on levels 1 to 2, based on the SAE classification, and are thus pure assistance systems that support the human driver (Eliot, L., 2019a). The driver must be able to take over in a scenario at any time.

In the future, it will become problematic if the driver is increasingly relegated to the background due to higher automation and only has to intervene rarely or in case of emergency. The rarity of intervention is likely to bring reaction time delay, leading to new hazards at level 3 of the SAE.

This poses particular challenges for development companies and certification organizations because the validation of such systems requires new test approaches due to the complexity and the large number of potential scenarios that need to be tested. In the research project Pegasus, a framework categorizes and describes scenarios. The proposal divides a scenario into five-layer (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020):

- Layer 1 (street level) - e.g., street geometry, topology, condition
- Layer 2 (traffic infrastructure) - e.g., signs, barriers, markings
- Layer 3 (temporal modifications) - e.g., road works
- Layer 4 (movable objects) - e.g., vehicles, road participants, animals
- Layer 5 (environmental conditions) - e.g., weather, light

For example, if unknown corner cases are not identified during the development or acceptance phase, vehicles are delivered with functions that can subsequently cause serious accidents in reality. In the past, there have been an increasing number of serious or fatal accidents at various vehicle manufacturers, where

failure can be attributed to automated functions. A representative example is shown in Figure 22, where a Tesla vehicle failed to correctly detect an overturned truck on a highway. This scenario subsequently led to an accident. In this case, fortunately, no one died or was seriously injured.

Figure 22: Photographs of a Tesla crash into an overturned truck (Stumpf, R., 2020).

The safety of automated vehicles in the future also depends on the confidence of drivers. If the systems are able to drive hundreds of thousands of kilometers without a single problem, the confidence and acceptance of drivers and passengers will probably increase very quickly. The relationship between trust and reliability was investigated by Kazi et al. (2007) in a long-term study using a driving simulator. The results show that trust increases over time. Koustanaï et al. (2012) came to a comparable conclusion in a study of behavioral changes and trust on the basis of a collision warning system. Overreliance on the vehicle will also increase the distraction caused by various activities, which in turn will lead to increased risk if a problem should occur. These results are in line with a study by Zhang et al. (2021), which shows the correlation between increasing trust in an automated system and driver distraction. Wien (2019) outlined in a published study for automated buses that there is a relationship between the characteristics of safety and confidence. Based on his findings, women appear to pay closer attention to these two factors. A representative example of overconfidence is shown in Figure 23 below.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 23: Photograph of conceptual misuses of today's automated vehicles (Rosenblatt, K., 2019).

The driver in the figure uses the functions of the vehicle to take a short nap while traveling with a female passenger. Carrying out such activity leads to a complete loss of attention and can lead to a serious

accident. This example is only one of many that can already be found on the Internet. The manufacturers of the systems explicitly warn in the manuals about the limitations of the functions, but these are often ignored and subsequently become triggers for fatal accidents. Conceptual abuses will always exist and can only be partially mitigated through additional systems, such as interior cameras. According to a report by Szymkowski (2021), Tesla vehicles, for example, will be equipped with such cameras in the future.

With the latest achievements in the hardware and software industry, the capabilities of automated vehicles have significantly improved over the last decade. When a vehicle is automated at a higher level, it is possible for the driver to lose track of the road and engage in various activities during the drive (Kochova, K. and Felipe, M., 2018). Today, drivers are distracted by three types of interaction (Bundy, A., 2019):

- Visual distraction: tasks that the driver must perform to obtain information about the current traffic on the road.
- Manual distraction: tasks that require the driver to release the steering wheel with one or both hands to operate an object or device.
- Cognitive distraction: mental tasks that are not related to the ride and thus cause distraction.

In the future, these driver distractions will no longer exist when vehicles take over all the drivers' tasks. Nevertheless, until that happens, the industry and drivers are in a transition phase comprising significant risks. New risks come with increased driver freedom during driving since there are a few challenges with AV. The two critical challenges are as follows:

- Reliability: The system's reliability needs to be developed in a way that it can handle all traffic scenarios under different road conditions.
- Testing: The system should be certified against all possible traffic scenarios to ensure correct functionality.

2.4 Human versus Machine

The research from Takacs (2018) agrees with Chen et al. and claims that current automated vehicles lack significant safety measures when it comes to the transition between automated and manual control. Various papers reported that automated vehicles at present are 15 - 4000x worse than human drivers in terms of accidents per cumulative mile driven (Liu, P., Zhang, Y. and He, Z., 2019). It is not clear from Liu et al. (2019) how the influence and weighting of different traffic environments, such as driving on a highway compared to a city center, is taken into account. This aspect is essential in the comparison, as there are other reports, e.g., from Dow (2019), which claim that Tesla's Autopilot is 9x safer than a human. In simple traffic conditions like on a highway, this seems realistic. At first glance, these statements seem to be promising if one makes a pure comparison of the kilometers driven. On average, a human driver is able to drive about 800,000 km without any accidents. In comparison, the statistic from Tesla gives an average value of 4.34 million km per accident (Dow, J., 2019). This comparison only corresponds to reality to a limited extent, since today's assistance systems are mainly used on highways, where the complexity of

traffic is limited. In contrast, statistics with human drivers include extended areas such as rural roads and cities. If the statistic included complex environments such as a city, the results would truly be comparable.

Hence, for systems to be operated in the future on public roads, they must be able to demonstrate at least the performance and accuracy of a human driver (Bertram, T., 2019). For the homologation of systems in the area of safety, a concept called Equivalent Level of Safety (ELOS) could be introduced to meet compliance, similar to other industries like in the drone world (Ross, H.-L., 2016).

2.5 Driver Attention and Takeover

One more critical issue in the introduction of automated vehicles to the public is driver awareness about the functional capabilities and their limitations (Gupta, N., Prakash, A. and Tripathi, R., 2011). Limitations of the functions can occur under various environmental conditions of which the driver is not aware (Leitner, A., Watzenig, D. and Ibanez-Guzman, J., 2020).

Recent studies, as reported by Takacs et al. (2018), also show that there are serious safety issues in vehicles with a higher level of automation. One of the reasons for this is the transfer of control from the driver to the vehicle and back again. The current state of development of such systems still requires the driver to be able to take over control in the event of a critical or unknown scenario (Takacs, A. et al., 2018). This procedure is not standardized but demands up to level 3 functions to have a fallback option for the human driver. In reality, this takeover causes safety-critical issues, as drivers are distracted and this leads to a higher Takeover Reaction Time (TORT) in case of a problem (Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A., 2017); furthermore, the vehicle-to-human handover poses another safety-related problem in this context, as humans are often not fast enough to take over the vehicle under certain conditions (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).

2.6 Regulations

Safety functions introduced in the last few years, such as AEB, are already doing an excellent job. Based on a study in China by Tan et al. (2020), these systems have reduced traffic accidents for front-to-rear crashes by 43%. In the USA senate, for example, such statistics play an essential role in expediting the approval of automated vehicles and establishing a regulatory framework. According to a study by the NHTSA, there were approximately 35,000 fatal traffic accidents in America in 2015. In 94% of the accidents, human error can be attributed as the cause (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). The figures presented here are in agreement with the data provided by Maurer (2016) in his work; however, he draws attention to an important point. The introduction of automated vehicles will reduce the number of human-caused accidents to almost zero, but the number of technical errors will increase. The same view is shared by Engholm et al. (2017) as new types of accidents will be caused by the introduction of fully self-driven vehicles. According to Maurer's statistics, only 0.7% of accidents are due to technical failure. In addition, the expanded accessibility to new groups of people will also increase the number of drives. Due to these two factors, the number of total accidents could increase in total, while the relative number of accidents may decrease.

Even though the public looks forward to highly automated vehicles, existing regulations and international standards lack rules on the same. There are already a few international standards and USA regulations in place to address the safety of AV. Figure 24 shows an overview created by Bradley and Preston (2020) with some examples. The table does not cover by far all existing regulations. It is an extract of a few relevant regulations in the field.

Figure 24: Standards and USA regulations for automated vehicles (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020).

Existing functions for automated vehicles up to level 3 rely on human drivers to act as a fallback option in case of a problem or the allowed environmental conditions, also called ODD ends for level 4 vehicles (Forster, Y. et al., 2019). This also requires the current drivers to have a driving license. From a long-term perspective, a new regulation will be required to address all these new challenges. For highly automated vehicles, appropriate testing procedures will be required so that it is as safe as a human driver. These procedures will be fundamental to approving safety for automated vehicles on all levels. Still, higher levels of automation also entail big risks due to the transfer of responsibility to the vehicle.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Chapter 3

State-of-the-Art in System Development and Validation

3.1 Current State of Development

The most significant development of automated vehicles started about ten years ago when a few companies like GMC promised availability by 2019 (Valdes-Dapena, 2017, p.1). Today, one can see significant advancements in assistance systems, but these are still far from FSD vehicles. The key challenges of each automated vehicle development project are described by Tiulkin, B. v. and Kulabukhova, N. v., (2018):

- Speed of data processing, as it is necessary to obtain them in real-time.
- Driving in the absence of road markings.
- Influence of weather conditions and lighting.
- Obscured visual landmarks.
- Actions in an unforeseen scenario.

Lately, achievements in hardware and software have increased the development speed in the field of automated vehicles. New sensor technologies like lidar, radar, ultrasonic and video cameras are supporting object detection (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018); furthermore, new processor technologies enable Graphics Processing Units (GPU) and special systems for AI environment support real-time calculation, which is essential for FSD vehicles (Tiulkin, B. and Kulabukhova, N., 2018). The complex environmental conditions on the road and difficult traffic scenarios are the key challenges that companies developing automated vehicles need to solve; furthermore, vehicles must also understand the “language of the road” since there are many complications that humans overcome with visual communication and by ignoring rules. Another issue concerns communication with other road participants, a critical point mentioned by Wang et al. (2018). The behavior of a human driver is strongly adapted to the current scenario and environmental conditions. Information is usually exchanged with the environment via direct eye contact or hand signals. The size of a neighboring vehicle, like a truck, also influences one's own behavior. For these aspects, there is some research, but the existing implementations do not yet meet the level to enable a smooth traffic flow. As described by McFarland (2019), today's automated vehicles lack the human touch to make driving maneuvers seem natural. A similar view is held by Wang et al. (2018), who also identify problems in today's behavior of automated vehicles compared to human drivers. In addition, he also mentions that existing systems for maneuver control need to be extended to include appropriate methods.

An article from the magazine MIT Technology Review Insights (2019) defines a set of five common sense-driven rules for the operation of an autonomous vehicle:

- Do not hit someone from behind.
- Do not cut in recklessly.
- The right of way is given, not taken.

- Be careful in areas with limited visibility.
- If you can avoid an accident without causing another one, do it.

Presently, there exists no single commercial vehicle with fully automated functions level 5 of the SAE framework that has reached the production stage and is available on the market (Sjafrie, H., 2020). According to Takacs et al. (2018), there is a lot of space for research activities in this field, which must be undertaken in the coming years. Solving the “last mile” is a hard task and will probably take years or even decades. Development companies nowadays are struggling to solve all unknown problems. Eliot (2018c), one of the top experts in the field of AI and AV made a simple but precise statement:

“No AI, no self-driving cars.” (Eliot, L., 2018c, p.23)

This statement is a clear indicator that without the use of AI components in an autonomous vehicle, this system will not be able to operate safely and efficiently on public roads. His personal opinion is currently an unconfirmed hypothesis but there are experts like Grimes (2019) who have a similar opinion. Grimes believes that in about 10 years, there will be more automated vehicles on the road than people behind the wheel (Grimes, R. A., 2019); however, in his view, this breakthrough will require true AI systems that think in a similar way to the human brain. The main problem of both arguments is the lack of information about the solution approaches to overcome the current challenges. Due to the complexity and many influencing factors, an educated guess about a timely breakthrough is purely a guess and cannot be proven. In fact, maybe without a new revolutionary technology breakthrough, there will never be a vehicle without a steering wheel (Mcfarland, M., 2019).

Many different approaches can be taken to ensure safety and robustness. International standardization organizations such as ISO; for example, propose a sustainable validation framework based on the traditional V process. This approach may work in the first step for simple functionalities like ACC or LKA. But as soon as highly complex black box systems are used, the traditional test methods cannot achieve sufficient test coverage with economically justifiable effort.

3.2 Challenges Caused by Unforeseen Scenarios

3.2.1 Edge Problems on Public Roads

The biggest challenge at the moment in the development and validation of automated vehicles is posed by so-called edge problems, corner cases or wicked problems. These terms refer to scenarios that may rarely occur in reality, but nevertheless, they need to be considered (Milford, M., Anthony, S. and Scheirer, W., 2020). These scenarios are usually not identified in the normal development process and only come to light when the vehicle is actually used on the road. Often, edge problems are a chain of several unfavorable factors that come together in a particular scenario and subsequently lead to a problem for a system. Even if certain scenarios are infrequent and one-time occurrences, they still pose a safety risk to people and their

environment. Nonetheless, such cases must be identified and resolved as best as possible if the systems are to be scaled up worldwide; otherwise, more problems would occur and AV acceptance by society would thus decline.

The technology giant Google reported a few edge cases, which are extremely difficult to solve; for example, stop lights in combination with sunset, junctions, and heavy traffic is just one combination that makes the assurance of safety difficult. Figure 25 presents a scenario where a green traffic light is covered by a red ball.

Figure 25: Photograph of an edge problem on public roads (Williams, C., 2016).

Automated systems must also be able to correctly detect such unusual scenarios and perform the appropriate actions. In the example shown in Figure 25, the traffic scenario is only critical to a limited extent since the main lane has a green light. If a similar scenario arises but with the lights reversed, this could result in a fatal traffic accident.

The challenges in the context of development lie in the identification of unknown scenarios as well as the reproduction of known scenarios, which were already recognized in the past (Bertram, T., 2019). There are a number of general challenges faced by developers of automated systems. Often, these problems occur in connection with the environment or the existing lighting conditions. When driving against a low sun, fading can occur; a scenario that can occur especially in the morning or evening hours (Tian, Y. *et al.*, 2017). Figure 26 shows an example where two out of three traffic lights are not visible to the camera due to direct sunlight. If such information is evaluated by the system, a wrong decision with fatal consequences can be made too quickly. The development of new technology like lidar in recent years has provided additional options to deal with these limitations and issues.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 26: Photograph of challenging light conditions on a public road (Williams, C., 2016).

Since AI-based systems learn on the basis of existing data and derive a network for decision-making, if a scenario that was not taught to the system during the training phase occurs during a real drive, this can lead to system deactivation or failure (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020). Having a theoretically infinite number of traffic scenarios makes covering all of them impossible (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018).

3.2.2 Influencing Factors

External environmental factors such as weather conditions influence the recognition and behavior of a scenario. During a drive, a system needs to handle many conditions, which makes the development of automated systems considerably more difficult, as large differences can occur depending on the region and time of year. These aspects must be taken into account during validation, which considerably increases the testing effort for certification organizations. In the following, the most important influencing factors with some sample values are listed, which must all be taken into account in the development, validation and approval:

Weather (Bizon, N., Dascalescu, L. and Tabatabaei, N. M., 2014):

- Sun
- Rain
- Dust
- Sand
- Snow
- Fog

Roadway (Isermann, R., 2017):

- Highway
- Suburbs
- Inner-city
- Public road

Environment (Sjafrie, H., 2020):

- Other traffic participants (people, children, animals)
- Light conditions (morning, sunset, midnight)
- Road condition (dry, wet, icy, dirty)
- Road infrastructure (lanes, road type, constructions)
- Vehicles (cars, trucks, motorcycles)
- Buildings
- Objects (static or dynamic)
- Traffic signs

Data quality (Eliot, L., 2019c):

- Dirt
- Light
- Incorrect signal data

Another topic that strongly influences vehicles is internationalization. Countries in the world either have their own rules or adopt them from others; furthermore, there are of course other factors that need to be considered (Deruyttere, T. et al., 2019):

- Left/right driving
- Street signs
- Rules and laws
- Driving style (Middle East, South Europe, North Europe, China, etc.)

Furthermore, road width can also play an important role; for example, the roads in Japan tend to be narrower than the roads in the USA (Eliot, L., 2018c). As long as there is a mixed environment (human-driven and automated vehicles in parallel), automated vehicles will have to adapt to the existing rules. Eliot (2018c) expressed this in an excellent way:

“Do as the locals do, within reason, and be flexible about it.” (Eliot, L., 2018c, p.223)

3.3 Development Approaches

In the development of automated vehicle software, two essentially contrasting development approaches must be considered. The following Figure 27 compares these two approaches.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 27: Illustration of traditional programming versus machine learning (David, J., 2019).

This type of development is the classic variant that has been used since the beginning of the development of computer systems. The necessary logic for the production of a result is coded into a program by a human programmer. If this program is provided with data as input, exactly the defined processes are executed and calculated on the basis of the stored program logic. This approach always leads to the same result (Deshpande, A. and Kumar, M., 2018); furthermore, this approach is used in the automotive industry, e.g., for the development of control units. An ESP system has a fixed stored algorithm, which executes predefined actions based on different measured values. The same principle is used today by many manufacturers for the provision of an ACC or LKA system (Sjafrie, H., 2020). The complexity of the functions is manageable and can be mapped by a certain number of predefined use cases. The traditional development approach reaches its limits when it comes to vehicles with a higher level of automation (levels 4 and 5 of the SAE framework).

The development of automated vehicles with complex functions requires the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the backend to make correct decisions, according to many experts like Eliot (2019a), Maurer (2016) and Isermann (2017); or alternatively, it requires a similar system, as mentioned by (Sjafrie, H., 2020). Companies like Waymo recognized early on that new approaches are needed to solve complex traffic scenarios. As there is a theoretically infinite number of traffic scenarios, this can no longer be expressed as a "simple" program. In order to solve this problem, machine learning systems develop their own solutions based on existing data and the expected outcomes. Through this approach, the program logic in the broadest sense is developed independently by a computer system (Maurer, M. et al., 2016). The generated result thus depends very much on the quality of the provided data and on which scenarios were identified during the drives by human drivers. If the system is confronted with an unknown scenario, which was not present in the training data, this leads to a problem.

AI-based systems form a black box in terms of the underlying decision structure. The underlying results of a trained network cannot be seen (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). Due to this, it is not possible to understand how the system arrived at the result. This fact makes the applicability in the field of automated vehicles extremely difficult (Tian, Y. et al., 2017); for example, if a calculation is performed twice

with identical input data, this can lead to a different result (Milford, M., Anthony, S. and Scheirer, W., 2020). This circumstance makes AI-based systems not certifiable at the moment (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). In the context of automated vehicles, an incorrect decision such as triggering an emergency break event can mean the difference between life and death.

Eliot (2018d) points out that the capabilities of AI-based systems for automated vehicles are overestimated. The new technology misleads consumers and legislators into believing that these systems have higher safety and robustness. This misconception can lead to false expectations among the different stakeholders and thus bring a potential risk in the use of these systems.

Experts such as Takacs (2018) believe that for the development of safety systems, a balanced compromise between traditional programming and AI-based algorithms is necessary to solve the three main tasks (perception, localization, and planning) in a sustainable way.

Machine learning-based systems are trained on real and virtual data. As primary input, video recordings are often used, enriched by humans and machines with additional information, such as labels, to identify static and dynamic objects. Figure 28 shows a simple example of the labeling of the ground truth environment.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 28: Video still with ground truth labeling of the road targets (Ma, Y., Li, Z. and Sotelo, M. A., 2020).

Based on the data, patterns are then derived and used for decision-making. For a correct decision, the recognition of the scenario and context is essential. Only in this way can a machine learning system correctly interpret traffic scenarios and derive correct measures. Due to the high complexity of traffic scenarios and the variety of influencing factors, such as weather, development companies have not yet achieved the necessary breakthrough to establish the technology in the mass market.

Another big challenge in the development of AI components is fixing an identified issue, as systems need to be retrained and retested. A reproduction of a known issue is possible but difficult because all input criteria need to be the same (Concas, F. et al., 2020). With this approach, there is a risk that repeated training will create new problems in the system (Isabel, M. et al., 2019). Although theoretically, it is necessary to test

against an infinite number of scenarios; today, only a conditional check against a predefined selection of scenarios is possible; this selection represents only a fraction of the potential possibilities that can occur in reality (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). Currently, it is difficult to prove that systems are safe since testing and approval institutions traditionally made tests only for system functionalities like crash and durability (Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R., 2018). As illustrated in Figure 1, with automated vehicles, testing is not simply owing to an unlimited number of scenarios (Kalra, N. and Paddock, S. M., 2016). Another issue is the repeatability of a scenario as it is not possible to exactly simulate a real scenario since there are too many influencing factors.

3.4 Testing Approaches

3.4.1 Classification of Testing Environments

There are a number of different approaches for the validation of automated vehicles available. Maurer (2016) created a matrix, which is shown in the following Figure 29. This illustration breaks down the testing options into vehicle and environment. For both categories, there are three subcategories – virtual, artificial, and real. In the intersections of the individual combinations, the test possibilities are shown.

Figure 29: Illustration of different testing options for automated vehicles (Maurer, M. et al., 2016).

A relevant overview of the four main environments that must be passed through during development is shown in the following Figure 30:

Figure 30: Illustration of testing environments for automated vehicles (McQueen, B., 2019).

Under laboratory conditions, the entire environment can be fully controlled. This environment also allows for the best safeguarding possibility. When a vehicle is introduced to the market, the framework conditions

change completely. Safeguarding is no longer possible in this environment. Vehicles that are used in this environment must comply with all the necessary safety regulations.

3.4.2 Data Collection

A comprehensive analysis of a traffic scenario requires different types of data. Isermann (2017) presents in a schematic diagram, which is illustrated in Figure 31, a possibility to describe test scenarios for simulation purposes. The data required appears to be very similar to that which must be collected in the context of real tests in order to be able to perform a meaningful analysis. In his schematic representation, Isermann divides a test scenario into four groups. At the center of his model is the virtual prototype with all its properties and functions. This description is exchanged with the real automated vehicle in the course of real tests. Static and dynamic objects describe the environment of a scenario. In a further group, the exact description of the environmental information, such as weather or lighting conditions, takes place. When using a real vehicle with automated functions, documentation of the current driving functions (e.g., sport mode for ACC) must be created instead of the virtual prototype configuration since these settings have an influence on the behavior. This information may have important relevance later during data analysis while making a statistical comparison of different drives.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 31: Illustration of test scenario structure (Isermann, R., 2017).

3.4.3 Testing Tools: Virtual Vehicle and Virtual Environment

An increasingly relevant variant for testing automated vehicles is complete virtualization. This is referred to in the literature as Software in the Loop (SIL) and comprises complete virtualization of vehicle and environment. This test variant offers the possibility to repeat scenarios as often as desired. In addition, parameters can be individually adjusted and new test series can be performed. The different results can

then be compared automatically and provide information about the safety of the system. This approach can also be used for the identification of unknown test cases in the case of black box systems, as is the case for machine learning-based systems. By combining a wide variety of parameter settings, it is possible to identify new and previously unknown problems in the systems (Tian, Y. *et al.*, 2017).

Another advantage of virtualization is scalability since by splitting the scenarios, parallel execution is possible. This allows a large number of test cases to be processed efficiently with a corresponding cluster system. Still, this type of testing still has certain limitations. On the one hand, modeling a real scenario with all its details is not possible today. Due to a certain abstraction in the representations, partial information is there for loss. But, when performing tests in comparison to a real scenario, a simplified level of details could make a crucial difference between a successful detection of a problem. A closer look at the literature on simulation technologies for system validation, however, reveals a number of gaps and shortcomings. As described by Pathrose (2022), an additional challenge is the simulation of sensors, which are used in different testing environments like Vehicle in the Loop (VIL) to stimulation systems. Similar challenges in the context of scenario-based validation with simulation technology are also shared by Leitner *et al.* (2020). A realistic representation also reaches its limits with current means. Although many authors have conducted studies and good progress has been made in recent years, simulation technology still has weaknesses and must be considered critically in the validation of automated vehicles, since not all problems can be identified. Regardless of the current limitations, this test method is now an excellent option for covering basic safety. In this context, Maurer (2016) suggests that all known traffic accidents from around the world should be integrated into the development and validation process in order to include more statistically relevant scenarios for ensuring safety.

3.4.4 Testing Tools: Real Vehicle and Real Environment

This section reviews the literature related to the validation of automated systems under real conditions as a counterpart to the completely virtual test method. Real tests are conducted on public roads or on a special proving ground, often referred to in the literature as a test track (McQueen, B., 2019). In the past, the proving ground approach was used mainly for vehicle approval. A large number of existing literature from Leitner *et al.* (2020), Akamatsu (2019) and Coelingh *et al.* (2018) have examined proving ground testing. In comparison, there is little literature and methods for conducting tests on public roads for the safe validation of systems.

In principle, testing under real conditions is the best way to identify problems; however, this method has significant disadvantages when it comes to scaling and repeatability. On the one hand, economic factors limit the possibility and number of tests. In addition, the time factor plays a significant role. According to Pathrose, typically about 500 to 700 km are completed on a proving ground until tests are conducted on public roads (Pathrose, P., 2022). Due to the fact that the software status can change continuously in the course of development, this variant can only be used for selected scenarios (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020).

3.5 Simulation Technology

3.5.1 Enabler for Scalability and Repeatability

Simulation technology has played an essential role in the development of complex software systems for many years in different domains. Takacs et al. (2018) describe in their work the success of simulation environments in recent years that achieved very promising results for the safeguarding of automated vehicles. Experts such as Sjafrie (2020) and Maurer et al. (2016) see potential in simulation to achieve a scalable and repeatable way of performing tests. This approach has also been pursued by Waymo for years, and based on a safety report from 2020, 32+ million self-driven km and 15+ billion simulated km have been driven in 10+ years with 5 different generations of automated vehicles (Waymo, 2020). This remarkable number can be achieved by scaling this testing method. Today, cluster computer systems can be used to perform an incredible number of parallel calculations at high performance. The advantage here is the continuous execution. Tests can be executed continuously and never have to be stopped. As mentioned, one limiting factor is the cost and associated server resources (Eliot, L., 2018d). Regardless of the immense number of test kilometers performed, however, there still seem to be significant problems with public road deployment. Waymo started development more than ten years ago, and to date none of the targeted public services are available (Badue, C. et al., 2019).

There has also been massive development progress in the area of sensor simulation, which is an essential building block for the virtual testing of vehicles (Leitner, A., 2019). Due to the increase in the performance of computer systems and the additional cost reduction in recent years, complex simulations can now be performed on standard computer systems. A variety of educational programs are also available that provide an overview of automated vehicles, such as Udacity. Three simulation scenarios are shown in Figure 32. In the first image, the vehicle is on a proving ground and learns on the basis of the stored algorithm. This is then applied to the other two images in the middle and right-hand areas. By differentiating between a training and a test data set, the learned behavior can be tested appropriately.

Figure 32: Screenshots of Udacity driving simulator (Chen, Y. et al., 2018).

There are projections by experts such as Herrmann et al. (2018), who consider 600,000 km as the necessary test distance for a traffic-jam pilot. For a city pilot, the distance traveled should be between 200 to 5 billion km due to the higher complexity based on their recommendation. This large number makes it clear that real tests on this scale are not possible. For this reason, only a certain number of selected scenarios with the highest probability of occurrence can be tested.

3.5.2 *System Models*

According to Sjafrie (2020), a very substantial amount of effort is required to comply with ISO 26262 to ensure the safety of a system, and this cannot be reduced if one wants to protect people and the environment in a satisfactory way. A typical toolchain for the development of automated vehicles focuses heavily on simulation (Leitner, A., 2019). The simulation process requires a model of the physical system, which can be considered almost infinitely complex, and a simulation model (computer or even scaled device) can only provide an approximation. Normally, the physical model will be deployed on a dynamics model requiring some level of mathematics, which in itself enforces limitations. Sjafrie describes one of the biggest challenges related to the creation of complete system models of all details. This includes the consideration of all external factors that have an influence on the behavior. From his point of view, today's models are probabilistic because they represent oversimplification and under-specification. The reality presents far more complicating factors that must be taken into account. Simulating the full details of an actual traffic scenario can be extremely challenging (Qudrat-Ullah, H., 2014). So, although development companies can cover a wide range of test cases through simulation, the final validation must be done on public roads. The simulation system will always provide results with a certain level of errors which will need to be estimated, evaluated and acknowledged; furthermore, not all external factors can be identified. The problems mentioned are just a few of a long list that has significantly slowed the development of automated vehicles in recent years. McFarland (2019) describes it as extremely difficult to prove the safety of the systems. Poor weather conditions make it difficult for sensors to detect the environment. In his view, today's systems lack the human touch to enable a smooth operation. He highlights the role of experts who see the need for a new technological breakthrough to make the systems suitable for the mass market. This view is supported by Xia et al. (2021), who argue that the next generation of automated vehicles should mimic the human mind and reach full autonomy.

3.5.3 *Limitations*

Virtualization brings many benefits. Milford et al. (2020) address the question of how to show and prove that the systems which have been developed in simulations would work on public roads; concluding that a simulation model will never be perfect. This view is also shared by other experts in the field, such as Rajabli et al. (2020). Even the best simulation with the highest level of detail will never be able to depict all details and behaviors of reality. In synthetic scenarios, representing lighting conditions is a well-known problem that remains unsolved to date. This limitation restricts the validity of virtual test environments compared to real environments (Kang, Y., Yin, H. and Berger, C., 2019). Even if new research approaches based on AI enable a close-to-reality simulation, there will always be differences in the foreseeable future that make it necessary to carry out tests under real conditions.

From the perspective of Eliot (2018b), the use of simulation technology for testing purposes can be summarized to one simple weakness. A simulated drive does not correspond to a real drive on the road; furthermore, it raises the question of how to ensure that the simulation has correctly modeled the AI system

of the automated vehicle. Such fundamental questions have not been solved to date and pose significant challenges to developers. Other authors like Takacs et al. (2018) argue that it is very difficult to track problems with current approaches; furthermore, they agree on the problem, that not every conceivable case can be covered. Takacs et al. proposes to build a much more robust system based on the analysis of human behavior in order to define basic building blocks for the software of automated vehicles. A similar opinion is held by Al-Nuaimi et al. (2018), who consider the current simulation technology insufficient and see a need for more advanced methods to solve the problem.

Due to all the current weaknesses in the simulation system and process, it is still necessary to carry out final tests on proving grounds and public roads for the approval of a vehicle under real conditions, as described, for example, by Maurer et al. (2016). Maurer et al. argue that there is no way around testing the limits of systems in reality as this activity cannot currently be replaced by simulation. He also suggests that a system of virtual scenarios should be built based on historical traffic accidents in order to test the systems against these known problems.

3.6 Real World Testing

3.6.1 Closed Testing Environments

A popular intermediate solution to test systems between pure simulation and public road environments provide delineated proving grounds. Waymo (2020), for example, delivers new updates first to vehicles operated by experienced drivers. They perform the initial testing on these safe environments before testing it on public road conditions. There are several proving grounds around the world such as Mcity in Ann Arbor, built by the University of Michigan at the cost of \$10 million (Khajepour, A., 2020). As one can see from Figure 33, in the model city, automated vehicles can be tested under near-real conditions without injuring people.

Figure 33: Photograph of Mcity for testing of automated vehicles on a closed proving ground (Khajepour, A., 2020).

The literature reports that testing on proving grounds has an essential disadvantage compared to testing on public roads. Driver behavior on a proving ground is different from that on a normal road due to the lower

complexity of traffic scenarios and the lack of real road participants (Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A., 2018). McQueen (2019) added that the collection of "public reaction data" and "driver behavior data" is an important next step for testing automated vehicles as the data is essential to prove the maturity and safety of the systems. Another area that has a lack of research in the literature concerns the continuous validation of the safety performance of automated systems on public roads. Takacs et al. (2018) see a long-term need for such a system.

3.6.2 Comparison of Testing Approaches

In the previous sections, the two primary variants of test methods were presented. On the one hand, validation can be achieved by simulation, which offers excellent scaling and repeatability. Scaling enables the parallel execution of simulation models, and therefore the time until the results are available can be reduced. Instead of running through 100 executions in a sequence, the computation can be parallelized on 10 systems, for example, allowing a reduction in time by a factor of 10. This simplified representation assumes that the execution of each model takes the same amount of time and that there is no dependency between the individual calculations.

Another advantage of simulation technology is achieved by the repeatability of a calculation. Repeatability refers to the unique description of a simulation model and its parameters, allowing a scenario to be executed in the same way over and over again. Due to unique input parameters, an execution with the same result can be obtained repeatedly, as long as the model itself does not contain any random calculation logic. If for example AI logic is used in the models, this can lead to different results since there is no fixed programmed algorithm.

On the other hand, testing can be performed under real conditions. Both variants have their advantages and disadvantages. Isermann (2017) compared the two test methods to generate scenarios. His model is shown in Figure 34; it proposes three different ways of generating scenarios based on the two axes, "Realism and details" and "Scenario size."

Figure 34: Illustration of scenario generation methods (Isermann, R., 2017).

For the creation of a small number of scenarios with a low degree of reality, manual creation is very suitable. For the creation of the opposite, many scenarios with a high degree of reality, Isermann's model proposes to build on measurement data. As a third alternative, the creation based on map data such as OpenStreetMap or similar providers is suggested. Another alternative to the approaches mentioned would be the generation of scenarios based on historical accident data, which is proposed by Leitner (2019). There are already scenario catalogs with representative examples, which were built using data from accident databases. The advantage of this variant is that each scenario is based on real measurement data from public roads and thus provides a good reference. The approach has two major disadvantages. On the one hand, the modeling of a scenario is very time-consuming and requires a lot of detailed information. On the other hand, the information that is often available in an accident database is not sufficient to perform a complete reconstruction since no measuring devices were installed in the vehicles at the time of the accident.

All of the mentioned test approaches have their advantages and disadvantages and depend strongly on the use case in which they are required. In the entire product life cycle of a vehicle, for example, simulation technology is heavily used in the development, as this method offers optimal scaling and repeatability. Due to the already described weaknesses of simulation technology, it is also necessary to perform tests under real conditions, such as on closed proving grounds or on public roads. A middle way, which becomes more and more important, is the VIL approach, where a real vehicle is tested in the laboratory with simulation technology.

The validation of automated vehicles is still a very new discipline in the automotive industry. Manufacturers, legislators and certification organizations have developed numerous approaches in recent years to validate the systems in the best possible way. At the moment, there are some trends, such as simulation technology, in which direction validation will be performed in a standardized way in the future. To date, there is no standard for full and complete validation.

3.6.3 Automated Driving Requirements in the EU and USA

All standards and regulations for the homologation of vehicles basically have one thing in common, minimizing risk, hazards and damage of automated driving, as shown in green in Figure 35. The image showcases the complexity of the issue, with the current requirements for homologation and safeguarding of automated vehicles in the EU and the USA (Winkle, T., Erbsmehl, C. and Bengler, K., 2018).

Figure 35: Illustration of automated driving requirements in the EU and USA (Winkle, T., Erbsmehl, C. and Bengler, K., 2018).

The specifications and regulations are intended to contribute to risk reduction of an automated system. In addition, the danger and thus potentially possible damage should be reduced to a minimum; for example, the introduction of the ODD is intended to define the area of use of functions in a standardized manner (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). This is intended to exclude incorrect use of the system under unintended conditions.

According to Bradley et al. (2020), a key challenge in defining and conducting standardized tests is transferring them to other scenarios, similar or otherwise. A human driver can handle complex traffic scenarios after completing a driver training course regardless of whether these were practiced as part of the training or are new traffic scenarios. With automated systems, there is a weakness, as systems are programmed or trained for specific scenarios. If a new or unknown scenario occurs, this can pose a problem for the system and ultimately lead to an accident. In terms of transferability, standardization is still a major obstacle to the homologation of automated systems and needs to be further researched (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020).

Pathrose states that current verification and validation procedures have a lot of gaps. Existing test methods on different levels need to be enhanced to avoid safety-critical problems in the products (Pathrose, P., 2022). From today's perspective, final validation must still be carried out on public roads, since the many framework conditions and influencing factors cannot be completely covered by a simulation. This view is supported by Leitner et al. (2020) as virtual tests cannot cover all cases. From their point of view, there is a

need to establish an intelligent combination of virtual and physical tests in the field, thereby creating a sustainable homologation procedure with corresponding standards.

In the USA, manufacturers of automated systems currently have the option of carrying out homologation independently. It must be proven to the legislator that the systems have sufficient test coverage. In the case of problems, these must be investigated and reported (Maurer, M. *et al.*, 2016). One problem with this approach, which should be viewed critically, is the freedom that manufacturers are given in the validation process. A lack of comparability and transparency can lead to considerable differences in the quality of the systems; nevertheless, this approach offers the potential to be used in combination with a standardized homologation process and thus to obtain a comprehensive validation.

The European homologation authorities oversee mandatory certification requirements within the EU in accordance with the UN World Forum for Harmonization of Vehicle Regulations. In most EU member states, homologation applies to the majority of major vehicle components, facilitating certification of vehicles and components between countries. This agreement is not applicable to the USA, which has its own regulations enacted by NHTSA. There are fundamental differences in the approaches to homologation between the EU and the USA. The homologation process in the EU is based on "third-party verification" by approval authorities or technical services. In the USA, homologation can be accomplished through a process called "self-certification," where test reports that prove the safety of the operation must be submitted in support. It is also possible to combine these two approaches, as seen in the Australian example (Bhaskaran, B., 2022).

3.6.4 Confidence Level and Approval Trap

There is a wide variety of literature that addresses the question of the number of kilometers that must be driven for a system to be confident. Kalra and Paddock (2016) calculated a distance of 440 million km to bring automated vehicles to a higher performance level than humans at a 95% confidence level. In their calculations, they also go a step further and perform a projection of what this would mean in real terms. Assuming that a fleet of 100 vehicles is operated 24 hours, a test effort of 12.5 years would be required. This turnaround time represents an unreasonable duration in reality. Figure 36 shows the statistical results of their calculation, which are a good indicator of the complexity and effort required to test automated vehicles for safety.

Figure 36: Illustration of statistical calculation to ensure safety for automated vehicles (Kalra, N. and Paddock, S. M., 2016).

The associated costs would be high and could never justify the development of the system's functionality (Alawadhi, M. *et al.*, 2020); furthermore, the test drives would have to be performed after every major software change. This excellent computational example from Kalra and Paddock (2016) shows the need for scalable testing methods, an opinion shared by experts such as Patrose (2022). The calculation of Kalra and Paddock (2016) appears to be fundamentally legitimate and 12.5 years is not an option for test driving but with a larger fleet of vehicles, such as by a factor of 100, this time could be significantly reduced. Kalra and Paddock (2016), however, do not consider that new test approaches, in which a wave roll-out is carried out, could counteract this problem. Initial tests are conducted by experts and, once a certain level of test coverage or robustness has been reached, qualified private individuals are also involved. This approach would allow scaling while reducing costs; hence optimizing the approval process. This system would allow for updating vehicles after production and delivery to the customer thanks to the introduction of Over-the-Air (OTA) updates, bugs, optimizations or new functions (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020).

Tesla is a pioneer in this area and has already incorporated this functionality into its vehicles at a very early stage. By using a simple mechanism, vehicles can be updated in a very short period of time. This new approach brings many advantages, yet there are also some new challenges that certification companies face in this context. Due to the increasing number of updates, which already take place regularly every few weeks for some manufacturers and functions, a re-validation must be carried out for certain functionalities (Leitner, A., Watzenig, D. and Ibanez-Guzman, J., 2020). This necessity is also shared by Bradley *et al.* (2020), since OTA updates mean that the traditional testing approach no longer works. In his view, changes must be tested as part of a re-validation before release (Bradley, C. and Preston, V., 2020). Particularly, in the case of functions that are related to automated driving, there is an unsolved problem in this context. The validation of vehicles can only be performed against a certain number of selected scenarios on proving grounds. Many problems can be covered in advance via simulation technologies, but due to the increased complexity in validation, it is highly probable that a certain problem may not be identified. So, if a software update with an unknown problem is rolled out to a public fleet, it can lead to devastating problems. The new opportunities created by OTA updates technology have a further downside. As reported by Pathrose, many projects skip various verification and validation processes because the time to release a new vehicle is fixed

(Pathrose, P., 2022). Existing bugs in the systems are then fixed by the manufacturers at a later date. This approach carries significant risk, especially for automated functions.

Furthermore, the increase in vehicle connectivity creates an additional problem. Systems are becoming more vulnerable to external attacks, and additional protection mechanisms need to be integrated to prevent external interference or the introduction of malicious software (Jahan, F. et al., 2019). Cyber Security did not play a significant role in the automotive industry until a few years ago because vehicles had no connectivity, and there was no connection to control systems such as steering wheels or pedals. In the future, this aspect will have to be taken into account when certifying a vehicle. The Federal Motor Vehicle Safety Standards (FMVSS) and the NHTSA, for example, are working together to create regulations for the reduction of risk.

Today, the homologation process of a vehicle consists of a large number of different test criteria that vary across countries. Figure 37, Isermann (2017) illustrates the homologation for a passenger car based on the legal regulation RREG 2007/46. Today, the acceptance process for the final road approval consists of approximately 60 different packages.

Figure 37: Illustration of passenger car homologation regulations (Isermann, R., 2017).

The classical homologation process is mainly performed on proving grounds and controlled environments such as test laboratories. In these environments, only limited scenarios and a small number of tests can be performed. Simple automated functions such as Emergency Brake Assist (EBA) can be validated using this approach (Maurer, M. et al., 2016). With complex functions which are used at higher automation levels, this approach reaches its limits. According to Maurer et al. (2016), the current approach is not sufficient for the acceptance of automated vehicles in terms of safety. By limiting the effort for economic reasons to a reduced number of test cases, only fractions of checks can be performed. This subsequently leads to the

release of systems with unknown problems, as previously described, which can ultimately lead to life-threatening accidents on the road.

For the homologation of automated vehicles, the International Organisation of Motor Vehicle Manufacturers (OICA) suggests a framework built on the following three pillars to ensure safety:

- Audit/assessment
- Physical certification test
- Real-world drive test

The OICA framework is designed for the initial homologation of vehicles and, as currently defined, does not provide for continuous homologation of new or updated functions. This essential limitation represents a potential safety risk and requires an extension in the long-term (Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P., 2020). An alternative approach to the validation and homologation of automated vehicles is proposed by Fethet al. (2018). The approach of this concept divides validation into the following three disciplines:

- Functional safety: Safeguarding the risks of a system against malfunction or failure.
- Functional safety: Handling of risks that occur in connection with traffic scenarios in which an automated system is not able to handle them safely and correctly.
- Functional insufficiencies: Description of driving behavior under specific conditions that should be considered safe. This discipline should include driving under real conditions.

The authors of the framework, Feth et al. (2018), point out gaps in all three disciplines in their work. When it comes to the guarantee and robustness of the automated systems, no complete safeguarding can be carried out with current procedures. This circumstance requires the improvement of the current standards, which will subsequently also have an influence on the framework.

A number of challenges in system safety, reliability, validation, security, testing, human-machine interaction, social acceptance and legal framework and the need for a safe homologation method for acceptance in society were explained by Koopman et al. (2017). A fundamental requirement for automated systems for which there is no solution today concerns the behavior of the systems. According to Koopman et al., this should have a similar behavior to a human driver to ensure safe operation. As long as there is mixed operation, this is an unavoidable necessity from the authors' point of view.

Shaoshan et al. (2018) describe another challenge that automated vehicles have to solve. There are basically traffic rules that must be followed; however, when a critical scenario occurs, the safety-first rule would have to come first. If it is possible to safely resolve a dangerous scenario by violating a traffic rule, this should be done. Validation of such scenarios is an extremely complex challenge (Rosenfeld, A. and Kraus, S., 2018).

3.7 Critical Analysis and Summarization of Existing Literature

In existing testing methods for automated systems, gaps exist because scenario-based approaches do not consider all aspects of real traffic scenarios or because there is a limited number of tests. For a better

validation of the safety, reliability and robustness of systems, a safe method is needed that considers the complexity of real traffic situations and can be executed in a more scalable form. The effort and complexity required to validate vehicles before releasing them to the public market have increased significantly in recent years due to the transfer of driving activities to an automated system. New functions are capable of handling increasingly complex driving activities. In this context, it is even more important that the automated functions have a high level of operational performance in order to avoid traffic accidents. Certification organizations test the functionality as part of the homologation process before approval is issued for public use. Due to the high complexity of the subject and potential sources of error, traditional test methods, which are carried out in laboratory environments or on proving grounds, are reaching their limits. Current test methods focus strongly on the simulation of defined scenarios in closed environments in order to ensure the basic functionality of the vehicle. Due to the high effort caused by setup, execution and analysis, only a very small number of tests can be performed under time and financial constraints. This approach is not sufficient for safety assessment and the associated avoidance of traffic accidents, since the low test coverage means that there is a high probability that problems have not been detected. Another limitation of scenario-based testing is the simplification of complexity compared to traffic scenarios on public roads, and due to the large number of influencing factors under real conditions, different results may be obtained when validating similar scenarios.

There are additional gaps in the literature regarding scalable testing methods under realistic environments to test more scenarios with higher complexity in a safe way. In particular, there are conceptual and methodological gaps in the current approaches, which create the need for an optimized or new solution. In addition, the well-being of drivers during the use of a system is not surveyed at the moment, so there are no data on their levels of confidence regarding the correct handling of traffic scenarios.

Within the scope of this research, the current gaps and weaknesses of testing methods used in the homologation processes are addressed by developing a scalable approach based on tests on public roads. As a result of this research, an objective assessment of an automated system can be made by using a standardized method without regard to vehicle type, manufacturer, model, or variant. The vehicle is to be considered a black box in the validation, which means that no consideration is given to the underlying technical realization. This should enable and ensure a standardized assessment of the systems. In addition, intervention in the vehicle itself is to be avoided so as not to influence test results and to prevent additional safety risks. In order to execute the tests on public roads safely and effectively, an expert driver is kept in the loop so that he or she can intervene immediately if a critical traffic scenario occurs.

This research fills this gap by achieving a significantly broader test coverage under different traffic and environmental conditions through simple configuration, application and analysis. As part of the automated assessment of the system, objective criteria are used to support a standardized validation process. This assessment also takes into account the comfort and confidence of the driver, which differs depending on the specific scenario.

Part 2:
Theoretical Framework Development and Concept Realization

Chapter 4

Theoretical Framework of the Shadow System

4.1 Aims and Objectives

Current methods for the homologation of automated vehicles perform a significant portion of testing on closed proving grounds. Defined scenarios are performed by human drivers or programmed systems such as Ultra Flat Overrunable (UFO) robots or a combination of both. As scenarios require a high degree of configuration, the number of tests is relatively low. Combining public roads with current methods would allow testing to validate more scenarios on longer distances in short time frames; furthermore, it is the most realistic possibility since there is no simplification of the environment and traffic scenarios.

The first aim of this research is the assessment of the performance of an automated vehicle to prove the roadworthiness of a system as part of the homologation process. Current research focuses on the use of robots on proving grounds to create artificial scenarios; however, this does not have the benefit of testing on public roads for a realistic insight covering a larger distance, which is what this research does. In order to validate the performance of automated vehicles, the following objectives are defined.

The safe validation of automated vehicles on public roads requires the development of a holistic approach for objectively assessing their performance. Safety, reliability, and robustness are the main performance assessment criteria. Further, the driver's well-being is taken into account as part of the validation to get a better understanding of the system. After establishing this first objective, it is possible to accomplish the second objective, which is the development of a standardized test method for automated vehicles with a human driver as a fallback to ensure safe driving on public roads. Finally, this allows for the completion of a further objective, which is the development of a device for the independent measurement of the driving behavior of an automated vehicle compared to a human driver to determine the performance of the systems by detecting deviations.

The second aim of this research is to validate a production vehicle with the developed framework on public roads to assess the safety, reliability, and robustness of the system. The second set of objectives is to establish a standardized method for evaluating test drives in order to make an objective assessment of a system's performance. This allows for the following objective, which entails equipping a vehicle with a measurement device for independent recording of steering movements in order to collect data for the analysis of deviations between the human driver and the automated system. After this equipment is installed, it is necessary to perform test drives with a vehicle on the public road to identify and collect data from critical and uncomfortable traffic scenarios. Finally, data from test drives is evaluated to assess the safety and criticality of identified issues.

4.2 Framework Outline Design and Interface

Today's test methods for the validation of automated vehicles are not sufficient to prove the complete safety of the systems. A human driver has been considered the benchmark to date as an average driver can travel a large number of kilometers without an accident. Automated systems must at least match the performance of a human driver in order to be accepted by lawmakers or society.

In this research, the theoretical framework is built based on these two theories in order to objectively evaluate the safety of an automated system by means of validation by a human driver on public roads. With this approach, critical events in automated vehicles should be identified. The overall concept is based on the detection of behavioral differences between humans and machines. This idea is comparable to the widely used ELOS approach. ELOS is used in areas where the homologation specifications cannot be fully demonstrated. This means there will always be some information missing. This is precisely the problem facing today's automated vehicle manufacturers and legislators. Based on the ELOS principle, an evaluation of the safety of an automated vehicle is performed by comparing it to a human driver.

Experts such as Takacs et al. (2018) propose to build a validation concept based on the analysis of human behavior. In addition, Maurer et al. (2016) suggest performing the final tests on public roads because simulation environments and closed proving grounds can only represent simplified scenarios, and only reality can demonstrate if a system acts correctly under certain given conditions.

A large number of test methods for the validation of automated vehicles are designed to measure human intervention. Through these methods, the Takeover Time (TOT) and the corresponding action of the driver can be measured. Usually, sensors measuring the force on the steering wheel are used for this purpose. Every intervention by the driver directly leads to an influence on the vehicle and thus changes the position or behavior (Akamatsu, M., 2019). The use of expert drivers for the validation of automated vehicles on public roads is already used today, as the example of Uber shows; however, the current approach allows the expert to take a passive position while driving and intervene only in case of a critical scenario. On the one hand, this method has the disadvantage that the test driver loses attention over time due to various activities, thus increasing the reaction and intervention time; furthermore, this method does not provide information about the well-being and driving behavior of a human driver compared to an automated vehicle. As soon as a driver intervenes, control of the vehicle is taken over. The intervention can be caused by a critical event or by the driver's uncomfortable feeling, for example because the vehicle is too close to the guard rail.

This research aims to address this problem and develop a concept on how the validation of automated vehicles can be demonstrated in an objective, standardized and more scalable way. The main purpose of this framework aligns with the approval of automated vehicles. Here, the focus is on proving whether a system can function correctly on public roads and thus ensure safe operation. Due to legal regulations and boundary conditions, there are various validation processes in different regions. Regardless of these contrasting processes, the framework developed in this research supports all.

The theoretical framework is designed with a safe and sustainable data acquisition so that the acquired measurement results can be used for further data analysis. Based on data from real test drives, an analysis identifies critical scenarios; furthermore, the overall concept is designed in a way to be used in different types of vehicles, independent of the make, model, or region where it is to be operated; therefore, this research treats a vehicle as a black box system since information about system architecture and automated software approaches does not help in the identification. The major focus of the research is to measure the driving behavior of humans and automated systems to identify safety-critical issues. The measurement of the data is carried out completely independently between the human and the vehicle in order to avoid mutual interference. This is to ensure that there is no falsification of the data in the results.

4.3 Theory Behind the Detection of Behavioral Differences

The theory used in this research relies on the fundamental idea of detecting differences in behaviors. As described in Section 1.4, humans are excellent drivers and are capable of handling most traffic scenarios safely. The idea of this research is to capture the behaviors of a human and an automated vehicle during a drive, such that they do not influence each other. The following are the main actions executed by a human during a drive:

- Braking
- Acceleration
- Steering (left or right)
- Using the indicator and lights
- Honking

By detecting critical scenarios on public roads based on independent measurement of these behaviors, a validation method obtains an objective statement about existing deviations in the context of development and homologation tests. The overall concept is referred to as Shadow System (SS) in this research and can be used independently of the vehicle type. A key element of this theory and its associated system is the independent execution of driving activities such as steering or braking. The human driver can perform steering movements during a journey when actively using an automated function such as LKA without directly influencing the vehicle. Up to a defined safety limit, the human driver should not influence the vehicle and vice versa.

Figure 38 shows an illustrative scenario that intends to represent the basic theory based on a steering movement. In the final development stage, the overall system consists of different system components to measure differences from pedals and control levers such as turn signals or lights. But in the following description, the focus is purely on the steering movement. The term Shadow Steering Wheel (SSW) is used to describe the component, shown in blue in Figure 38.

General activities like gear shifting, checking the mirrors, using swipers are excluded to simplify the validation of the concept. In a holistic expansion stage, all interactions of a driver with the vehicle and the environment should be recorded in order to compare the behavior towards the automated system.

Figure 38: Illustration of the Shadow System theory.

The scenario in this fictitious illustration is in an automated vehicle driving on a three-lane roadway. Oncoming traffic is on the left side of the lanes. The center and right lanes are aligned in the direction of travel and can both be used by the vehicle. It is assumed that the Highway Autopilot (HAP) is activated at the time of the scenario and thus the vehicle should act completely autonomously. Based on the SAE framework, these functions correspond to level 3. There are already vehicles on the market today that support this functionality.

In this illustrative example, an obstacle in the form of another stationary vehicle suddenly appears while the vehicle is moving, thereby blocking the middle lane. Marker 1 indicates that the automated vehicle, hereafter referred to as the ego vehicle, has a neutral steering position on its real steering wheel. The basic idea of the SSW, which is shown around marker 2, involves adding an additional layer to the normal steering wheel. This layer is intended to enable the driver to perform steering movements independently of the vehicle. In the illustration, the driver's hand movement is applied to the SSW. This movement shows the behavior of the human driver in the current scenario. So, through this method, the difference between the vehicle and the human driver can be measured.

In the example shown in Figure 38, a human in the scenario would make a steering movement to the right to avoid a collision with the target vehicle, which is shown via marker 3. Due to the speed of the automated vehicle, which is surrounded by other human-controlled vehicles, this example assumes that emergency braking would not prevent an accident. An accident can be avoided by following the navigation path represented by marker 4. In the area of marker 5, a simplified form of the measurement signal is shown, which is to be detected via the SS. The blue line shows the difference in the movement of the human driver as compared to the steering wheel of the vehicle. The threshold value shown in marker 6 serves as a safety

mechanism. As soon as the threshold value is exceeded, as can be seen in the illustration, the steering movements of the SSW are transmitted directly to the steering wheel of the vehicle. This allows the driver to take control of the vehicle's steering movement and independently control the traffic scenario.

A point is identified when exceeding the threshold value; this point is to be classified as critical on the basis of the stored threshold values. The detection of such points forms the basis for the recognition of critical scenarios based on a differential measurement, which is the main objective of this research. These measurements provide evidence of the hypothesis in the context of post-data analysis.

These measurements are taken through the threshold values triggering a lock-up of the SSW, which supports a dynamic range of values. Depending on the speed of the vehicle, a limitation of the movement range for the SSW component is required; for example, at a vehicle speed of up to 50 km/h, the SSW component may perform a deviation of +/- 2 cm. If the speed changes to between 100 and 130 km/h, the range of movement may only be +/- 0.5 cm. This limitation is necessary because at higher speeds, only the slightest steering movements are allowed. The exact determination of the limiting values is carried out as part of calibration under real conditions.

Two detailed figures better explain the two safety variants. In Figure 39, the difference between the real steering wheel and the SSW is shown by the red reference points using marker 1 as an example. The distance between the two red points is the difference between the two components. In data acquisition, to determine the deviation, the angle should be measured in degrees. Based on this value, the distance in cm can then be calculated by the distance of the SSW component.

Figure 39: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with distance difference approach.

The second variant determines the force applied by the driver onto the SSW component. Higher force means that the driver wants to perform a faster movement. If the force exceeds a predefined limit, this immediately leads to a lock of the component. When implementing an SS component, both safety variants are implemented and used in parallel. When the limiting value for the distance or the force is exceeded for

the first time, the component is automatically locked. This example may be compared in certain aspects with the traffic accident of a Tesla vehicle on a highway due to a fallen over truck, which is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 40: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with correction force approach.

4.3.1 Human as a Benchmark

On public road drives, the overall idea is to take human drivers as the benchmark for all actions applied during a drive in the automated vehicle. The drivers should be able to have many years of experience on the road and should not have an aggressive and risky driving style. Another necessary criterion should be the number of accidents in the past and the average distance traveled per year. Every day, around 70 million journeys are made worldwide, covering an average distance of 15 km. This leads to approximately 1.25 million fatal accidents per year. In America, statistics show that an incident occurs every 772,485 km. Approximately 53% of accidents are caused by driver distraction. Considering a wide range of traffic scenarios and environmental conditions, a person's driving performance cannot be underestimated (Hanna, P., 2020). The powerful combination of information, knowledge, and wisdom enables humans to be the perfect benchmark to validate and use automated vehicles.

4.3.2 Vehicle as a Black Box

In the context of this research, the vehicle is to be considered a pure black box. The assumption is applicable regardless of make, model, version, or the associated hardware and software. The theory takes into account that humans can be used as a benchmark for safety on public roads as long as they are not influenced by factors such as alcohol, drugs, or cell phones. Humans, and automated vehicles, hereafter also referred to as machines, are to be considered independent of each other. By measuring the behavioral differences between a human and a machine during a journey, critical scenarios can be identified in the first step by means of larger deviations. In the second step, by refining the deviation, detected non-ideal or uncomfortable scenarios for the driver are recorded.

The theory is designed to put safety-first. At no time should the use of the system compromise the road safety of the driver or the environment. The system is not designed for industrial or private use and may only

be used in strict compliance with the existing road traffic regulations in the respective country. The knowledge gained is to be fed back into system development in the long-term so that it contributes to increasing safety within the framework of optimization loops.

As a superordinate goal, the theory described in the following section aims to improve the validation of automated vehicles, which should make a significant contribution to the early detection of critical scenarios. This should help prevent problems in the automated systems from reaching the mass market and causing accidents.

4.3.3 Safety Approach

In the application designed in this research, when using the SS, locking of the affected component must generally occur when a certain threshold value is exceeded, ensuring that all further human movements are transferred to the vehicle. There are two types of thresholds that can trigger the lockout. The first variant is distance overrun, as shown in simplified form in Figure 39. In the context of this research, this type of locking is used when the difference between the real steering wheel and the SSW becomes too large. For safety reasons, direct control by the driver must be resumed at this point. The second variant is force overshoot. This means that depending on the strength of the movement performed by the human driver on the SSW component, a lockout must occur. This type of safety mechanism is relevant, for example, in scenarios where the driver must intervene immediately. This ensures that the threshold value from the first variant need not be exceeded before the component is locked. What is important with the SS is that the lockout remains active until the driver informs the system that the scenario is again under control, and the system can be put back into an active state. After reactivation, the system must automatically reset to the initial position so that the differential measurement can start from zero for further scenarios.

4.3.4 Behavior Difference Visualization

This research uses the visualization shown in Figure 41 to illustrate how the behavior between the vehicle and the human is different. This example illustrates the basic concept by using the distance variant presented in Section 4.3. The same representation is used for the second variant, where the applied force on the SS component must be displayed.

Figure 41: Illustration of the behavior difference visualization for the Shadow System.

The primary measurement signal is displayed by means of a line diagram, which shows the time course of the measurement in seconds on the x-axis and the difference of the components in cm on the y-axis. In Figure 41, the difference signal is represented by the blue line and marker 1. There are two threshold values, which are represented by orange and red horizontal lines. The direction of the steering movement is seen at the end of the graphic, where the difference can deviate to the left or right. The so-called warning limit is defined by marker 2 and the orange line connected to it. All deviations between the centerline (gray, 0-cm deviation) and the orange line are classified as normal. This difference has no influence on safety and does not cause any uncomfortable feelings to the driver. Deviations between marker 2 and marker 3 are in the warning range. This means that the deviation does not yet represent a safety risk but can no longer be classified as comfortable for humans. An example of this would be an overtaking maneuver by a truck, where the distance between vehicles is too small. This scenario does not pose an immediate safety risk but would be navigated differently by a human driver. This approach allows, for example, deviations of 50 cm to the left or right to be classified as normal. If the deviation is between 50 and 75 cm, this is classified as a warning. If the difference exceeds the threshold value of 75 cm, this is a safety-critical classification, and the driver must take control of the vehicle. Next, the area represented by marker 3 indicates the threshold value for the critical limit and is shown as a red line in Figure 41. Exceeding this value should trigger the safety functions and activate a lockout of the component. Marker 4 shows a corresponding exceedance. From this point on, all steering movements of the driver are directly transferred to the real steering wheel of the vehicle. This safety mechanism enables the immediate takeover of control in safety-relevant scenarios. The identification of critical events on public roads can therefore be made based on these points.

The example shown in Figure 41 is intended to explain the basic concept of visualization for the acquired measurement signal based on the deviation between the human and the automated vehicle. The threshold

values for the warning (3 cm) and error (4.5 cm) levels have been arbitrarily set in the figure. The correct values have to be determined by calibration activities during the implementation. For this purpose, the SSW component is tested in a vehicle, which is tested on the test bed under laboratory conditions, and then on a closed proving ground with different speed profiles. As noted, the limit values shown in Figure 41 are purely for illustration of the concept and must be determined and adjusted in the final implementation after an appropriate calibration phase. In addition, the illustration is a completely static view. During a journey, the limit values must be adjusted dynamically on the basis of the speed of the vehicle, since at higher speeds even the smallest movements lead to large changes in the position of the vehicle.

4.4 Justification of the Selected Theory Approach

The theory with a human driver as a benchmark and validation on public roads was chosen because scenario-based approaches have weaknesses in representing reality, and they are not scalable. Validating the safety of a system with pure simulation technology is not fully demonstrable due to reduced complexity from model abstraction. Validations on closed proving grounds can achieve a higher degree of realism, but only a very limited number of tests can be performed due to the complexity of recreating a scenario. Hence, to address the realism weakness of simulation approaches and scaling issues in proving ground tests, a human driver approach on public roads was chosen.

For the generation of scenarios, the measurement-based option was chosen for this research based on the different testing approaches explained in Section 3.6.2. This variant offers the highest degree of realism and can be used to map complex scenarios. By performing test drives on public roads, an automated vehicle can be validated in the best possible way, and at the same time, the functionality of the SS concept can be validated. The described concept of the SS, which can be detached from the vehicle, was chosen for three main reasons. First, the human driver provides a considerable benchmark for performing correct driving activities, and the system allows to measure of human driving behavior with precision and without any distortion and thus; furthermore, the concept deals with de-escalating the capabilities of a human driver in critical scenarios; especially in scenarios where a human takeover is required, an experienced and attentive driver can make a significant contribution to road safety.

The second reason is the independence of the system. By introducing an intermediate layer, which is achieved by the SS, the possibility of an independent action execution is possible. Here, the major advantage is that the movements of the two systems do not influence each other up to a defined point, but this can still be applied in a real driving scenario. The chosen approach thus completely deviates from existing possibilities such as those described by Wang, Guo and Jia (2018a) to measure the influence of a human driver on the steering wheel.

The third reason, which relates to the selected system, addresses the most important topic-safety. The SS keeps the driver connected to the vehicle but also ensures a defined margin. When a defined threshold based on applied force or distance moved is exceeded for a component, the component is automatically locked, and the driver is able to take over the vehicle within milliseconds. This possibility of fast intervention

offers excellent safety for use on public roads and represents an alternative to the current methods, as shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: Video still of public road testing with removed hands (42HOW, 2021).

There are traffic rules defined by legislators on the road that need to be followed by everyone; however, there are also some convenience factors to consider; for example, a vehicle may drive correctly next to a truck, but the passenger sitting in the vehicle may not feel comfortable because of the closeness with the truck (Isermann, R., 2017). Scenarios in which the human driver does not feel comfortable should also be taken into account in the development of the framework. These factors have no direct influence on safety, but they have a negative impact on comfort, and thus, on passengers' trust in the systems. In the context of this research, this aspect is included in the identification and analysis of the behavioral differences between the driver and the system.

4.4.1 Implications of the Theory

The human driver and their behavior have a clear impact on the result. As described by Eliot (2018c), human behavior can vary and, in the worst case, can even have negative effects if inappropriate or incorrect behavior is used as a benchmark. This fact is especially important when human data is used to train AI systems, as the behavioral patterns can be adopted by the software systems, or the system can compare the behavior difference with the SS. In addition, each person's driving style represents a potential bias in the results. Individuals with a high level of safety awareness are likely to respond more rapidly during critical scenarios. In addition, the type of intervention may also differ based on the experience level of the driver.

Another implication that the theory assumes is the presence of control systems such as steering wheel and pedals that can be operated by a driver. In the case of level 4 to 5 vehicles, the interior will change significantly in the future, as control systems will basically no longer be necessary. Today's development and test vehicles, which are classified in the level 4 and 5 range, are generally based on normal production vehicles and therefore contain all control systems, making the theoretical framework relevant.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

4.4.2 Features of the Theory that Enables New Knowledge

This approach fills the gap of existing approaches such as simulation technology by using the two selected approaches (distance and pressure), together with the fact that validations shall be performed on public roads; furthermore, by means of driving on public roads, the scaling factor shall be solved compared to scenario-based approaches on closed proving grounds. Due to the fact that no artificial scenarios with complex control and measurement technology have to be set up, many more tests under more realistic conditions can be performed at the same time. The third point, which speaks for the selection of the concept, addresses safety. In contrast to current methods, in this approach, the driver must always actively stay in the loop and provide feedback to measure behavioral differences. As soon as a significant deviation occurs, control must be handed over directly to the driver to resolve the scenario.

The novelty of the theory lies in the independent detection of the behavior between humans and machines in order to identify critical and uncomfortable scenarios based on the differences. By avoiding any mutual influence up to a safety-critical range, automated systems can thus be tested on public roads in a scalable manner. Through the active and continuous involvement of the driver, a higher level of safety is achieved during validation, as intervention is possible at any time. None of the current validation methods are based on the approach of using a human driver as a benchmark for the evaluation of an automated system. This idea makes the theory novel and addresses the essential drawbacks of simulation technology and real testing on closed proving grounds.

4.5 Key Concept of the Shadow System

4.5.1 Overview

In the context of this research, the SS concept is the overall system that is used for the realization of the theory. The concept is a combination of hardware components and software applications to capture the primary signals of the individual components such as the SSW. In addition, other data such as metadata, time series, videos, and Global Positioning System (GPS) are collected during test drives to provide more context for later activities. The collected data is finally used in post-data analysis activities to assess critical and uncomfortable events that occurred during a test drive.

The SS is based on a black box concept, which treats a vehicle and its components as an unknown system. This is the central concept, as illustrated in Figure 43. For a test drive, additional hardware equipment is installed on top of the control systems of an automated vehicle to measure the required information. This approach allows the generated data of the SS to be acquired without vehicle-specific access to different interfaces such as On-Board Diagnostics (OBD) or CAN bus. A generic design of the SS components is intended to enable universal reusability without adaptation to the respective test vehicle. This should ensure the use of a wide range of vehicle models from different manufacturers.

Figure 43 shows the overall concept, which is divided into two categories. The area with a blue background (existing data) refers to general information that can be easily determined. This area also includes the international OBD II standard since all modern vehicles generally support it. The data form the basis for the final assessment in the post-data analysis process. The yellow-shaded area shows the extension by individual components of the SS. The additional data sources are used to collect further data that cannot be collected via the automated vehicle. In the context of this research, the focus is on the SSW component. All other components could be considered in more detail in future research work in order to gain further information on the detection of critical events.

Figure 43: Illustration of the Shadow System framework components.

In the following sections, individual aspects from Figure 43 are briefly explained to create an overall understanding of the SS concept:

4.5.2 Shadow Steering Wheel

The purpose of the SSW component is to assess lateral functions, such as LKA, in an automated vehicle, in order to provide an understanding of performance and comfort when the system is used in real-world traffic scenarios. The primary objective of the measurement device is to identify safety-critical events and uncomfortable scenarios through continuous comparison of behavioral differences between a human driver and an automated system. A further objective is to apply the system safely on public roads under different environmental and traffic conditions to achieve a high test coverage without simplifying test scenarios. This measurement device also aims to provide an objective and standardized assessment of the performance of an automated system by comparing its performance to that of a human, which is used as an indicator of safe driving behavior. During the execution of tests, a quick and safe takeover of control of an automated vehicle by a human driver is essential in order to prevent accidents. As another objective of the SSW component, it is intended to detect steering movements between human and automated vehicles

independently up to a safety threshold, which prevents mutual interference and enables better observation of the progress of the scenario. Standardization of the method and its ease of implementation by certification organizations during the homologation process is another objective. It is also important for the measuring device to be universally applicable to a broad range of road types and speed ranges. The measuring device is also intended to be of generic design, which allows a universal application for a wide range of vehicle types, manufacturers, and models. The SSW component is intended to serve as an independent measuring device to prevent potential safety risks associated with complex integration into the vehicle system.

4.5.3 Shadow Pedal

The SP component is based on the principle of the SSW measurement device and in principle, fulfills the same purpose and objectives. The only difference is the consideration of the functions. The SP component evaluates the performance of longitudinal functions such as ACC instead of lateral. The focus is on the difference detection of brake and accelerator pedal actuation between the driver and the automated vehicle.

4.5.4 Shadow Guard

The next component is used to monitor the distance of the ego vehicle from surrounding objects. If the distance falls below a defined value, the driver is informed via an acoustic or visual signal to take over control of the vehicle. An example regarding the use of this component is an overtaking maneuver of a truck during which the vehicle falls below a lateral distance of, for example, 50 cm. This distance represents a potential danger at higher speeds, as the slightest steering movement of the vehicle or truck could lead to a collision.

4.5.5 Shadow Light

Another essential influencing factor for camera-based systems is the available light conditions. In this context, the angle of incidence and the intensity of the light can make clear detection much more difficult. A representative example is shown in Figure 26. With the SL component, the mentioned factors like the angle of incidence and luminous intensity can be captured independently. This allows conclusions to be drawn in the post-data analysis as to whether these influencing factors played a role in the occurrence of the critical event.

4.5.6 Shadow View

Rain, snow, dust, or dirt can have a strong influence on the view, especially with purely camera-based systems. A suddenly obscured view or partial visibility of nearby objects can lead to a critical problem. In such scenarios, the SV component is used to measure the degree of impairment.

4.5.7 Shadow Sensor Deception

SSD allows for the detection of unusual movements by the vehicle possibly caused by the obstruction of the sensors. This approach is used to test vehicle behavior, for example, in the scenario when a rock chip hits the windshield on the highway, blocking the view of the camera. SSD can block several sensors at the same time.

4.5.8 Shadow Eyes

This component is used to accurately determine a vehicle's position in the lane. As a result, the orientation of the vehicle can be determined precisely, allowing conclusions to be drawn about its behavior during certain driving maneuvers, such as negotiating a tight curve.

4.5.9 Human Driver

For the execution of test drives, general data on the driver is collected. This includes attributes such as age, years of experience, gender, and driver type (passive, normal, sporty). This data will later be used as information in the evaluation to create a statistical comparison.

4.5.10 Vehicle Configuration

On the one hand, this aspect describes the specification of the vehicle such as make, model, version, and year of manufacture, and on the other hand, information about the existing ADAS/AD driving functions such as ACC and LKA are recorded. Further, in the course of testing, the configuration of the individual functions is also recorded, as these influence vehicle behavior.

4.5.11 On-Board Diagnostics Standard

OBD II is an international standard in the automotive industry for determining certain diagnostic information of a vehicle. It concerns, for example, measured values such as vehicle speed, engine speed, and pedal positions. The SS Framework is designed to capture and store additional data about the vehicle automatically and in a standardized way during a journey. The OBD interface is usually easily accessible in a vehicle and therefore does not require complex integration or access to the board network, as is necessary with CAN or FlexRay, for example. With the additional data, a comparison can be made with the data of the various SS components to ensure correct recording; furthermore, additional data such as the steering angle of the original steering wheel can be collected. These data can bring added value in a future detailed analysis of scenarios.

4.5.12 Weather Conditions

One of the main problems that automated vehicles face today is related to difficult weather conditions. A representative example of this is shown in Figure 26, where the traffic light of an intersection is not visible due to a low sun in a camera-based system. Weather conditions are taken into consideration during test

drives by manually collecting relevant data. In the post-data analysis process, additional information about existing weather services can be integrated.

4.5.13 Road Conditions

In addition to weather information, the road surface condition must also be considered as rain or snow can strongly influence the necessary driving behavior: For example, even if according to road traffic regulations, a speed of 100 km/h is allowed on a route, a human usually reduces the speed to ensure safe driving.

4.5.14 Route

It is also necessary to record the route traveled in order to be able to determine the exact position of a critical event in later data analysis based on GPS data.

4.5.15 Feedback

Irrespective of all the objective data collected during a test drive, the subjective perception of the driver also plays an important role. This component is used to collect feedback via a logbook during and at the end of the drive. These comments provide an insight both on how critical a scenario or the whole drive was from the driver's point of view, as well as the driver's personally perceived well-being.

The concept of the SS framework was chosen because the approach can be used independently of the automated vehicle. Due to the fact that it is based on a black box approach, it can be used without manipulation of the vehicle. This fact plays an essential role in the certification process, as it eliminates the need for complex vehicle-specific system integrations and allows the system to be installed quickly and easily, which increases scalability. In addition, this ensures that the test result is not influenced or changed by the test method.

Another aspect of the selection of the concept concerns safety. In order to keep the driver constantly in the loop and avoid scenarios like the Uber accident, active movements have to be performed by the driver. When a critical event occurs, intervention can take place without delay.

Today, test systems and methods mean that any intervention on the vehicle's control units immediately leads to an influence on the automated vehicle. The SS concept allows the intermediate range between standard driving behavior and critical events to be captured. This makes it possible to determine how comfortable a driver feels in the automated vehicle and in which scenarios a different behavior would be better.

The concept behind the SS has been developed primarily for the use of validation on public roads. Nevertheless, the idea and its associated components can be used in combination with simulators. A central application is required for the standardized recording of existing and new data. In this research, this application is called Shadow Application (SA) and is used in the context of test drives for the recording of all

generated data. The primary function blocks of the application include coordination of the process for the execution of a test drive; visualization of the received data from the individual shadow components; management of reference and master data; acquisition, storage, and upload of measurement data; and management of settings for external devices.

4.6 Introducing the Shadow Steering Wheel Component

4.6.1 Requirements and Use Cases

In this research, the SSW component is selected from the SS framework for recording the steering movement difference during a journey because this is one of the most relevant and difficult control actions for an automated system. To use the SSW component on public roads, the concept must satisfy a number of use cases to ensure safety. A use case is a method for systematically identifying, clarifying, organizing, and describing requirements for a system. The following primary use cases have been identified as essential to the concept in order to meet the safety aspects of test drives and to ensure robust detection and handling of critical events:

- **Safety-first:** Regardless of all the necessary requirements to be considered, safety is paramount. The concept must be implemented in such a way that a human driver can take control of the vehicle at any time without delay in the event of a critical event.
- **Locking:** If a threshold value for the critical level is exceeded, as illustrated in Figure 41, the component must be locked immediately, and all further steering movements must be transferred to the real steering wheel of the vehicle. The limit value can be set for two different parameters. On the one hand, for the force applied to the component and, on the other hand, for the deviation in the movement performed. The real values are determined during the calibration phase of the component.
- **Real-time:** The responsiveness of the system must be near real-time so that values are immediately converted into executable actions.
- **Influence:** For the concept to work, it is essential that the component operate independently of the automated system up to a certain point. The driver must also be aware of this fact when carrying out a test drive. In addition, it is important that the vehicle is not modified in any way and does not influence the behavior of the automated system.
- **Dynamic Limits:** The threshold values for the two stages-warning and error need to be automatically adjusted based on the vehicle speed during a journey in order to restrict the movement area for safety reasons. The limitations concern the distance and force values. The mean value of 3.25 meters was used as a basis for determining the limit values for the distance deviation, as the average lane width in Europe ranges from 2.75 to 3.75 meters.
- **Natural behavior:** The steering movements on the SSW should feel as natural as possible for the driver so that it is perceived as no different from the normal steering wheel is noticeable.

- **Synchronization:** Control movements performed on the SSW component must have an effect on the opposite side, resulting in a natural motion sequence; for example, if the component on the left side is moved up, the system component on the right side must move down.
- **Reactivation:** After a critical event has occurred, it must be possible to reactivate the component after the vehicle has been returned to a safe driving condition. Only after an explicit release may the component be reactivated after a lockout. This is to ensure that the vehicle is again in a safe position and that an automated journey can be continued.
- **Standardization:** The design and implementation of the component must be universal so that it can be used on different models and vehicle manufacturers without any adaptation or vehicle system intrusion. In principle, no dependence on the vehicle should be necessary, which means that the system should be able to determine all relevant information independently.
- **Installation:** The component should be quick and easy to install and remove from the vehicle. In this context, there must also be no damage to existing vehicle parts such as the steering wheel; furthermore, a high level of safety should be ensured during use on public roads.
- **Data consistency:** Complete and high-quality data are required for the final evaluation and validation of the hypothesis. It is essential to ensure consistency throughout the entire testing process in order to ensure uniform data collection and storage.

The use cases ensure that the theoretical concept covers the following three major challenges. The first one is ensuring safety while driving. Under no circumstance should the component compromise traffic safety; furthermore, the system must be developed in such a way that the two steering wheel systems (vehicle and SSW) do not influence each other up to a defined point; therefore, when one system moves due to steering movement, the other system must not change position. The second challenge relates to the system's accuracy and responsiveness. Since the component is intended for public roads and only allows a minimal deviation at higher speeds, its implementation must be highly accurate and responsive in near real-time. This challenge in connection with tests on public roads was described by experts such as Schinkel et al. (2020) as an essential element for a successful application. According to Ross (2016), tolerances as low as 20 ms can lead to safety-critical scenarios in level 2 vehicles. With a delay of 20 ms and a vehicle speed of 130 km/h, a distance of 0.72 meters is traveled.

4.6.2 Design and Interfaces

Figure 44 shows the basic building blocks required to use the SSW and the associated data analysis tools. In addition to the component (shown in blue), a data logger for persistence and a visualization system that displays the data in real-time are required. At the end of a test drive, the data must be uploaded into a central system where harmonization, like timestamp synchronization of the time series data and format standardization takes place, and then the reporting and analysis part is undertaken based on this information. The harmonized database is used for detailed analyses and statistical evaluations.

Figure 44: Illustration of the general Shadow Steering Wheel concept.

The four essential functions of the SSW include an independent measurement of steering differences between vehicle and human performance; safety limits to detect critical events; a universal component design to fit different vehicle makes and models; and data logging to record information of the SSW component and the vehicle. To be able to use SSW on the road, a set of advanced functions are needed. These include an automatic component lock based on distance or force; component reactivation (i.e., safe unlocking); component reset to the initial position; dynamic limits to detect critical events and uncomfortable scenarios; and steering angle of the vehicle, which is provided by the OBD interface. Moreover, other advanced functions necessary are the nonlinear movement of the SSW component (i.e., higher force leads to faster movements), as well as extended data collection through GPS, weather, videos, light, etc. An additional characteristic is that the data transmission from the SSW should be wireless so that there is no interference from cables while driving.

The theory of the SS foresees the installation of additional measuring devices for the detection of behavioral differences without influencing the automated system. The SSW component allows the test driver to perform steering movements independently of the original steering wheel. As part of this research, a design was developed to determine how the data can be collected theoretically in accordance with the defined use cases. In the following, the design variant is presented in detail.

4.6.3 Electronic Design

The electronic version of the SSW system is shown in Figure 45, which uses an additional intermediate layer, which here is referred to as a Sledge and is located between the Base (201) and the Handle (202) to control component movements and execute them in mirrored form between the left and right sides. The Sledge component is the essential design element of the SSW measurement device, as it allows independent movements between the original steering wheel and the device. Steering movements of the human driver are performed by this intermediate layer through mechanical movements. This is done without changing the original steering wheel position. The contribution of this design element allows the use of a human driver as a benchmark for assessing performance based on differences in behavior. An object detection sensor (203) is used to detect the hand of the human driver and the associated activation of the component. If the SSW device does not detect the driver's hand, the device locks and all movements are transmitted directly to the original steering wheel; furthermore, hand detection is used to restore the system

to its initial position if no hand detection is detected for a period of time. Via built-in force sensors in the Sledge, driver movements are measured and passed onto the Data Collection Box (300). The Data Collection Box is another essential design element of the SSW component, as program logic is executed based on the readings from the force sensors. The logic is primarily responsible for positioning the Sledge component. Depending on the measured values, the current position of the Sledge and the speed of the vehicle, the distance of the movement is calculated and executed. Movements on the left and right SSW components are performed in opposite directions in order to ensure a natural behavior. Whenever the left component is moved upward, the right component is also moved downward or vice versa. As part of the program logic, thresholds for detecting safety-critical scenarios are also calculated and verified. If they are exceeded, an automatic lockout of the SSW component is performed. As a result, all movements performed by the driver are transferred to the original steering wheel (100). This function contributes to a safe and rapid takeover of responsibility by the driver in case of an emergency. All collected data is forwarded via a wireless connection to allow visualization and storage of the data. In the later post-data analysis phase, this data is used to assess an event and scenario.

Figure 45: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel with electronic design.

4.6.4 Implications of the Concept

The design concept allows the measurement of behavioral differences without having to intervene in the vehicle's system. This aspect has a positive effect on standardized use in the different vehicle makes and models; however, the introduction of an additional layer and the decoupling of the driver from the vehicle creates additional risk. For this reason, the implementation must be robust and reliable. In case of imminent danger, the driver must always have the option of taking over the vehicle directly. Another implication of the concept is the response of the vehicle and the associated feedback. If a steering movement is performed on the original steering wheel of a vehicle, the position of a vehicle changes immediately during a journey. By using the SSW component, there is no direct reaction because only when a critical event occurs, the component is locked, and from this point on, movements are transferred to the vehicle. The concept also has an influence on steering behavior for the driver, since the SSW component increases the diameter of

the steering wheel. As a result, a minimally larger steering movement has to be performed to have an effect on the behavior. Due to the design of the concept, it can only be applied to vehicles with a steering wheel. For vehicles with levels 4 and 5, this may lead to restrictions in use.

4.7 Advantageous Differentiation to Existing Concepts and Knowledge

In the literature, there are a variety of concepts for the validation of automated vehicles, which are based on the measurement of human behavior. The approaches taken by some of these authors fail to accomplish the objectives of this research. In the case of Wang, Guo and Jia (2018b), they used a model-based approach to capture human steering input via an additional torque sensor; this enabled decoupled detection of the driver's input (their basic concept of the implementation is shown in Figure 46).

Figure 46: Illustration of a steering wheel actuation system of an automated vehicle (Wang, X., Guo, L. and Jia, Y., 2018b).

The issue with Wang, Guo and Jia's approach is that the automated vehicle is directly influenced by steering movement. By installing an additional torque sensor in combination with a toothed ring on the original steering wheel, the influence of the human driver can be measured, but every steering movement is directly transmitted to the vehicle. This means that, compared to the SSW concept, no objective assessment of the difference in behavior is possible up to a critical event.

For the measurement of human intervention in real-time, Schinkel, Van Der Sande and Nijmeijer (2020) present a similar approach, where by using a torque sensor, the applied force of the driver on the steering wheel is measured. Figure 47 shows their modified control system with an additional torque sensor.

Figure 47: Illustration of driver intervention detection with a torque sensor (Schinkel, W. S., van der Sande, T. P. J. and Nijmeijer, H., 2020).

By intervening in the steering system using a torque sensor and then controlling one motor, the steering movements of a human driver and an automated vehicle can be recorded independently of each other. With

this approach, the same measurement result can be acquired as with the SSW component, but the two concepts differ significantly in two aspects. On the one hand, the concept developed by Schinkel, Van Der Sande and Nijmeijer requires a complex integration into the steering system of the vehicle. This involves considerable effort and poses a safety risk. On the other hand, the original behavior of the automated vehicle changes. For the driver, however, their concept has an advantage over the SSW concept. By changing the system behind the steering wheel, the driver can use the original steering wheel normally. With the SSW, the additional structure increases the radius.

Another way to validate the steering movement and determine differences was developed by Inga, Flad and Hohmann (2019). Using two decoupled steering systems, the behavior of two human drivers is recorded independently and then compared. Figure 51 shows the basic setup of the experiment. In their work, the concept is presented based on a simulation approach.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 48: Illustration of human cooperative steering behavior model (Inga, J., Flad, M. and Hohmann, S., 2019).

The basic theoretical idea for measuring behavioral differences is similar to the SSW concept in that behavioral differences are determined independently; however, the approach differs significantly with its implementation, as a second steering wheel is required for data collection. Due to the fact that the SS framework is intended to be used for the validation of automated vehicles on public roads, Hohmann's approach is not ideally suited. In order to perform tests, a second steering wheel would need to be installed in the vehicle, as well as intervention in the vehicle's system. This modification would be associated with corresponding additional safety risks, and this has an impact on the behavior of the driver, since they would have to perform the steering movements from the passenger seat.

An alternative to measuring the driver's torque was proposed by Huang (2020) with a device that can be applied to future steering wheel generations based on Steer-by-Wire (SBW) systems. The system has only been validated in Hardware in the Loop (HIL) tests and needs further research to be used under real environmental conditions. The concept from Huang involves positioning an additional steering wheel above the original steering wheel and placing a Kistler MSW sensor between them to detect the driver's steering movement as shown in Figure 49.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 49: Photograph of a test bench with driver feedback module (Huang, C. et al., 2020).

The concept of Huang with a second steering wheel has a similar fundamental idea as the SSW component, but it differs in a few points. One is that no steering movement can be performed independently between the two steering wheels, as every movement is transferred to the other steering wheel. Another difference in design concerns safety, since the second steering wheel and the additional sensor cover the airbag of the original steering wheel. When used under real environmental conditions, the airbag would therefore have to be deactivated during a journey, which would lead to an intervention in the vehicle system. In addition, the takeover of the vehicle in case of a problem is very difficult due to the second steering wheel, because the original steering wheel is covered by the additional steering wheel, and it is therefore difficult to reach. In Huang's approach, the positioning of a second steering wheel changes the steering behavior of the driver. In the SSW concept, the steering wheel diameter is increased, and in Huang's concept, the distance to the steering wheel is increased slightly, which subsequently has an influence on the pedals.

Another way of recording the behavior of the steering wheel is proposed by Marcano et al. (2020). Figure 50 shows the suggestion in which the steering wheel is decoupled from the steering unit. In this approach, the driver remains connected compared to the SS concept. This approach requires a complex intervention in the existing vehicle system and may affect performance, making the approval process more difficult.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 50: Illustration of a uncoupled steering system for testing an automated vehicle (Marcano, M. et al., 2020).

The concept of Marcano et al. is very similar to the approach of Schinkel, Van Der Sande and Nijmeijer mentioned above. By interrupting the original steering movement of the vehicle and then controlling it via an additional motor, a significant intervention in the system is necessary. This approach has advantages in the development and validation phase in closed environment conditions, as the system works in the background and the steering behavior remains the same for the driver via the original steering wheel. Due to the certification of automated vehicles on public roads, this approach has a significant safety risk due to the system intervention. In addition, the installation is complex due to vehicle integration and must be done individually for each vehicle; thus, this approach does not have a simple and safe application, and it cannot be scaled.

A further approach by Kerschbaum, Lorenz, and Bengler (2014) proposes a steering wheel decoupled from the steering link. As shown in the left part of Figure 51, in the stationary concept, the steering wheel decouples from the steering link and remains at the same position at an angle of 0° while driving in a highly automated mode. On the other hand, in the second concept, which is shown in the right part of Figure 51, there are no visible spokes on the steering wheel. Hence, it does not display its physical orientation to the driver. Kerschbaum, Lorenz, and Bengler wished to test the influence of the visibility of the steering wheel position on the driver. In the stationary variant, the driver knew that the steering wheel was in a neutral position. In the second variant, this information was not available to the driver. As part of their experiment, drivers had to take over the automated vehicle in a curve in a simulation environment. It was found that the steering wheel without visible spokes performed even better than the control condition.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 51: Illustration of a decoupled steering wheel with stationary and rim (Kerschbaum, P., Lorenz, L. and Bengler, K., 2014).

The concept of Kerschbaum, Lorenz, and Bengler differs significantly from the SSW approach, as their focus was on measuring the influence of the visibility of the steering wheel angle in the case of a takeover scenario. Regardless of the different use cases and implementations, the concept is interesting for the SSW concept because for the driver it seems that the steering wheel position has no influence in cases of a takeover. Based on this finding, the design of the SSW concept should not have a significant impact on driver behavior.

A simulation approach to measuring different control interventions in time-critical scenarios was adopted by Schneider, Purucker and Neukum (2015). They determined the effectiveness of different intervention strategies considering safety and controllability. In their experiment, two different use cases were tested: (a) an evasive maneuver by a vehicle and (b) the sudden appearance of a cyclist on the roadway. The two use cases can be compared in parts with the abstract example in Figure 38, which was used as a starting point for the creation of the theoretical framework for this research. During their study, the main objective was to measure the effectiveness of the different interventions while taking into account safety-of-use issues, as well as controllability concerns. It was observed that all steering interventions reduced collision rates in comparison with the baseline condition.

Figure 52: Illustration of steering interventions comparison for two traffic scenarios (Schneider, N., Purucker, C. and Neukum, A., 2015),

The aim of Schneider, Purucker and Neukum's concept for measuring steering engagement is only comparable to the SSW concept to a limited extent since the same journeys were repeatedly performed with different test subjects sequentially in a simulation environment, and the results were compared at the end. A manipulation of the torque on the steering wheel has shown that this has no essential influence on the results. This aspect is an interesting finding since the SSW concept is one that affects torque. Due to the decoupling through the shadow layer, a driver does not have to apply the same force as on the original steering wheel. Besides, Schneider, Purucker and Neukum did not compare their participants' behavior with that of an automated vehicle. This is a prominent issue, as according to Rosenfeld and Kraus (2018), the survey of human behavior in terms of psychological or behavioral factors is a crucial area of research; however, classical methods currently used for this purpose are time-consuming and require exhaustive resources. According to the authors, in the future, testing must take scaling into account; furthermore, the experience of the participants is an essential influencing factor that needs to be considered because a new driver coming into contact with automated vehicles at an early stage in the future will probably show a different behavior toward the machines. Hence, the main drawback with tests like the two virtual scenarios in Schneider, Purucker and Neukum's experiment is that their coverage and scope are always limited.

Hairong (2019) describes another possibility for the detection of critical events based on external sensors such as a cell phone or a GoPro camera. This approach coincides with the independent black box approach but deviates in regard to the interaction with the automated vehicle. Figure 53 shows the concept for detection in detail. Sensors in smartphones, GoPro cameras or similar devices are used for detection. Based on force and gyro sensors, critical scenarios are identified when a limit value is exceeded. A simple example of this would be an emergency brake of the vehicle. After the detection of a critical scenario, the concept extracts the functions and fuses them using a duration and deviation-based concept. In the last step, the final evaluated events, which have been classified as critical, are loaded into a central database system.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 53: Illustration of a proposed system flow for unusual events identification (Wang, H., 2019).

The concept of Hairong does not perform an immediate detection of critical events based on the comparison of behavioral differences as it is performed in the SSW concept. Each intervention has a direct impact on the vehicle, which is why no direct measurement of the behavioral difference is possible. Still, the work describes a good approach to extract relevant functions at a detected event and subsequently use them for a refined assessment; furthermore, critical events are loaded into a central database to enable statistical evaluation. The work of Hairong does not provide exact trigger values for the detection of critical events. In the literature, however, a proposal for lateral acceleration and longitudinal deceleration is described by Singh and Kathria (2021) in the same context. Their values are listed in the following figures:

Table 4: Critical event triggers and their threshold values (Singh, H. and Kathuria, A., 2021).

For the SSW concept, these values provide a good starting point for detecting critical events, which are identified based on the force expended; however, as described in Section 4.1, the final threshold values for the system are determined based on calibrations under real conditions.

All mentioned works have a common difference compared to the SS theory described in Section 4.3 and the SSW concept. None of the considered works foresees an independent measurement of the behavior without influencing the automated vehicle. From this point of view, the main functions of the approaches are similar, but the final idea, which in this research has been realized by the SS and in particular by the SSW, shows a new form for the detection of differences between human and machine in order to finally identify critical on public roads. By using this strategy, it is possible to incorporate a significantly broader range of scenarios.

The theory and concept for the validation of automated vehicles based on the detection of behavioral differences is novel in the way it has been presented. There are similar works dealing with the detection of behavioral differences but none of the approaches is comparable to the SS theory or the concept of the

SSW component because a human driver is used as a benchmark for the objective assessment and measurement of the behavior up to a critical event can be performed independently; furthermore, the theory allows the measurement of the intermediate range between a normal scenario and a critical event. The detection of this range allows inference of the comfort and confidence factor of a human driver in the automated system.

An essential aspect compared to other work concerns the environment in which the tests are performed. The SS framework is designed for the certification of automated vehicles on public roads to enable realistic validation. In addition, the approach considers a vehicle as a black box, eliminating the need for complex system integration. This has a positive impact on the universal use of the measurement system and scaling of the tests. Compared to existing works, which are often based on scenario-based testing in simulation environments or proving grounds, more tests can be performed under more realistic conditions.

The main similarity with existing works is the collection of data through a human driver. In the literature, there are different concepts that measure the input of the driver to get information about the behavior; however, all known concepts have the consequence that any intervention immediately leads to a change of the automated vehicle or requires a complex system; furthermore, differences are not considered in real-time or on public roads. The SS framework, on the other hand, makes human driver intervention relevant only when a safety-critical threshold is exceeded.

4.8 Drawbacks

Currently, the SSW concept, like any other test approach, also has drawbacks. On the one hand, scalability on the level of simulation models can never be achieved by performing test drives on public roads. Additionally, a scenario cannot be repeated with the same or adjusted parameters. Another disadvantage results from the basic principle, which is based on the experience of a human driver. Every human has a unique behavior based on the existing experience, which influences the objective assessment of a critical event to a certain degree. Additionally, the SSW concept also assumes the presence of control options for the human driver, such as a steering wheel or pedals.

For the general addressing of the scaling problem, the SS theory could be implemented in the long-term as a native integration in an automated vehicle. When SBW systems are used in combination with appropriate software, individual components such as the SSW system could be replaced. In addition, a wave approach could be introduced for validation and the associated release of a system, which would allow a gradual roll-out of automated functions in the field. If a new function or update works without problems over a certain distance, this version of the automation can be made available to a larger group. The wave concept can be coupled with the competence of a driver. The first tests are only carried out by qualified experts as part of the homologation process. Once this initial phase is successfully completed, the automated system can be made available to experienced individuals with additional qualifications. A controlled roll-out can thus be carried out on the basis of a wide range of experience and qualification levels.

It might be possible to record all sensor information when attempting to solve a repeatability issue for a real scenario. This data could be recreated using a VIL approach. This method has limitations in scaling and

requires a complex infrastructure to execute; therefore, only critical scenarios detected on public roads would need to be repeated. Finally, to address the human influence factor, it would be conceivable to determine the sensitivity of a human driver in advance by performing benchmark examples. By means of defined scenarios in a simulation environment, which have to be completed with the SSW component, the difference in behavior between different drivers can be determined. This difference could then be taken into account when setting the limits for warning and error.

4.9 Relation to Aims and Objectives

An objective performance assessment can be carried out using the theoretical framework described in this research, which compares the behavior of a human driver and an automated system. Through this approach, the first aim of this research is addressed. To achieve the related objectives, the SS framework was developed to provide a holistic view when performing validation. A standardized design ensures that the test method works on vehicles of different makes and models. A safety-first approach was utilized in the development of this theory in order to ensure its safe application on public roads. For the validation of the theory, the SSW component from the SS framework was selected to provide evidence of operation based on differences in steering movements.

The second aim of this research is to identify critical scenarios in a production vehicle. To achieve this objective, test drives are performed on public roads with the SSW component. Using a standardized testing method, this measuring device records the behavioral differences and determines additional data in order to obtain more contextual information for the post-data analysis of a scenario. The theory described and the concept developed fully address the defined aims and objectives of this research.

With regard to the defined research questions, the developed SS framework and the SS component described in detail present a possibility of how automated vehicles can be tested on public roads in the future as part of the homologation process. The high level of standardization and associated reusability allow for more tests to be performed safely and in less time. In addition, tests on public roads offer a better degree of realism compared to predefined scenarios that are simulated on a proving ground; furthermore, the concept addresses the second research question for the objective assessment of a driver's comfort level. Not every scenario has to lead directly to a critical event.

Chapter 5

Methodology

5.1 Theoretical Framework and Concept Realization

The theoretical framework and concept were validated to achieve the aims and objectives described in Section 4.1. For this purpose, the SSW component was developed from the SS framework to perform a validation of the concept in the context of real test drives. For the consistent recording and visualization of data, a separate software application called SA was developed. This ensured that all relevant data for the validation of an automated vehicle was recorded and available for the post-data analysis and assessment of traffic scenarios. In addition, the application ensured that the defined test drive workflow was followed, making different drives comparable. The action research method was applied to implement the hardware and software components as well as the execution of the drives. On the basis of several iterations, various tests were carried out in order to achieve an improvement of the entire solution on the basis of the results and the findings derived from them. With the final version of the SSW component and the SA software, tests were performed on public roads to identify critical scenarios when using automated functions.

5.1.1 *Justification of the Approach*

The approach based on SS theory and the SSW concept was chosen because it allows automated vehicles to be objectively validated and evaluated on public roads using a standardized method. The required measurement equipment can be installed in different vehicles within a few minutes without additional adaptation. Compared to scenario-based tests on closed proving grounds with complex test setups, such as UFOs, significantly more scenarios can thus be considered with less effort. This test variant provides the most realistic results for evaluating a system since the vehicle is operated in its normal environment and is not artificially influenced by predefined scenarios, additional measuring devices or test methods.

The safety aspect plays the most important role when conducting tests on public roads, as the driver and all other road participants must be protected in the best possible way at all times. Since a human driver with appropriate experience is now considered an excellent benchmark for the safe execution of journeys, the approach surveys the performance of the automated vehicle in comparison with humans. By actively involving the driver during the execution of tests, the approach prevents distractions from occurring, such as the one described in the incident with UBER.

5.1.2 *Test Drive Workflow*

Before defining the individual data types and their structure, the process of execution and associated data acquisition to be accomplished must be defined. Figure 54 shows the process that was defined for the test execution in the context of this research. As the first step, a new “Test Drive” is started to provide a

container for all further activities. Based on the stored metadata, the vehicle used is then selected in the second step. Subsequently, the "Test Parameters" are defined at the beginning of the drive, which include data such as current weather conditions, road type, and driver information. All data from the first three steps is stored in a common result file and serves as a basis for all further steps. Before a test drive can be started, all the used equipment, like SSW, data logger for the OBD interface, and GPS connection, must be checked. In this step, it is possible to specify exactly which measurement data is to be recorded. After the preparation phase, a test drive can be executed. As soon as the execution is started, data from the individual systems must be collected and stored. While collecting data from different sources, it is particularly important that the recorded measured values use a synchronized timestamp; otherwise, there could be problems with comparisons during the analysis phase. After the completion of the test drive, the system provides a summary with basic information. Based on this information, the driver can decide whether the recorded raw data should be uploaded to a central cloud environment for further processing. If the raw data is uploaded, the data is harmonized and converted into an analytical format so that a clean and performant data structure is available for complex analyses on large datasets. A detailed description of the data structure, attributes, and formats is described in the upcoming sections. The final step in the process involves data analysis. In this step, using standardized reports, the collected data is graphically processed and supplemented with aggregated information.

Configuration of the used equipment can be done before the steps are described. It is also possible to store the necessary meta-, master-, or reference data. These steps were not explicitly mentioned previously since the focus was placed purely on the execution of test drives, in which support processes do not play any role.

Figure 54: Illustration of the data collection workflow for test drives.

The described mapping process of an end-to-end data pipeline for the acquisition of all relevant data is done by the SA software mentioned above. The software is used to manage the full data lifecycle process for context data and measurement signals; furthermore, data is kept in a harmonized and structured store to enable future analysis. To ensure data consistency, a normalized data model with primary and foreign keys is used; furthermore, all attributes are mapped with uniform data types. In the following sections, the different attributes are shown including their format and an example. In addition, the source of the data point is also given. This allows for making cross-validations, comparisons, and benchmarks among different test drives. Different third-party tools are used to analyze the data, including MATLAB, Tableau, Mode Analytics, and Microsoft Excel. In order to analyze time series data in detail, MATLAB is used. With the support of these tools, a wide variety of visualizations can be created, such as line diagrams, or several signals can be

compared with each other; furthermore, the tool allows the calculation of Key Performance Indicators (KPI) such as the maximum speed of a drive. For exploratory analysis of data, the Business Intelligence (BI) tool Tableau is used to compare data based on dimensions and measures. For complex analysis, the online tool Mode Analytics is used to create more complex evaluations and analyses with the support of the Python programming language. As a last tool, Microsoft Excel is used to manually enrich graphics with additional information in order to present them in this research.

5.2 Data Collection Structure

5.2.1 Master Data

Master data is essential for a specific business case or process. This kind of data represents the most important information in the context. Figure 55 shows an overview of the primary master data and its relation to the SS. An essential point in data acquisition concerns the uniform use of identifiers and formats to achieve a harmonized representation in the later processing and evaluation. For the unique identification of each data object, a Globally Unique Identifier (GUID) is used, which is a 128-bit text string. This unique ID is also used for referencing between objects to ensure referential integrity based on a primary and foreign key. In the context of this research, the following specification was selected for the acquisition of time and date:

Date and Time Format (ISO 8601)

Pattern: yyyy-mm-ddThh:mm:ss:ffff+|-hh:mm

Example: 2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00

Figure 55: Illustration of the Shadow System core domain model.

A description of the individual domain objects and their contents, including an example, is provided below.

Test Drive

The core object in the domain model for the SS is represented by the “Test Drive” entity. This object serves as a container for summarizing all relevant data types and adds general information to them to establish context for a test drive. The relevant data is used for unique descriptions in later data analysis. Each test drive is identified by a GUID and can subsequently be used for statistical comparisons among different test drives.

Table 5: Master data for a test drive.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>General</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Start Date/Time	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Automatic
End Date/Time	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Automatic
VehicleId	1 (a reference to vehicle master data Table 6)	Manual
DriverId	1 (a reference to driver master data Table 8)	Manual

Vehicle

The corresponding metadata comprises specific details of the vehicle used. Basic information such as make, model, version, and year of manufacture is recorded here. In addition, the existing automation functions are also noted. In the context of a test drive, the domain object “Test Drive” refers to a vehicle. The configuration used for the individual functions is recorded in a logbook, as these values can change during the course of a drive.

Table 6: Master data for a vehicle.

Attribute	Data type/Example	Source
<i>Vehicle</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Make	Text (Audi)	Manual
Model	Text (A5)	Manual
Version	Text (2.0 TDI Quattro Tiptronic)	Manual
Model Year	Integer (2019)	Manual
Market	Text (Europe)	Manual
VIN	Text (WAUZZZ8K3FA000000)	Manual
Image	Blob 	Manual

Vehicle Configuration

In the following table, the most important basic data of the vehicle and the settings of individual automation functions are collected in order to use this information for detailed analysis and comparisons in the future.

Table 7: Master data for vehicle configuration.

Attribute	Data type/Example	Source
<i>Technical data</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Powertrain.Configuration.Drive	4WD	Manual

Powertrain.CombustionEngine.MaxPower	130 kW	Manual
Powertrain.Body.Style	Shooting brake	Manual
Powertrain.Transmission.Type	Automatic	Manual
Vehicle.Information.SpeedLimitation	228 km/h	Manual
Vehicle.Information.Weight	1678 kg	Manual
ADAS.LKA.Available	1 = yes, 0 = no	Manual
ADAS.LKA.FeatureMode	Early, standard, late	Manual
ADAS.LKA.ActionType	Active (e.g., steering car), passive (sound, vibration, visual)	Manual
ADAS.ACC.Available	1 = yes, 0 = no	Manual
ADAS.ACC.FeatureMode	Slow, standard, sporty	Manual
ADAS.ACC.ActionType	Active (e.g., braking car), passive (sound, vibration, visual)	Manual
ADAS.EBA.Available	1 = yes, 0 = no	Manual
ADAS.EBA.FeatureMode	-	Manual
ADAS.EBA.ActionType	Active (e.g., braking car), passive (sound, vibration, visual)	Manual

Driver

When conducting test drives, data must also be collected from the driver as this additional information can subsequently be used during evaluation; for example, to make comparisons between different age groups or years of experience. Another aspect being considered is the driving style. Table 8 is used as a reference for recording the behavior of a driver.

Table 8: Master data for driver.

Attribute	Data type/Example	Source
<i>Driver</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
First name	Text (e.g., Manuel)	Manual
Last name	Text (e.g., Schwarz)	Manual
Age	Integer (e.g., 37)	Manual
Driving experience (years)	Integer (e.g., 18)	Manual
Gender	Enum (e.g., male)	Manual
DrivingStyleId	GUID (a reference to driving style Table 17)	Manual

Logbook Data

Specific datasets can change during the course of a drive. A classic example of this is the weather, which can in turn have an influence on-road and lighting conditions. The driver uses a digital logbook to record changing framework conditions, which logs a change by means of a timestamp and the selected value by the driver.

Table 9: Logbook data structure.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>General</i>		
TestDriveld	1 (a reference to test drive Table 5)	Automatic
<i>Weather condition []</i>		
WeatherConditionId	1 (a reference to weather condition Table 12)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Manual
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Manual
<i>Wind condition []</i>		
WindConditionId	1 (a reference to wind condition Table 13)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Manual
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Manual
<i>Road condition []</i>		
RoadConditionId	1 (a reference to road condition Table 10)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Manual
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Manual
<i>Country []</i>		
CountryId	1 (a reference to country Table 14)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Automatic
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Automatic
<i>Ambient light []</i>		
AmbientLightId	1 (a reference to ambient light Table 15)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Manual
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Manual
<i>Traffic Condition []</i>		
Traffic Condition Id	1 (a reference to traffic condition Table 16)	Automatic
Start	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Manual
End	2019-04-06T16:47:451211+01:00	Manual

5.2.2 Reference Data

Reference data values are defined by different parties for reuse purposes. This helps avoid redundant and inconsistent values; furthermore, it ensures that no different terms and notations are used for the same value. Moreover, the administration is done from a central place, which reduces administrative effort and ensures clarity. Table 10 to Table 18 show the reference data used in this research, including the corresponding value lists. The reference data described is determined, for example, when the test

parameters are defined during the execution of a test drive. The management, selection, and storage of the values are carried out via the SA.

The following tables describe the essential reference data and their corresponding values used by the SA. The values are fixed in the application to ensure consistency. Certain values can also be defined on the fly to record changing conditions.

Table 10: Reference data for road conditions.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Road condition</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Dry, wet, ice, sand	Manual

Table 11: Reference data for road type.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Road type</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Urban, highway, rural, residential	Manual

Table 12: Reference data for weather conditions.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Weather condition</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Sun, rain, fog, snow	Manual

Table 13: Reference data for wind condition.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Wind condition</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	No wind, moderate, strong, very strong	Manual

Table 14: Reference data for a country.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Country</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Austria, Germany, Italy, Hungary, ...	Manual
ISO2	AT, DE, IT, HU, SL, HR	Manual
ISO3	AUT, DEU, ITA, HUN, SVN, HRV	Manual

Table 15: Reference data for ambient light.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Ambient light</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Dawn, day, dusk, night	Manual

Table 16: Reference data for traffic conditions.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Traffic Condition</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Average, accident, roadwork, congestion	Manual

Table 17: Reference data for driving style.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Driving Style</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Conservative, standard, sporty	Manual

Table 18: Reference data for road lane.

Attribute	Value	Source
<i>Driving Style</i>		
Id	GUID	Automatic
Name	Excellent: the lane is clearly and completely recognizable Good: small parts of the lane are not recognizable or have low contrast Bad: the main parts of the lane are not recognizable or have low contrast None: no lane is visible	Manual

5.2.3 Metadata

Metadata provides additional information regarding the master and reference data. It enriches the context of the various types of data and allows more information to flow into the subsequent data analysis. This type of data can be seen as a glue between measurement data and all other data. Metadata is also commonly used in practice for data representation, search, and classification. It can also be used for statistical comparison among different datasets.

Results Data

General meta-information about the test drive, such as length, duration, and distance, is recorded as results data; furthermore, additional values can also be recorded in aggregated form by the SS, such as the number of events that occurred, including the corresponding category.

There is also the option to store statistical information about the availability of the automated functions if these can be provided by access via the OBD II interface.

Table 19: Results data for test drives.

Attribute	Example	Source
<i>Drive</i>		
Duration	23 minutes	Automatic
Distance	17.6 km	Automatic

MaxSpeed	132 km/h	Automatic
Shadow Steering Wheel		
Events.Error	10 (number of occurrences)	Automatic
Events.Warning	134 (number of occurrences)	Automatic
MaxSpeed	132 km/h	Automatic
ADAS		
LKA.Availability	0.83 > 83%	Automatic
EBA.Occurrence	2 (number of occurrences)	Automatic
ACC.Availability	0.89 > 89%	Automatic
Reported events		
Events.Report.Error	3 (number of manual events reported by the driver)	Automatic

During the execution of a test drive, according to the process defined in Section 5.6, different types of data are generated, stored, and made available for the final data analysis. Metadata and reference data are also used in this context. A detailed explanation of the values used is given in the following section.

5.2.4 Measurement Data

The last type of data related to the SS is represented by measurement data. This form of data is a time series of data points or video streams with a timestamp, which is generated by the individual external devices, mainly the OBD II interface, GPS sensor, and camera. Moreover, the components of the SS, like the SSW, provide a series of signals for the detection of the difference. Table 20 shows the individual signals and their format.

Table 20: Measurement data overview.

Attribute	Example	Source
<i>Shadow Steering Wheel</i>		
Timestamp	2019-04-06T15:33:123214+01:00	Automatic
Force.Left.Up	10 g	Automatic
Force.Left.Down	0 g	Automatic
Force.Right.Up	0 g	Automatic
Force.Right.Down	10 g	Automatic
Differentiation.Left	+13°	Automatic
Differentiation.Right	-13°	Automatic
Safety.IsLocked	1=yes, 0=no	Automatic
Safety.HandDetected	1=yes, 0=no	Automatic
Gps.Latitude	47.016025	Automatic
Gps.Longitude	17.584923	Automatic
Gps.Speed	112 km/h	Automatic

Gps.Altitude	453 m	Automatic
Vehicle (OBD)		
Speed	112 km/h	Automatic
Pedal Position	50%	Automatic
Temperature	23°	Automatic
Shadow Application		
Front Camera		Automatic
Side Camera		Automatic
Mirror Camera		Automatic

5.2.5 Data Storage

Structured and standardized storage of data on a file system plays an important role if the data is to be processed automatically in later steps. Automation is only possible with an identical storage structure, including the associated name designation. This enables the one-time evaluation of a single test drive, as well as the recalculation of several test drives after the change of calculation rules. Figure 56 presents the schematic diagram of the data structure that is used for storage on a local file system and for post-data analysis processes in a cloud environment.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 56: Illustration of the result storage structure.

5.3 Development of the Shadow Steering Wheel Measurement Device

5.3.1 Elements and Components of the Design

The purpose of the SSW component is to measure the difference between a human driver and a machine to identify critical events and uncomfortable scenarios on public roads when using automated vehicles. This measurement device was realized based on the theoretical concept described in Section 4.6. In multiple iterations, four generations with different versions were developed using the action and experiment-driven research model approach. The following section presents the results of the final version, based on the fourth generation of the component. This version was used for the execution of test drives on public roads in order to validate the theoretical concept by the identification of critical events. Figure 57 shows the three main parts of the SSW component, which have the following functions:

Base

The Base component is used for mounting on the original steering wheel of the automated vehicle and includes two guide rails for connection to the Sledge component and a gear band for the transmission of movement. It is attached to the original steering wheel by two hooks on the front and two on the back.

Sledge

In the center of the SSW component is the Sledge, which detects the force movement from the driver via two sensors and executes the movement via a DC motor. A digital RC DC motor with 270° rotation is installed in the middle of the part to control the movement (the specification of the DC motor can be found in Table 34 in Appendix I). The movements of the DC motor are transferred via a toothed wheel to the Base via a toothed wheel belt. This causes the second level to move left or right based on control commands calculated and executed by the central Data Collection Box; furthermore, there is also a sensor for detecting the driver's hand. During the operation of the SSW system, movement is only possible when the driver's hand is detected, otherwise the component is locked and every steering movement is transmitted directly to the original steering wheel.

Handle

The third layer is represented by the Handle component, which was used to detect the movement of the driver and passed on to the Data Collection Box. With a minimal margin of less than 1mm, the Handle can be moved to the left or right. For the detection of the driver's control commands, high-precision force sensors are mounted on the second layer, which gets activated by the third layer. As soon as force is applied to one of the two sensors per side, this triggers a movement of the second layer to immediately release the force. The driver's input is converted into a mechanical movement by design. This subsequently leads to a simulated steering movement. This movement reduces the force from the sensor and once it is back to zero, the DC motor stops. On the opposite side of the steering wheel, however, the same movement is performed in the opposite direction. A detailed description in the form of a technical drawing is given in Appendix II, where all additional parts necessary for the entire component are described.

Figure 57: Illustration of the Shadow Steering Wheel of generation 4.

5.3.2 Realization

The structure of the three realized layers is shown in Figure 58. By using a round guide bar, it was possible to reduce the resistance and friction at the wayside to a minimum so that steering movements no longer had any influence on the steering wheel of the vehicle. The result of the optimization can be observed when the vehicle is at a standstill because when performing a steering movement on the SSW, the original steering wheel should not move. In addition, the steering wheel angle of the original vehicle was measured during tests in the laboratory while using the SSW component. The results showed that the angle of the original steering wheel did not change. This ensures that the components do not affect each other.

Figure 58: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel layers in version 2 of generation 4.

A force sensor was installed to detect human movement, as shown in Figure 59. Two force sensors were installed per component in order to be able to detect the movements to the left and right. The position of the first force sensor is visible in Figure 59. The second sensor is placed on the opposite side of the Sledge component. The measuring range of the selected sensor is from 0.1961 to 14.7099 newton (20 to 1500 grams), which allows the measurement of very small force differences up to large force. A calculation of the position movement of the Sledge component via the integrated DC motor is possible on the basis of the recorded measured values, which are determined by the force sensors.

In order to achieve a more natural motion, a curve was implemented using a slowly increasing acceleration and an equal deceleration to avoid an unnatural motion caused by fast DC motor acceleration. The implementation was produced using the sigmoid function to calculate an S-shaped graph. With this approach, the linear motion behavior was replaced. The sigmoid function is a bounded and differentiable real function with a positive and negative first derivative and exactly one inflection point.

Figure 59: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel force sensor in version 2 of generation 4.

The new position of the DC motor is calculated by the Data Collection Box and passed on to the two DC motors with the formula (6.0). This formula was used on the basis of the sigmoid function in order to be able

to change certain parameters in the context of the calibration. The individual parameters and their use are listed below.

$$f(x) = \frac{k}{1 + v^{a+bx}} \quad (6.0)$$

Equation parameters:

$f(x)$ = The change of the position of the DC motor in degrees.

k = The maximum value of the function. For the SSW DC motor component, the value 180 is used to define the maximum rotation value.

v = The logarithm base for changing the curve slope.

a = The horizontal displacement of the function

b = The horizontal displacement and slope of the function.

The curve resulting from the function is based on the used parameters for the SSW component; this is shown in Figure 60. By introducing the displayed curve, a delay in the acceleration or deceleration of the SSW component was achieved. This made it possible to eliminate the unnatural behavior at the beginning or at the end when executing a movement via the Handle, which was noticeable in a jerky movement.

Figure 60: Plot of the acceleration and deceleration curve used for the Shadow Steering Wheel (desmos.com, 2020).

To optimize the measurement accuracy, the force area of the sensor had to be precise in the design of the Sledge and the force point of the pusher component. The pusher shown in Figure 61 is positioned very precisely on the integrated force sensor to record accurate values.

Figure 61: A rendered image of the integrated Pusher in the Handle component of the Shadow Steering Wheel.

A full description of all the hardware components used to build the two handles and the Data Collection Box is available in Appendix I.

5.3.3 Circuit Diagram

A circuit diagram, including wiring for the hardware components, is shown in Figure 62. For the development of the program logic, the software Arduino IDE was used. The circuit diagram was created using the online tool EasyEDA.

Figure 62: Circuit diagram of the Shadow Steering Wheel component.

5.3.4 Driver Hand Detection

An additional sensor was also integrated into the Sledge to implement a hand-detection function, as shown in Figure 63. A TCRT5000 IR line sensor was used to detect the hand on the SSW component. The exact specification of the sensor is described in Table 34.

Figure 63: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel component with a hand detection sensor.

The sensor is used to detect whether the driver has his hand on the Handle of the SSW component. Only in an active state, it is possible to execute a movement. Otherwise, the component locks and the steering movement is transferred directly to the original steering wheel of the vehicle. If a critical limit is exceeded during SSW use, the component is automatically locked and all further movements are transferred directly to the original steering wheel. To release the lock, a reset function was implemented. When the driver returns the vehicle to a safe driving condition, the hand needs to be removed from the SSW component for 3 seconds. This signal automatically resets the position of the two handles to zero and the driver can start again with the execution of steering movements via the SSW component.

5.3.5 Data Collection Box

For the storage of all electronic components, which are necessary for the acquisition of the signals, control of the handles, and transmission of the data to an external device, a separate Data Collection Box was developed. This box was installed in the upper area on the inside of the original steering wheel. Because it is positioned on the inside, there is no interference with steering movements. In terms of safety, there are no problems since the box is located behind the airbag, and in the case of a deployment, no parts of the SSW system are located in the relevant deployment area. Figure 64 shows the interior of the Data Collection Box. This matches the individual electronic components so that the installation of the parts can be carried out easily and there is no overheating of the parts. The box can be opened and closed quickly via a lid with a magnet.

Figure 64: Photograph of the Data Collection Box.

The box contains an ESP32 microcontroller with a custom-developed software for the implementation of the use cases described in Section 4.6. The collected measurement data is sent to a computer via Bluetooth for visualization.

5.3.6 Program Logic

The program logic for the acquisition of sensor data and execution of control movements on the SSW component based on a defined logic is shown in the flow chart in Figure 65.

Figure 65: Flow chart of the Shadow Steering Wheel program logic.

The program follows a set of steps starting with the "Initialization" of the program logic when all relevant modules like Bluetooth, GPS and the SSW force sensors are activated, and the program is configured with the parameters described in Figure 66. The second step is to "Set limits based on vehicle speed," where the maximum movement distance for the Sledge is determined based on the vehicle speed. This mechanism is

intended to ensure that only small movements and earlier locking of the SSW component are performed at higher speeds. In the third step, "Read force sensor values," the individual measured values of the various force sensors are recorded, and the movement for the Sledge component is subsequently calculated on the basis of the configuration parameters and determined limits.

The developed control software offers a number of parameters such as the maximum value of the force until the component is locked. Figure 66 presents a list of the parameters that were used to perform the test drives.

```

////////////////////////////////////
/// Calibration ///
////////////////////////////////////
#define Rotation_Blocking_force_level 65 // Emergency block level of force sensor. If the value of one force sensor exceeds the value the servo rotation will be blocked.
#define Max_Servo_Angle_Step 30 // Max. angle of the servos to move per input. A higher value makes the move of the handle faster.

////////////////////////////////////
/// Configuration ///
////////////////////////////////////
#define max_angle 180 // Max angle of the servo's
#define Box1_Servo_pin 18 // Signal pin for servo 1
#define Box2_Servo_pin 23 // Signal pin for servo 2
#define FSR1_pin 4 // Signal pin for force sensor 1
#define FSR2_pin 15 // Signal pin for force sensor 2
#define FSR1_Standard 60 // Default return value in % of force 1 when a weight of 200g is applied
#define FSR2_Standard 60 // Default return value in % of force 2 when a weight of 200g is applied
#define FSR_Max_Value 2000 // Defines the max. value provided by the sensor
#define LineFollowing_Sensor_pin 5 // Signal pin for line force sensor (hand detection)
#define GPS_Rx_pin 26 // Signal pin to receive data from GPS modul. Attention: They wiring needs to be on pin 27
#define GPS_Tx_pin 27 // Signal pin to transmit data to GPS modul. Attention: They wiring needs to be on pin 26
#define Baud 9600 // General baud rate
#define Device_Name "SSW-" // Name of the ESP32 that is visible for Bluetooth connections
#define BT_pair_waiting_time 15000 // Milliseconds delay for Bluetooth connection
#define Servo_reset_delay 1000 // Milliseconds delay for Servo reset after hand is removed
#define smoothness 4.4 // Servo acceleration smoothness. The value must greater than 2.
#define export_csv true // Overwrite the standard serial output by a CSV format

```

Figure 66: Software parameter of the Shadow Steering Wheel component.

In the case of distance deviation, the angle of the DC motor (0 to 180°) was used to calculate it. Each degree means a Sledge displacement of 2.26 millimeters when using a gear wheel with a radius of 13 mm. The following formula was used to calculate the distance per degree:

$$f(x) = \frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot r}{360} \quad (6.1)$$

Equation parameters:

f(x) = The change of the distance in millimeters.

r = The radius of the gear used to convert the angle of the DC motor into a path movement.

If the measured value of a force sensor exceeds the defined error limit for distance or pressure, the components are immediately locked and no further calculations and associated movements are performed. As soon as a lock is activated, all steering movements of the driver are transferred directly to the original steering wheel of the vehicle from this point on. If no limit value is exceeded, the new position of the Sledge layer is calculated, and in the next step the result is executed via the DC motors. Through this process, the detected steering movement of the driver is transferred to the SSW component, and the difference of the movement compared to the vehicle can be determined. In the last step "Send data via Bluetooth," the acquired data is made available via Bluetooth for external applications such as the SA. The data package is transmitted in JSON format and contains the information shown in Figure 67.

```

{
  "servo-angle": 30,
  "force1": 12,
  "force2": 0,
  "latitude": 47.018019,
  "longitude": 15.482913,
  "speed": 50,
  "is_locked": 0,
  "date_time": "2021-04-17T15:13:43.125"
}

```

Figure 67: JSON data package of the Shadow Steering Wheel.

5.3.7 Installation

The final version of the SSW component, which was used for the execution of test drives, is shown in Figure 68. The handles are mounted on the left and right sides of the original steering wheel. The two SSW components are connected via cables to the Data Collection Box, which is shown in the upper part of Figure 68.

Figure 68: Photograph of the Shadow Steering Wheel realization in version 3 of generation 4.

Figure 69 shows the flexible fastening straps, which can be adjusted to the shape and size of the vehicle's steering wheel via various levels. The four hooks of the Base component are used to connect the straps on the rear and front.

Figure 69: Photograph of the flexible connectors for the Shadow Steering Wheel.

5.3.8 Calibration

For the functional check of the software on the ESP32 and calibration of the sensors, component tests were carried out specifically for the use cases defined in Section 4.6. Due to the individual production and high precision of the force sensors, an initial calibration was to be carried out once so that both force sensors got exactly matched to each other. For the calibration of the force sensors, a mass of 200 grams was placed on the sensor, and the thereby generated force value should return 60% of the maximum total capacity (1.5 kg) of the sensor. The value of 60% was chosen due to the characteristics of the force sensor used, as the relevant measurement range for the SSW component is between 0 and 200 grams. As shown in Figure 70, the electrical resistance of the RP-C7.6-LT Thin Film force sensor does not return linear values. On the x-axis, the applied force in grams and the y-axis shows the resistance value is shown. This fact requires an individual determination of the value based on the relevant measuring range, which was defined during the calibration.

Figure 70: Illustration of the RPC7.6-Lt force sensor characteristic.

In case of a deviation from the measured values, the installed sensors were adjusted in the program logic via the parameters FSR1_Standard and FSR2_Standard. Here the determined measured value of the sensor must be entered, which indicated over 60% during the evaluation; thus, the sensitivity of the force sensor may be regulated by variable resistors so that the value of 60% can be set.

Operation Areas

For the SSW component, there are three operating zones (normal, warning and error), which were explained in Section 4.3.4. For the determination of the limits of the individual zones, the mean value of 3.25 m for the width of a road was assumed in the context of this research since in the EU, the width is between 2.75 - 3.75 m. Table 21 lists the calculated widths of different zones. The normal operating zone was assumed to be 70% of the lane width and the critical zone was assumed to be 3%.

Table 21: EU road parameter.

Parameter Road	Value	Unit
Mean road width in EU	3.2500	m
Critical threshold distance	3 %	
Critical threshold distance	0.0975	m
Normal operating area	70 %	
Normal operating area	2.2750	m
Warning operation area	0.7800	m
Warning operation area (50%)	0.3900	m
Normal & warning operation area (50%)	1.5275	m

Figure 71 shows the areas of the individual zones including a vehicle with an average width of 1.85m, such as an Audi A5.

Figure 71: Illustration of the average operation area of a road in the EU.

Steering Wheel Parameter

A normal steering wheel of an Audi A5 was used to calculate the limit values of the SSW component; these values are listed in Table 22. Depending on make, model and variant, there may be differences in size. This factor was not taken into account in this research.

Table 22: Steering wheel parameter.

Parameter Vehicle	Value	Unit
Audi A5 steering wheel diameter (1)	35.600	cm
Audi A5 steering wheel perimeter	111.841	cm
Distance per steering wheel degree	0.311	cm
Audi A5 width (without mirrors)	1.850	m

The listed values and the range of movement of 0.226 mm per degree at the SSW component were used as the basis for calculating the limits, which are shown below.

Threshold Limits

The described road and steering wheel parameters were used to define the limits of the individual operating zones of the SSW component. Three-speed zones were defined in the context of this research, ranging from 20 to 50 km/h, 51 - 100 km/h, and 101 - 130 km/h. Based on these speed values and a fixed assumed reaction time of the driver, the average distance traveled by the vehicle was determined. The result was used to determine the lateral movement of the vehicle within a speed range. Using the calculated value "Vehicle steering wheel movement" and the SSW parameter "Distance per degree" of 0.226 mm per degree, the limit values for the operating ranges warning and error were calculated. Table 23 shows all calculated values stored as calibration parameters and used during the execution of the test drives.

Table 23: Shadow Steering Wheel threshold limits.

Parameter	Value	Unit	Value	Unit	Value	Unit
Minimum vehicle speed of range	20.000	km/h	51.000	km/h	101.000	km/h
Maximum vehicle speed of range	50.000	km/h	100.000	km/h	130.000	km/h
Mean vehicle speed of range	35	km/h	75.5	km/h	115.5	km/h
Driver interaction time	1.5	s	0.8	s	0.7	s
Vehicle distance traveled	9.72	m/s	20.97	m/s	32.08	m/s
Vehicle distance traveled per interaction time	14.58	m/s	16.78	m/s	22.46	m/s
Vehicle lateral movement (α)	5.990	degree	5.209	degree	3.894	degree
Vehicle steering wheel movement	1.861	cm	1.618	cm	1.210	cm
Vehicle steering wheel movement	18.610	mm	16.183	mm	12.097	mm
Maximum SWW movement (error)	82.346	degree	71.607	degree	53.528	degree
Maximum SWW movement (error)	18.610	mm	16.183	mm	12.097	mm
Maximum SWW movement (warning)	57.642	degree	50.125	degree	37.470	degree
Maximum SWW movement (warning)	13.027	mm	11.328	mm	8.468	mm

5.3.9 Recommended Improvements From the Last Implementation

During the validation of the SSW component, some points were identified that would lead to an optimization of the solution; however, these points were not implemented in this research as they would not have had any influence on the results. So, in future enhancements, the findings should be implemented in a revision of the design.

Component Size

The size of the SSW measurement device has been significantly reduced over multiple iterations; however, for more productive use, the design should be revised again to reduce the distance between the Handle and the steering wheel to a minimum. Moreover, the size of the Data Collection Box can be reduced by at least 50% with a simple adjustment. This would make the overall system much more compact.

External Status Lights

In the latest implementation of the Data Collection Box, no status lights have been installed in the external area. For a quick overview of the current status of the component, it should be possible to visually read at least the following information:

- Power (on/off)
- GPS position available
- Vehicle speed
- Distance limitation of Sledge in %
- Component locked (yes/no)
- Bluetooth connection established (yes/no)
- Battery level
- Hand detection (yes/no)

Dual Motion Sensors

In the final version of the SSW component, a motion sensor was installed only on one side. For future generations, the components on the left and right sides should be identical so that steering movements can be executed on both sides. Such a change would also require an adjustment of the control software so that the sensor with the highest force is given priority and thus, the movement execution is accordingly prioritized.

5.4 Data Collection

5.4.1 Tool Review and Selection

For the collection of all relevant data, which is necessary for the realization of the SS theory and the SSW component, a custom-developed software with the name SA was used. This software covers the data acquisition process and also provides data synchronization; furthermore, the complete end-to-end test drive workflow is covered. When using several external devices for data acquisition, such as different cameras and an external GPS system, the time stamps must be synchronized and stored in a unified way. The resulting data from the test drives were stored in a Microsoft Azure cloud environment for further processing. After each test drive, data was uploaded to the central storage system.

In the context of this research, the individual SA software was developed since no existing applications on the market enable the holistic mapping of the test process as well as the required integration of the shadow components. For instance, there are various standardized tools on the market for the collection and visualization of data and the control of processes. Various manufacturers such as National Instruments or Keysight offer ready-made solutions for data acquisition. In addition, there are other data acquisition and visualization tools such as MATLAB or DIAdem from National Instruments, which allow a wide variety of visualizations and calculations. The standardized products of the manufacturers always have a certain

focus, such as data acquisition or visualization. The type of data visualization required, which was described in Figure 41, is not an Out-of-the-Box (OOTB) functionality provided by existing software products. As a result, several tools would have to be combined in order to cover all relevant aspects. For the seamless coverage of the entire test drive workflow from Section 5.6, which ranges from the management of the master data to the upload of the harmonized data, no suitable solution was found. Another argument for custom development concerns the operability of the application while driving; for example, to perform log entries about changing weather conditions or generate manual reports of critical scenarios. In addition, the user interface had to be designed for use with a touch device since data is collected in the vehicle while driving.

5.4.2 Shadow Application as a Custom Development

This section describes the main elements of the software developed for the purpose of this piece of research. Section 5.1 explained the core workflow for the data acquisition, including the corresponding meta-, master-, reference-, and measurement data and their structure and values. With the SA software, all required data was recorded from the various data sources during a test drive. Since the SSW component is custom developed, the decision was made to record and visualize the data using custom-developed software. The advantage of this is that the process of the test drive can be mapped exactly in a User Interface (UI), and the structure of the result data can also be defined individually; furthermore, this approach enabled the synchronization of time stamps when using different external data sources such as OBD loggers, GPS sensors, and cameras. Another reason for the custom development is the visualization of the SSW data in near real-time and the display of two y-axes. On the primary y-axis, the difference signal, including the threshold values for warning and error, are displayed. In addition, the metadata can change during a drive. A digital logbook with predefined values is essential for recording this information.

For the realization of the application, the Universal Windows Platform (UWP) technology from Microsoft with C# as the programming language was used. Further, all UI elements were optimized for use on a device with a touchscreen during a test drive.

To illustrate the internal structure of the SA software, Figure 72 shows the individual layers and underlying functionalities. The first layer, "Application" was used for the input and output of data at the UI. In addition, this layer controlled the process of the test drive to collect all necessary data according to the flow. In the middle layer, different services orchestrate the data recording and synchronize the background tasks with the UI. The data from the SSW component is delivered via a service using Bluetooth and displayed in the form of a line graph on the UI. In addition, all data is stored in a measurement file. The lowest layer was used for the persistence of the various data. This included master, meta, and test drive data in JSON format. All recorded signals from the SSW component and the vehicle were stored in separate CSV files, including the corresponding time stamp. Video data from the individual sources were also stored separately as MP4 files. Documentation of the graphic user interface and the individual functions is described in Appendix I.

Figure 72: Illustration of the Shadow Application software components.

5.4.3 Optional Data Logging

International SAE standard J1979 pertains to recording of vehicle data in the automotive industry (Lawrenz, W., 2013). This standard regulates the provision of basic data via an interface. Usually, the OBD interface is provided in modern vehicles to read out this type of data. Typical data that are read out are as follows: vehicle speed, throttle position, and brake position. A detailed definition of the available OBD parameter IDs can be found in various specifications or on related websites, for example, SAE International (SAE, 2016). In most cases, the OBD connector is located in the foot area, console area, or glove box of vehicles. Figure 73 shows the position and the connector for an Audi vehicle.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 73: Photograph of an Audi OBD interface (motor1.com, 2019).

For data interpretation, a translation file called the DBC II file is used in all cars (Hennessy, B., 2019). Manufacturer-specific DBCs must be used to translate the raw data. In this research, the OBD interface of

the automated vehicle was integrated by means of the SA software to obtain a plausibility check of the SSW data; for example, the recorded speed of the SSW component was compared with the real vehicle speed in order to detect deviations. When driving in a tunnel, there can be a difference, because the GPS of the SSW component has no signal. In such a case, the SSW component was automatically locked by the control software and all movements of the driver were automatically transferred to the vehicle. The OBD interface also recorded additional data, such as the steering angle of the original steering wheel.

By recording OBD data, the measurement data can be enriched with additional information that is helpful in a detailed post-data analysis. In principle, however, the SS concept and related components like the SSW envisage that the individual components can also operate independently; for example, in the case of the SSW system, the vehicle speed can be determined via the built-in GPS antenna. As an alternative, it is also possible to retrieve the GPS position directly from the vehicle bus system if the corresponding coding of the signal is known to the manufacturer. A detailed description of how standardized values can be determined via the OBD II interface is described using an example in Appendix V.

5.5 Test Drives

5.5.1 Assessment Structure

For validation of the SS theory and the SSW concept, several test drives were performed on public roads to provide evidence based on data. The test drives were performed on different highways and federal roads in Austria in 2021. All test drives were limited to the region of Graz and its surrounding area. At the time of data recording, the highways available there had a wide variety of characteristics, such as road works and dynamic speed limits. In addition, there were also highway sections with tunnel systems and different types of lanes, ranging from two to four lanes.

All test drives were carried out by the same person since the implementation of the system is a prototype and would have required training or instruction for new drivers. In addition, the independent execution of the drives allowed the behavior of the system to be optimally observed. Due to the character of the system, a very high level of attention and experience were required during use in order to quickly and safely take control of the vehicle in the event of a problem. Due to the intensive involvement with the system as well as special attention, it is possible that the results deviate in comparison to a neutral driver; however, this aspect was not considered in more detail in the context of the research since only experts are used in the context of vehicle certifications, and their competencies extend beyond those of a normal private driver. When carrying out the tests, an attempt was always made to carry out the tests neutrally and without bias by neither overreacting nor underreacting in different circumstances.

All test drives were carried out during the day and under good weather and light conditions, as these general conditions are ideal for automated systems, and therefore fewer problems occur. For the basic validation of the SSW concept, these drives were sufficient. In addition, an analysis and description of

identified scenarios were easier since driving at night or in rainy conditions makes it difficult to capture the environment with cameras.

5.5.2 Context Information

For the post-analysis of scenarios identified during a test drive, additional metadata is an important source of information to gain a better understanding of the context. This information can be determined manually, semi-automatically, or fully automatically. Depending on the type of data, the additional data can be retrieved via public Application Programming Interfaces (API) from third-party providers. An exemplary interface would be the connection to a weather service or road traffic road operator. For the enrichment of the measurement data of the SSW component, context information was collected for the overall scenario. This type of data was important in the post-data analysis phase in order to make a well-founded statement and draw conclusions about the influencing factors that were present when a critical event occurred. Information about the vehicle, weather conditions, driver, and configuration was collected at the beginning of a test drive. In addition, information about light and road conditions was extracted during the post-data analysis phase. Due to the limited number of test drives, the data extraction process was performed manually. For better standardization, most of the process steps could be automated in the future.

5.5.3 Scenario Analysis and Assessment

For consistent assessment of identified scenario within the data analysis, some essential information was selected to describe the context at the time of occurrence. Table 24 describes the attributes that were documented for each scenario. The data was recorded automatically by the SA or manually by the driver at the beginning of a test drive; furthermore, changing conditions (e.g., the weather changed from clouds to rain) were documented during the drive.

Table 24: Attributes for the documentation of critical traffic events.

Date and Times	The start time of the identified event is stored in the UTC date and time format.
Vehicle Speed	Speed of the vehicle at the time of event detection (in km/h).
Location	GPS position at the instance of the critical event, where the threshold of the limit was exceeded, was stored in the decimal degree format.
Weather Condition	Weather conditions during the test drive; are classified according to the values described in Table 12.

Light Condition	The luminosity of the image; is classified into five values, as described in Table 15. For visualization, this type of scale was used:
Road Lane	Condition of the road lanes during the scenario; reference values are listed in Table 18.
Road Type	The type of road is defined based on the values described in Table 11.
Road Condition	The type of street is determined based on the values described in Table 10.
Activated Vehicle Features	Assistance systems are active at the time of the event occurrence, including the specified configuration.

For the assessment of an identified scenario, the four categories defined in Table 25 were used. The determination of a value was based on the criticality of the driver and other road participants. The determination of a value was based on the criticality of the driver and other road participants. The assignment of a classification to a scenario was carried out on the basis of the real recorded data and the associated information. Due to the fact that it is data on public roads, without the intervention of the human driver, the automated system could have handled the problem on its own; nevertheless, without the intervention, a scenario could have reached a higher criticality. Since the intervention is dependent on the human driver's perception, the result is a subjective observation and evaluation. An exact reproduction of a real scenario is not possible, which means that the alternative variants cannot be determined. The criticality can change in the course of a scenario or there can be overlaps of the categories. In this research, the most critical point was used for the assessment.

Table 25: Classifications for traffic scenarios.

Critical	The human driver had to take over the control to avoid a serious traffic accident.
Warning	Without the intervention of the human driver, the traffic scenario could have led to an accident.
Advisory	There was a discrepancy between the human driver and the automated system but without any safety-relevant influence.
Normal	The scenario was handled correctly and safely by the vehicle.

5.5.4 Test Vehicle

A production Audi vehicle was used in this research to carry out the test drives in the specified region. Table 26 lists the most important data about the vehicle. The vehicle was equipped with four ADAS functions. For the validation of the SSW concept, primarily the LKA function was relevant since it is used for the automated execution of steering movements to keep the vehicle autonomously within a lane. This vehicle was selected because Audi is in the premium segment of the automotive industry and the mentioned functions have already been developed over several generations. In addition, very similar systems are in use in other brands and models of the VW group, which means that there is a wide distribution on the market.

Table 26: Details of the vehicle used for the test drives.

	Make	Audi
	Model	A5
	Model Year	2019
	Market	Europe
	Assistance Features	LKA, ACC, BSW, EBA

Most vehicle manufacturers offer configuration options for various assistance systems so that the behavior of individual functionalities can be personalized as per the driver's needs; for example, distance from the ego vehicle to the target vehicle can be defined for an ACC function. Figure 74 shows an example from the Audi used. The first setting relevant to the ACC function is the distance to a target vehicle. Audi offers five different options for distance, as shown in the figure. With this setting, the driver can define the minimum distance between the ego and the target vehicle. These values can be adapted during a drive; however, for test drives, the value set at the beginning of the drive was maintained throughout.

Figure 74: Photograph of an Audi ACC configuration.

Furthermore, Audi offers the option to define acceleration behavior, as shown in Table 27. The driver can select from the three different options shown in the last line of the table: comfortable, balanced, and sporty.

¹ https://static.kufatec.com/media/image/6a/29/1d/41925-automatische-distanzregelung-acc-fuer-audi-a5-f5-_600x600.jpg

Table 27: Audi settings for adaptive cruise control (AG, A., 2018).

Systems	comfort	auto	dynamic
Engine/transmission	balanced	balanced	sparty
Steering	comfortable	balanced	sparty
Dynamic steering*	comfortable/indirect	balanced/direct	sparty/direct
Suspension control*	comfortable	balanced	sparty
Sport differential*	moderate	balanced	sparty
Engine sound*	subtle	subtle/sparty ³⁾	sparty
ACC*	comfortable	balanced	sparty

A similar configuration is usually available for LKA, where the intervention time of the vehicle can be defined. A vehicle's behavior changes during a drive based on the various settings described. Audi offers two settings for LKA that the driver can select. The following description provided in Audi's original owner's manual explains the available options "Early" and "Late."

"Adjusting the steering time and vibration warning applies to vehicles with Audi active lane assist. You can adjust individual active lane assist settings in the Infotainment system. Select in the Infotainment system: "MENU" button > Vehicle > left control button > Driver assistance > Audi active lane assist.

Steering time

Early: in this setting, the corrective steering happens continuously to help keep the vehicle in the center of the lane.

Late: in this setting, the system provides corrective steering just before a wheel goes over a detected lane marker line." (AG, A., 2018)

As part of the data collection process, the vehicle configuration used during the test drives was logged. This information was taken into account in the data analysis and may also be used for future analyses.

5.5.5 Data Acquisition

The Audi A5 was equipped with the listed software and hardware components described in Table 28. These were used on all test drives recording data from the SSW component and collecting additional data from the vehicle via the OBD interface. In addition, a video camera was mounted behind the windshield to record all details of the drives. The recorded videos were used for post-processing scenario analysis.

Table 28: Data capturing equipment used during test drives.

Software	The custom-developed SA software was used for all test drives to capture meta- and measurement data in standardized ways; furthermore, all data was recorded with synchronized timestamps for simplified post-data analysis. Details about the usage of the SA software are available in Appendix I.
----------	--

Video Camera	<p>A Logitech BRIO ULTRA-HD PRO webcam was attached to the windshield to record the events on the road for further analysis.</p> <p>Specification</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resolution: Full HD (1080p) ▪ Wide-angle: 65°, 78°, 90° <p>Recording Settings</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resolution: Full HD (1080p) ▪ Framerate: 30 fps ▪ Wide-angle: 75°
Data Logger (OBD)	<p>The Kvaser Memorator Pro 2xHS v2 captured the standardized OBD vehicle data via the SA software (for further information, see Section 5.4.3).</p>
SSW Component	<p>For all test drives in version 43 of generation 4, the developed measurement device was used. Details about the component were described in Section 5.1.1.</p>

5.6 Implications of the Selected Methodology

The presented method based on the SSW component has some implications that have to be considered when using this type of testing solution. The SS theory is based on the idea that a human driver can be used as a benchmark for the performance assessment of an automated vehicle (*cf. Chapter 4*). The consequence of this aspect is that the experiences and behaviors of a driver have an essential influence on the results. In this context, the results of the method may be affected by a difference in behavior between drivers. Additionally, decoupling the driver from the original steering wheel of the vehicle may result in a further behavior difference since not every steering movement directly leads to a change in the vehicle's position. Currently, an expert driver with a high level of attention is required to perform driving with the SSW component, since the operation and implications of the SSW system must be known; furthermore, the human driver must also understand how the vehicle can be taken over in case of a critical event to de-escalate the scenario. Another limitation of the method is the replicability of an identified event. Due to the fact that the drives were performed on public roads, the recorded data only provided basic information about the scenario. The method did not allow for detailed system information of the automated vehicle, which is needed for RCA in case of a critical event. This information can only be obtained through direct vehicle integration and cooperation with the system manufacturer.

In order to get a complete view of human and vehicle behavior, further components of the SS framework are necessary. The scalability of the method has advantages compared to tests on closed proving grounds. At the same time, the approach has certain limits if validations are to be performed regularly, such as for new software updates, under different conditions like weather conditions, lighting conditions, and different countries. Due to the large number of influence parameters and a theoretically infinite number of scenarios, only a fraction of the possible scenarios can be covered by this method. Another implication related to the variance of test parameters concerns the adjustment possibilities of ADAS functionalities. The behavior of an automated vehicle changes as parameters are adjusted, requiring repeated test drives to provide an objective assessment for the performance of the system with the defined settings. The SSW method can also only be applied to vehicles that have a steering wheel installed. For future level 4 and 5 vehicles, the current approach would not work.

5.7 Ethical or Philosophical Considerations

The concept developed in this research and the associated methods, tools, and implementations do not present ethical concerns. It only takes into account the fact that the methodology is designed for use on public roads during the development and testing phase. This means the system must always be used in a safe environment by trained and experienced drivers to avoid any critical driving scenario. Since a validation phase is about testing a new system, unknown problems with critical consequences can always occur in reality. Due to the fact that there can always be a failure or unforeseen problem when using the system, ethical problems may arise in this context. Hardware or software components are equally affected and must be handled with appropriate care. The safety of people and the environment must at all times be the priority and under no circumstances should the level of danger rise during the execution of a normal journey with an automated vehicle.

As part of the performance of test drives, the personal data of the driver was documented for use in data analysis. The data was collected with the consent of the participants concerned. In addition, videos were recorded on public roads. This data was used in the data analysis of critical events to understand the entire scenario and to generate documentation. In all visual material published in this research, persons and vehicle license plates have been made unrecognizable in order to comply with the European General Data Protection Guidelines (GDPR) and to respect the privacy guidelines of private individuals.

Part 3:
Validation of the Shadow System Framework and
Implemented Shadow Steering Wheel Component

Chapter 6

Results and Analysis

6.1 Public Road Test Results

6.1.1 Test Drive Execution

The results of this research consist of four identified scenarios with different criticality, which were detected when driving an automated vehicle on public roads. A total of approximately 650 km were tested with a standard vehicle using the SSW component. Two safety-critical scenarios were recorded on this distance using the developed method, which would have led to serious consequences if the driver had not taken over. The other two scenarios could also have led to a problem, but would not have been life-threatening for the driver or other road participants.

The identified scenarios were used to demonstrate that problems can occur under certain conditions by using a production vehicle that is approved for public use. Without a quick intervention by a human driver, normal traffic scenarios can very quickly become problematic. This is especially true for scenarios at higher speeds on the highway. Observations have also shown that difficulties mainly occur in more complex traffic and road conditions, such as in a construction zone or areas with many road markings. In the case of easily recognizable and continuous guidelines, such as on the highway, the performance of the tested vehicle appears to be very good.

In the following sections, the four relevant scenarios are described in detail and information about the context is provided. It is also shown, based on the recorded data of the SSW component, how the behavior differed between the human driver and the automated vehicle and at what point a takeover occurred due to a safety-relevant threshold being exceeded. The metadata table for the documentation of a test drive provides only part of the available data. Due to the comprehensive data size, the presentation is limited to essential information. Section 5.1 presented all data attributes of the full context used to describe the selected scenarios; furthermore, a slight adjustment of the background has been made in image areas where textual descriptions were inserted to increase contrast and, thus, readability.

6.1.2 Scenario 1

Backdrop

The first scenario identified during the test drives occurred in the area of a highway exit. At the time of the event, the vehicle's LKA and ACC systems were active. The automated system did not recognize or

interpret the markings correctly, resulting in problematic positioning of the vehicle in the lane. Without the intervention of the human driver, the scenario could have had serious consequences. In the following, the context of the event and sequence of the scenario is described, and an analysis of the recorded SSW data is provided. Based on this information, the behavioral differences between the human driver and the automated system are shown. Table 29 summarizes the most relevant metadata about the identified scenario.

Table 29: Metadata of scenario 1.

Date and Time	2021-04-17T15:13:43 (UTC)
Vehicle Speed	103 km/h
Street Type	Highway
Light Condition	
Weather Condition	Partly cloudy
Road Condition	Dry
Road Lane	Excellent (double lanes)
Activated Vehicle Features and Configuration	<p>LKA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Time of intervention = Late <p>ACC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distance level: 2 ▪ Acceleration: Balanced

Location

In Figure 75, the location of the critical event was on the highway A9 in Graz/Austria while moving in the direction of Vienna and it occurred during a regular drive, close to an exit of the highway. The speed limit in this section was 100 km/h at the time of data recording.

Figure 75: Illustration of the event location for scenario 1.

Scenario

This scenario occurred on a highway with functions ACC and LKA activated in normal ambient conditions. Before the critical event appeared, the drive was normal and did not cause any problems. Frame A in Figure 76 shows that the road lanes are doubled, the outermost lanes are solid and the inner ones are dashed. This marking allows the ego vehicle to turn left or right; however, a vehicle in the immediate left or right lane is not allowed to change into the current vehicle's lane. Another notable characteristic in this example is the truck in front. Due to its size, the visibility of the ego vehicle is limited; for example, lane division is not visible and the size of the truck also obscures the overhanging traffic signs.

In Frame B, approximately 3.3 seconds later, a slight deviation of the vehicle from the left lane can be seen. At this point in time, this deviation does not pose a problem. In comparison to Frame A, however, it is apparent that the lane is divided into a left and a right lane. The limited visibility due to the truck in front is still present, and the road signs are only partially recognizable.

A significantly larger deviation from the lane center can be clearly seen in Frame C, compared to the previous Frame B. This change in the scenario occurred within approximately 0.8 seconds compared to the previous frame. At this point, the vehicle tried to align itself in the center using the right lane and would have continued to follow this lane without further intervention. A turn to the right would not have been a safety-relevant scenario if the vehicle had positioned itself correctly and in time. The route for the navigation would have to be recalculated to bring the vehicle back onto the original path.

In this specific scenario, however, the driver had to intervene. In Frame C, the left and right distance markings clearly show that the vehicle is entirely located in the middle of the road immediately before the exit and would, therefore, potentially exit. This could lead to a serious accident since the vehicle is traveling at approximately 100 km/h and is heading straight for the apex by remaining in the middle of the lane.

In the last Frame D of the present scenario, the dangerous impact zone is shown in the center of the exit. The automated system did not show any sign of slowing down to avoid the apex, nor to deviate to avoid it. In the case of an accident, impact protection is designed to absorb the collision energy as best as possible in order to keep damage to a minimum. In this scenario, there could have been an unbraked impact at a speed of approximately 100 km/h. Hence, this would lead to a considerably serious accident. In the worst case, it could even lead to a fatal outcome for the car occupants. Compared to the previous images, in Frame D, the entire road sign appears visible, as the truck in front has passed and it no longer restricted the view. The total duration of the critical scenario was about 3 seconds. Had the driver been distracted during this period, this could have had serious consequences.

Figure 76: Scenario 1 with context information and sequence details.

Analysis

In the post-data analysis of the scenario, based on the recorded data of the SSW component, there was a correction by the driver before the immediate intervention. The increase in the difference compared to the original steering degree is visible in marker 1 of Figure 77. This indicator marks the human driver's maneuver to steer continuously to the left after approximately 16 seconds. Since the ego vehicle in the example continues the course in the middle of the lane in the turning area, a correction was carried out by the driver. This adjustment is shown by marker 2, which also exceeds the defined limit for the steering intervention. By exceeding this limit, the SSW component was locked, which is shown by marker 3, and the driver took over control of the vehicle.

Immediately after the lock, a strong correction to the left was carried out, as shown in marker 4. With this intervention, the vehicle was brought back into safe driving condition. After completing the maneuver, the SSW component was unlocked and returned to a neutral position. This change can be seen in marker 5, where the SSW difference signal returned to zero, and the "Is Locked" signal was reset.

Figure 77: Analysis of scenario 1 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.

Summary

Scenario classification: **Warning**

This scenario must be classified as a „warning“ since an accident could have occurred without the intervention of the driver. In the worst case, the vehicle would have driven into the turning area at approximately 100 km/h without braking. The exact cause analysis for the vehicle behavior is not covered in this research. But on the basis of the recorded video material, it can be seen that certain parts of the road were covered by the truck in front. Whether such visual restrictions can lead to dangerous scenarios in standard scenarios should be considered in the future.

6.1.3 Scenario 2

Backdrop

This scenario occurred during a drive on a highway in the afternoon with normal light and road conditions. The vehicle was in the far right lane, with a turn nearby onto another highway. In the 38-second-long scenario, the vehicle left the active lane with the LKA and ACC activated and carried out an unallowed lane crossing. Table 30 summarizes the most relevant metadata information about this scenario.

Table 30: Metadata of scenario 2.

Date and Time	2021-04-15T12:44:10 (UTC)
Vehicle Speed	87 km/h
Street Type	Highway

Light Condition	<p>Channel: Luminosity</p> <p>Source: Entire Image</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Mean: 119,41</td> <td>Level: 239</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Std Dev: 57,30</td> <td>Count: 227</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median: 115</td> <td>Percentile: 97,66</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pixels: 2073600</td> <td>Cache Level: 1</td> </tr> </table>	Mean: 119,41	Level: 239	Std Dev: 57,30	Count: 227	Median: 115	Percentile: 97,66	Pixels: 2073600	Cache Level: 1
Mean: 119,41	Level: 239								
Std Dev: 57,30	Count: 227								
Median: 115	Percentile: 97,66								
Pixels: 2073600	Cache Level: 1								
Weather Condition	Partly cloudy								
Road Condition	Try								
Road Lane	Excellent (single lanes)								
Activated Vehicle Features and Configuration	<p>LKA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Time of intervention = Late <p>ACC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Distance level: 3 ▪ Acceleration: Balanced 								

Location

The scenario occurred near an exit onto another highway (A2; see Figure 79) on a highway in Graz/Austria (A9) moving in the direction of Slovenia. The speed range allowed in this section was 100 km/h at the time of data recording, as shown in the left part of Figure 78. Due to the high volume of traffic, the speed was adjusted to approximately 85 km/h in accordance with other vehicles. Figure 78 shows a dynamic speed display with a maximum speed limit of 100 km/h on the highway. The contrast of the display panel can be a problem for cameras depending on the lighting conditions. Additionally, the angle at which the camera is capturing may also cause problems. In the example given, such a problem occurred only a few frames after the recording. The speed display disappeared for the camera from one moment to the next, as can be seen in the right part of Figure 78.

Figure 78: Video still of scenario 2 with dynamic speed limitation.

Scenario

Frame A in Figure 79 shows the initial scenario. The vehicle was in the center of the right lane. The red marker in the image represents the total width of the lane by means of 10 sections. A section thus represents 10% of the available width of the lane. The blue markers to the left and right of the lane help determine the deviation from the center.

Figure 79: Scenario 2 with context information and sequence details.

In Frame B of Figure 79, after 17.455 seconds in the scenario, a slight change in vehicle position can be seen by approximately 10% to the left. This was carried out automatically by the LKA and not corrected by the driver. The scenario was not critical at this moment. Additionally, it must be noted that there was another vehicle in the left lane with a slight offset to the rear. Frame C of Figure 79 shows the scenario after 18.288 seconds, where a clear deviation of the vehicle compared to the lane center can be seen. This change was approximately 33% compared to the starting point and represented a critical event at this point, as the vehicle slightly overlaps with the left-side lane. The scenario was de-escalated by a manual intervention of the driver, and the vehicle was brought back into the correct position. Without this manual correction, the vehicle would probably have continued to change lanes, and this could have led to serious consequences.

This scenario must be classified as „critical“ since the vehicle left the lane without acoustic warning or visual information when LKA was active. This could have led to an accident if the driver had not actively intervened, considering that there was another vehicle to the left with very little offset. If the driver had not been active at this moment, for example, the reaction time and the associated vehicle position would have changed significantly. The total duration of the critical scenario lasted about 1.6 seconds from the first steering movement to the correction. Without active observation of the road and vehicle behavior as well as immediate correction by the driver, such a scenario could have hardly been corrected.

Analysis

In the following section, data from the SSW system is analyzed in detail in order to assess the behavior of the human driver. In Figure 80, the 38 seconds of the scenario are represented on the x-axis. In the first few seconds, small and short manual corrections to the left and right can be seen by the driver. These have no significant influence on driving behavior and can be classified in this context as pure comfort corrections. From the 18th second onward, there is a clear increase of the correction to the right side, represented by an orange dashed line, within a few milliseconds. The change is highlighted in Figure 80 by marker 1. The correction is so strong in this scenario that the red horizontal line is exceeded. Consequently, both SSW handles were locked (see marker 3). From this point on, the signal “Is Locked” became active, and the steering movement of the driver was directly transferred to the original steering wheel. This activation allowed the driver to return the vehicle to a safe position. The blue dashed curve in the area of marker 4 indicates that the steering wheel was briefly moved to the left to compensate for the counter-steering and brought the vehicle back into the correct position on the road.

After the successful intervention, the driver briefly removed his hand from the left Handle of the SSW component. This gesture informed the SSW system that the scenario was back in a safe state and the assistance systems of the vehicle were fully recovered. With this confirmation, the SSW component was allowed to reset its position to the initial state and the locking of the Handle was removed; marker 5 shows the reset mechanism. The primary signal representing the difference goes back to 0 degrees. At the end of the scenario, there were other slight corrections by the driver. These signals show that the SSW component was reactivated and continued to detect the next event.

Figure 80: Analysis of scenario 2 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.

The total duration of the critical event, including the associated correction, was two seconds. A detailed analysis of the recorded raw data of the event shows that only 102 ms (00:18.218 to 00:18.320) elapsed between the start and the exceeding of the defined safety limit for the applied force. In Table 31, the second line shows that the force at the right sensor (Force (right)) jumps from 5.41% to 42%. Subsequently, the value exceeds the safety limit of 65%, as can be seen in data line 5. As a consequence, the SSW component was locked, which can be seen by the change of the value -90 to -80 in the column "Is Locked."

Table 31: Raw data analysis for scenario 2.

Row	Duration [ms]	SSW Difference [°]	Force (right)	Force (left)	Is Locked
1	00:18.148	18	5.41	0.00	0.00
2	00:18.218	7.83	42.00	0.00	-90.00
3	00:18.269	18.01	61.00	0.00	-90.00
4	00:18.320	29.70	64.00	0.00	-90.00
5	00:18.320	29.70	69.00	0.00	-80.00
6	00:18.321	29.70	69.00	0.00	-80.00

Summary

Scenario classification: **Critical**

The scenario described in this section must be categorized as "critical" since the vehicle crossed the left lane and tried to make an unauthorized lane change without any notification to other road participants. The issue was caused by an incorrect behavior of the active LKA. The problem may have been caused by the Y bifurcation and the presence of dashed lines. As this research focuses on the detection of deviations that can be observed in the driving behavior of automated systems and human drivers, the above statement is purely based on conjecture.

6.1.4 Scenario 3

Backdrop

This scenario presents a critical event on a federal highway, which could have had serious consequences without the intervention of the driver. Table 32 summarizes the most relevant metadata information about the identified scenario.

Table 32: Metadata of scenario 3.

Date and Time	2021-04-23T13:18:23 (UTC)
Vehicle Speed	99 km/h
Street Type	Federal Highway
Light Condition	
Weather Condition	Partly cloudy
Road Condition	Try
Road Lanes	Excellent (single lanes)
Activated Vehicle Features and Configuration	<p>LKA</p> <p>Time of intervention = Late</p> <p>ACC</p> <p>Distance level: 2</p> <p>Acceleration: Balanced</p>

Location

This scenario was recorded on a particularly narrow course of a federal road on a steeply sloping area, as illustrated in the left top section of Figure 81. The maximum speed limit of 100 km/h was allowed in the identified road section. This speed was appropriate for a straight roadway, and the vehicle could manage it

without any problems. At the time of the journey, the ACC system along with automatic speed regulation and LKA was active. The peculiarity of the course of the road was a close combination of a tight left curve followed by a long right curve.

Scenario

In Frame A of Figure 81, the vehicle can be seen going straight at a speed of 100 km/h, which is suitable for this section. A warning sign indicating a tight curve ahead can be seen in Frame A. The snapshot shows that the vehicle was moving along the lane center, and the vehicle appeared to be able to handle the scenario as expected. In Frame B of Figure 81, the left curve ahead can be clearly seen. At this point in time, the vehicle was still traveling with the ACC and LKA system active at a speed of approximately 100 km/h. The lane guidance was directed slightly inwards at approximately 13%. This positioning was suitable for the course of the road and roughly corresponds to human behavior. In Frame C of Figure 81, after approximately 2.5 seconds, a strong deviation to the right can be seen. At this point, the vehicle was already 35% off the lane center; the right front tire overlapped with the white line and was also using the shoulder of the road. The vehicle continued to travel at around 100 km/h; the system did not reduce speed, but it deactivated the LKA function without any prior notification. In this scenario, the driver intervened very late. Immediately after the time frame presented in Frame B of Figure 81, the scenario was brought back to a safe state by manual correction.

Figure 81: Scenario 3 with context information and sequence details.

Analysis

Manual correction can be seen clearly in Figure 82. According to marker 1, the SSW angle has changed from the original steering wheel; consequently, the driver had begun steering the vehicle to the left at an early stage. This behavior is presented in marker 2 in the following moments. The movement continues until the limit to lock the SSW component has been reached. The exceeding of the limit value is visible in marker 3, which immediately activates the “Is Locked” signal. A short distance is shown in marker 4 as a result of an

increase in force. Due to this increase, a strong manual intervention to the left can be observed. The force then decreased again relatively quickly; the countermovement to correctly align the vehicle in the lane is indicated by marker 5.

Figure 82: Analysis of scenario 3 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.

In the further course of the road, there was a long right-hand bend immediately after the left bend. In the last quarter of Figure 82, it is clear that the driver is making a longer steering movement to the right. During this period, the SSW was still locked, which means that the driver's corrections were transferred directly to the original steering wheel. These measured values show that the driver continued to control the vehicle.

Summary

Scenario classification: **Critical**

In this example, a very critical scenario was identified on a federal road with a tight left-hand bend. The activated LKA system did not support the vehicle correctly in this scenario, as the driver had to intervene to avoid an accident. At the time of the intervention, the vehicle was traveling at 100 km/h with the ACC system active, which is clearly too high considering the tightness of the curve. Without manual intervention, the scenario could have resulted in a serious accident. On the one hand, the critical point is in a section where trees are present; on the other hand, there is a steep slope on the right-hand side, which can hardly be seen in the images shown. The combination of surroundings and excessive speed could have been fatal if the driver had remained inattentive.

6.1.5 Scenario 4

Backdrop

This scenario describes an identified problem in a construction zone. The problem likely occurred due to temporary lane markings that required the driver to take over the automated vehicle. Table 33 summarizes the most relevant metadata information about the identified scenario.

Table 33: Metadata of scenario 4.

Date and Time	2021-04-17T15:02:15 (UTC)								
Vehicle Speed	78 km/h								
Street Type	Highway								
Light Conditions	<p>Channel: RGB</p> <p>Source: Entire Image</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Mean: 133,68</td> <td>Level:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Std Dev: 62,68</td> <td>Count:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Median: 137</td> <td>Percentile:</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Pixels: 2073600</td> <td>Cache Level: 1</td> </tr> </table>	Mean: 133,68	Level:	Std Dev: 62,68	Count:	Median: 137	Percentile:	Pixels: 2073600	Cache Level: 1
Mean: 133,68	Level:								
Std Dev: 62,68	Count:								
Median: 137	Percentile:								
Pixels: 2073600	Cache Level: 1								
Weather Conditions	Partly cloudy								
Road Conditions	Try								
Road Lanes	Poor (overwritten lanes)								
Activated Vehicle Features and Configuration	<p>LKA</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Time of intervention = Late <p>ACC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Distance level: 3 Acceleration: Balanced 								

Location

The identified scenario occurred in a temporary construction area on a highway with three lanes. In Frame A of Figure 83, multiple crisscrossed lines on the road are visible. Due to the area being a construction site, the original lines were partially blurred, and the lane was adapted to the necessary construction site

guidance with orange lanes. At the time of data recording, the road was reduced to two lanes due to the presence of the construction site. This limitation is highlighted by the indicators on the left. One of the notable characteristics of these lines was that some of them directly led into restricted areas. The construction site operators removed these, but some were still visible.

Scenario

At the start of the scenario, the vehicle was on the highway A2 from Klagenfurt in the direction of Vienna. The vehicle was positioned slightly to the left, which was suitable for the time of travel. Frame A in Figure 83 shows that the white markings on the lane were temporarily replaced by orange lines. Due to the low speed at the time of the scenario, and the slow lateral movement of the automated vehicle, there was no danger for the driver or other road participants. A speed limit of 80 km/h was active in the construction site area at the time of the scenario. In Frame B of Figure 83, after approximately 5 seconds, an exit on the right side is visible. In this area, there were no white lanes, as they were replaced by orange lines because of the construction site. At the time of the snapshot, the vehicle had a slight deviation to the right, by approximately 18%, compared to the center. There was also a reduced lane width, which can be seen on the right, compared to the regular route. Frame C of Figure 83 shows the exit area with the partially removed restricted area. In addition, the active lane was well represented by the temporary orange lines. At this point in time, the vehicle had been taken over by the driver, as the vehicle had announced a TOR with a visual and acoustic signal because the LKA system was deactivated. In the current scenario, the complexity of the scenario was evident because of the many markings.

Figure 83: Scenario 4 with context information and sequence details.

Analysis

In this detailed analysis of the scenario (see Figure 84), marker 1 shows how the driver begins to steer to the left at around the 15th second, as the vehicle had drifted towards the right lane. The driver continues with the steering movement to the left until a stronger steering movement takes place, which is indicated by

marker 2. At this point, the vehicle is clearly in the right lane, as can be seen in Frame D of Figure 84. Due to the increased counter steering of the driver, the SSW component helped to bring the vehicle back to the correct lane. Due to the locking of the component in marker 3, the differential angle of the SSW is no longer changing. By the countermovement highlighted by marker 4, the vehicle was again correctly aligned to the original lane. It can be seen at marker 5 that the SSW component has been reset, and therefore the vehicle may continue to move independently.

Figure 84: Analysis of scenario 4 with data from the Shadow Steering Wheel.

The scenario described shows how a continuous deviation of the vehicle is compensated with a manual countermovement. A clear unwinding between the driver and the automated vehicle in the scenario is recognizable. This example does not represent a critical scenario since the vehicle speed in the construction zone was approximately 80 km/h, and no other road participants were present in the immediate vicinity.

Summary

Scenario classification: **Advisory**

The scenario described was not critical, as the vehicle informed the driver about the deactivation of the system at an early stage and the driver took over without delay. If the driver had not intervened immediately, the criticality of such a scenario could have been higher. With an active automation system, the vehicle must independently find and hold the correct position in the lane. As shown in Figure 84, the vehicle had already moved to the right-hand side with a deviation of 18% compared to the center. If this movement had continued, the journey could have resulted in a similar scenario observed in Scenario 2. If the vehicle had remained in the middle of the lane division, this could have led to a dangerous accident; consequently, navigating construction site areas can be a major challenge for vehicles with automated functions, as correct lane detection can often be difficult. This challenge is shown in Frame D of Figure 84 as the new carriageway line leads through the construction site over the original restricted area.

Chapter 7

Advancing Knowledge in Automated System Validation

The performance of automated systems is highly influenced by a lot of different factors. Under good road and weather conditions, as well as simple traffic scenarios, the performance is already impressive. This fact was observed during the test drives with the LKA system, and this reflects the results of Reddy et al. (2020). In more complex conditions, for instance in the absence of road markings, there are problems and human driver intervention is necessary. In Reddy's et al. (2020) work, critical problems on public roads were also identified during test drives; all of which were related to poor road markings or weather conditions. In those cases, the takeover of the automated vehicle at a critical event was performed directly by the driver. The intervention was documented manually by the co-driver, as there was no automatic data collection for the purpose. Reddy et al. recommended automating data collection in future research activities to obtain objective data. Through the developed SSW components in this research, this improvement is addressed, eliminating the need for a co-driver to record takeover data. In this research, it has been shown that the performance of LKA systems relies on the quality and complexity of the road markings. When the markings are easily recognizable and the curves are wide, the performance of the system is very good. But as soon as more complex scenarios occur, such as in a construction zone, there may be a safety risk in its use. In a study by Utriainen et al. (2020), the same finding is described.

In terms of the time required for the human driver to take over the vehicle, the findings of this research are similar to those found in Schinkel, Van Der Sande, and Nijmeijer's (2020) study. In case of problems, a fast reaction by the driver is necessary. In Schinkel, Van Der Sande and Nijmeijer, an average reaction time of 0.3 to 0.4 seconds were achieved. A similar result was obtained in the study by Huang (2020), where the average intervention time by the driver was about 0.5 seconds. The analyzed test drives with the SSW component have shown that a faster driver intervention (approximately 0.15 seconds) in the vehicle is possible. A very limited number of studies have examined the evaluation of production vehicles with automated functions on public roads in the literature to date. Most of the works use simulation environments or closed proving grounds with artificial scenarios. Due to the limited amount of information in this area, no direct comparison can be made to the results based on the SSW component.

7.1.2 Identified Safety-Relevant Gaps

By realizing the theoretical SS framework using the SSW component and performing drives on public roads, safety-critical scenarios were identified when using a production vehicle with automated functions. The first finding, which was gained on the basis of the recorded data and analyzed scenarios, shows the criticality in the event of a problem. A normal traffic scenario can lead to a safety-critical circumstance within seconds when using automated functions. Without immediate intervention by a human driver and appropriate de-escalation, such scenarios can have serious consequences for the driver and other road participants. The literature, based on a wide variety of papers, reports an average driver reaction time of 3 to 7 seconds (Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A., 2017). This delay can be far too long in critical scenarios, such as those identified in Scenario 3. As long as automated vehicles are not able to resolve critical traffic scenarios on their own, their use is associated with certain risks. Drivers must always keep their attention on the road and intervene immediately in the event of a problem; however, with more automation, the risk that drivers will gradually move into the background increases, thus reducing attention and reaction time. This combination is currently an unsolved problem and corresponds to the findings of Herrmann, Brenner and Stadler (2018). Particularly for vehicles with level 2 and 3 functions, where the driver is necessary as a fallback, a safe possibility for the handover is needed.

Secondly, the results highlighted the robustness of automated functions under different traffic conditions. In cases with clearly visible and continuous road markings, the LKA system performs well. But as soon as more complex road markings are encountered, the functionality is very limited or non-existent. This aspect limits the safe use of the system since on public roads, changes in road markings can occur at any time. A comparable result was reached by Utriainen et al. (2020), who analyzed the robustness and influencing factors of LKA systems on the basis of accident data. The results of this research show that currently approved vehicles with automated functions are not capable of solving all traffic scenarios independently and safely. Additionally, the results confirm the need for good de-escalation capabilities in an experienced human driver in case of a critical event. The takeover of the automated vehicle and safe correction of a traffic scenario can be done within fractions of a second; however, this requires appropriate attention from the driver. The analyzed scenarios have shown that, similar to the work of Schneider et al. (2015), a takeover by the driver is possible within 200-600 ms. This aspect supports the theory of the SS framework for the safe validation of vehicles on public roads, as a human can be used as an excellent benchmark.

Overall, the results clearly indicate that safety-relevant gaps exist even today due to the countless environmental conditions. These must be addressed in order to increase the level of automation in vehicles. In the long-term, this will enable systems to operate autonomously. Nevertheless, much more development work is needed to reach this point. The methodologies and framework presented in this research could be useful in future validations of vehicles.

7.1.3 Strengths and Weaknesses of the Shadow Concept

By independently comparing the behavior between human and automated systems, an assessment up to a safety-critical level is possible. It is advantageous to use this approach since the driver is always in the loop and, therefore, if a critical event occurs, the driver is able to intervene immediately, leading to a safe and fast de-escalation of the scenario. One of the strengths of the implemented SSW component is its universal applicability. Regardless of the manufacturer or model of the vehicle or the existing automation functions, installation is possible within minutes; furthermore, no access to the vehicle's system is required to collect data. Compared to traditional test methods on closed proving grounds, the approach of this research allows better scaling since no artificial scenarios have to be built. Additionally, testing is conducted on public roads, which eliminates issues caused by missing details or simplified scenarios.

One of the weaknesses of the chosen approach is the dependence on the behavior and experience of a human driver, who is used as a benchmark. Hence, the results of drives may differ due to the personal feelings and behavior of the individual person. This fact also affects the safe execution of rides and de-escalation capabilities of critical scenarios. Another drawback in this context is driver attention, since similar to current testing approaches, the decision of the driver is responsible for the outcome. Another conceptual weakness of the SS framework is the requirement of control units in the vehicle, such as the steering wheel or pedals. In future vehicles with higher levels of automation (levels 4 and 5), the control units may no longer be necessary, and this would mean that this framework could not be implementable. In terms of the scalability of tests, the approach is significantly limited compared to simulation methods since real vehicles and human drivers are needed. Due to the fact that test drives are conducted on public roads, it is not possible to replicate traffic scenarios exactly. With the SS framework, problems on public roads can be identified using a simple and safe method, but the approach does not guarantee that all problems will be identified in an automated system. Due to the theoretically infinite number of scenarios, a certain residual risk always remains open, since only a fraction of possible variants can be validated on the basis of real drives.

The strengths of the developed framework provide advantages over current scenario-based validation methods on closed proving grounds, which may make the approach an alternative or complement in the future. In terms of scaling and repeatability of scenarios, the framework has weaknesses that need to be addressed for long-term, sustainable and efficient use.

7.1.4 Positioning of the Shadow Concept in the ADAS/AD Code of Practice

As mentioned in Section 2.6, there are already a number of standards that deal extensively with the topic of safety and acceptance of automated vehicles. In the next few years, the existing standards and regulations for AV for approval, use, and operation will be refined and extended, as there are still gaps in many areas today. Nevertheless, risk assessment models based on various standards, such as RAPEX, ALARP, and ISO 26262, are already available. Figure 85 shows a risk assessment model to define a code of practice for ADAS/AD systems. This and many other standards that are currently being developed in various working

groups should contribute to making the use of automated vehicles safer in the future. The definition of uniform standards is intended to address in particular non-tolerable and non-acceptable risks, which correspond to the yellow and red areas in Figure 85. The focus of this risk assessment model is on problems with a high probability of occurrence and those causing such effects on humans that cannot be reversed and must be avoided as far as possible.

	Injury severity (S1-3)			Level of risk	Vulnerable humans		Healthy adults				
	AIS 0-2 e.g. S 0-1	AIS 3-4 e.g. S 2	AIS 5-6 e.g. S 3		Injury irreversible	Injury partially reversible	No	Yes	No	Yes	Protect: e.g. warning Hazard: continuously
	Yes	Yes	No		Yes	No	Yes	No			
Probability of harm (E1-7)	Often	Probable	Disastrous	Risk not acceptable: Measures required immediately!							Protect: e.g. warning
	Often	Probable	Serious								Hazard: continuously
	Probable	Ocasio-nally	High	(Consideration of Safety levels - ASIL)							
	Ocasio-nally	Rare	Medium	Risk not tolerable Measures required (QM)							
	Rare	Very rare	Low	Risk socially and individually accepted Quality management (QM) and monitoring recommended							
	Very rare		Tolerable								
	Unlikely		Insignificant								

Figure 85: Illustration of the code of practice for ADAS/AD (Maurer, M., Gerdes, C. and Lenz, B., 2016).

A new way for the validation of automated vehicles on public roads was presented in this research using the SS framework. With this concept, certification organizations or manufacturers could perform the final validation to obtain objective proof of safety. Additionally, the ELOS concept could be applied as the basis for a comparable assessment. In order for an automated system to be safe, it must travel at least as far as a human driver before experiencing any problems. To this aim, legislation could be established to require public road testing with the SS framework over a certain distance under various road, traffic, and weather conditions. If no critical events occur during these validation drives, this could be a criterion for approval. This would also justify the use of the systems as an advantage over humans. In the long-term, it would be possible, with appropriate developments, to use this idea on a larger scale in production vehicles. It would be easier to recognize when drivers need to intervene if this were implemented; furthermore, it would also be possible to derive scenarios that represent a dangerous or uncomfortable scenario for the driver.

The safe operation of automated vehicles must be ensured by establishing efficient and sustainable international standards and test methods. This requires close cooperation between the various stakeholders, such as manufacturers, certification organizations and legislators in the coming years. The common goal of all parties must be the protection of vehicle passengers and other road participants in order to avoid accidents in the best possible way and thus to further advance the establishment of the systems.

7.1.5 Use of the System on Public Roads

The use of automated functions in vehicles offers many advantages for the driver and can have a positive contribution to increasing road safety and driving comfort; however, current systems require the driver to monitor a journey and intervene when a system is unable to handle a scenario. This fact currently limits the

benefits of the systems and partly causes problems in reality as the driver's trust in the systems increases, reducing attention and responsiveness. This can lead to serious consequences when a critical scenario arises, as a driver is no longer able to handle the scenario in time.

The identified scenarios have shown circumstances where serious consequences of using automated functions could have occurred without the intervention of a human driver. The vehicle used was a production vehicle, which can be found today in large numbers in many different countries. If the driver's attention is reduced while using the existing automated functions, such as ACC and LKA, this can lead to a serious problem within seconds in a critical scenario. The scenario presented in Section 6.1.4, and its associated potential hazards, prove the importance of safety in the field of automated vehicles. The relatively short distance of around 650 km covered by the test drives is purely a sample and does not allow any overall conclusions to be drawn about the performance of the vehicle. More extensive distances must be covered for the validation of new development statuses of an automated system (hardware or software or a combination of both), even to complete the validation of the homologation process. In addition, different environmental conditions (e.g., rain, snow, driving at night) and regions (e.g., rural roads, city) must be included in these tests. Even the short test distance included in the scope of this research has demonstrated that critical issues are present in the field under good environmental conditions (i.e., daylight, good visibility, sun, and dry road). The scenarios described constituting normal indicators of the maturity of the system used, as several problems could be identified on public roads. The results also highlight that currently approved systems, which have been accepted today by certification companies, contain gaps in their functionality in certain circumstances.

Due to the complexity of the topic and the associated consequences for the driver and their environment, safety must be put first. Further, manufacturers of automated systems must clarify what capabilities their systems can offer to the mass market in order to prevent false expectations. On the other hand, the driver of the systems must perform the application responsibly, taking into account the operating conditions. It is necessary to prevent scenarios such as those shown in Figure 3 in order to ensure the best possible level of protection for all road users. Further, legislators and manufacturers must define uniform standards in the coming years to ensure safe operation and correct use. In addition, new methods must be established by certification companies to validate the initial homologation process in the best possible way and to carry out continuous validation in the field.

7.2 System Reliance and Reliability

Significantly more critical events than expected occurred during test drives on public roads. Since the vehicle tested was a production vehicle and the test drives were carried out in good weather and lighting conditions and on simple roads, it was expected that intervention would only be necessary after several 10,000 km. Instead, the tests showed that a takeover by the driver was on average every 150 km necessary to avoid a critical traffic scenario. Based on these results, the automated functions are significantly less safe than those based on human performance.

The abrupt deactivation of the LKA function without appropriate TOR was observed. This can be explained by considering Scenario 3 where the vehicle was following the speed limit of 100 km/h not considering the road characteristics. The warning sign stating “Sharp Curves” ahead was not considered by the ACC system. The sharp curve in combination with the high speed could not be completed automatically by the system, which is why the vehicle had to be taken over by the human driver. Due to high speed, an uncritical scenario became very dangerous and would have led to a serious accident without the immediate intervention of the driver. In this case, the short TORT for the intervention and the development of a scenario showed how the criticality could change from a standard scenario into a dangerous one within seconds. For distracted or careless drivers, such scenarios could be safety-critical. The need for rapid intervention was identified by the tests, in particular Scenario 2, where without the driver taking over immediately, it would have led to serious consequences.

One challenge that has emerged from the analysis of the scenarios concerns the timely and short-term takeover by the driver when a critical scenario occurs. In some cases, this activity must be performed within seconds in order to take control, especially at higher speeds, to steer the vehicle into a safe operating state. In this context, Scenario 3 also showed that handover to the driver after a TOR is a challenge. In this scenario, the LKA was automatically deactivated without a corresponding TOR notification to the driver. There was also no waiting by the system until the handover was performed. The combination of high speed, sharp curves, and automatic deactivation of an automated function pose a significant safety risk. Another challenge in the use of automated functions is seen in narrow areas. Figure 86 shows an overtaking maneuver of a truck in a construction zone with reduced lane width. In this non-critical scenario, the normal lane lines were replaced by temporary orange markings. Due to the small distances to the left boundary and to the truck, the driver had to take over and execute the control. In the vehicle used, the required precision and reliability could not be observed during the test drives, which is why the control of the vehicle was already taken over by the driver in advance. As shown in the previous section, the LKA function often changes status from active to inactive and vice versa in construction site areas.

Figure 86: Video still of a challenging traffic scenario with a truck overtaking a construction area.

7.3 Identification of Critical Aspects

Specifically, on the basis of Scenario 3, concerns the safe handover of the vehicle to the driver. If an automated system is unable to handle a scenario, a better mechanism must be provided to ensure that the human driver is informed as quickly as possible of any necessary takeover; furthermore, the system should not deactivate until the human driver has taken control. Otherwise, scenarios like Scenario 3 may occur, where the LKA function is automatically deactivated, causing the vehicle to drive straight ahead from that point on. In a tight curve with high speeds, this combination is fatal. Based on the findings, the influence of high speeds and tight curves on the vehicle is another emerging theme that has been identified in this research and needs to be considered in more detail.

The number of identified problems on short distances and simple environment conditions, which were carried out during the test drives, presents as a critical aspect. Extensive test drives with several 100,000 km should be carried out to address this issue. In this research, test drives were conducted in daylight and good weather conditions with clear visibility conditions. The system should also be tested in bad weather scenarios such as rain or snow. In addition, different lighting conditions, for example, those during sunset, night or in fog, must also be tested. In addition, data collection in various extended regions is important to validate the behavior of the vehicle in extended ODD.

Due to the fact that some problems were identified with the vehicle used, there is also a need to conduct further tests with other vehicles from different manufacturers. In addition, the settings of the automated functions should be changed in order to identify potential deviations in behavior. Another aspect that should be considered when conducting future tests concerns the left- and right-hand traffic. In most regions of the world, right-hand traffic is in place; however, there are countries like the UK, the Republic of Ireland, Malta, Cyprus, India, Japan, Australia, and others, where left-driving is defined by the law.

Chapter 8

Impact of the Shadow Framework and Concept on Safety Assessment

8.1 Integrating Human Behavior into the Homologation Process

As a result of the findings of this research, new validation and approval methods are necessary in order to fill the gaps in the current validation and approval methods. Based on the recorded data, it has been demonstrated that automated systems in an approved production vehicle are not capable of independently handling certain traffic scenarios. This fact can lead to safety-related problems with serious consequences, and this confirms a gap in the literature. Today's automated systems are limited in functionality under certain conditions and may pose a risk to the driver and other road participants. Using the SSW component developed and the test drives conducted, a new method was proposed to allow validation on public roads. The test drives showed that the approach could be applied quickly and easily, regardless of the underlying vehicle. The generic approach and ease of installation allow more tests to be performed within a shorter time compared to scenario-based testing on proving grounds, allowing for better scaling. This advantage addresses another gap identified in the literature review of current methodologies. In addition, it was shown that safe application on public roads is possible and a driver can take control of the vehicle within a fraction of a second. In this context, human drivers as a benchmark for safely performing a drive proves to be a promising approach. Some of the currently established test methods are based on predefined scenarios, which are re-enacted on proving grounds. This approach is time-consuming and involves high costs. Moreover, it only covers a certain number of known scenarios. By means of the test drives on public roads, critical scenarios were identified, which were obviously not considered during the approval of the vehicle. Another gap, which was identified in the course of this research, concerns the assessment of the driver's well-being. Using the SS framework, up to a certain safety-critical level, the behavior of the vehicle compared to the human driver can be observed and recorded to measure the level of comfort in a scenario. As minor corrections of the driver have no direct influence on the automated vehicle or vice versa, this allows for an objective assessment of the performance.

Validation of automated vehicles on public roads, taking into account human behavior, seems to be a promising complement to existing methods to support development and homologation in the future. The current homologation process for a passenger car does not consider the connection between longitudinal and lateral dynamics. Figure 87 shows some of the packages that are validated during the homologation process. Using the SS framework, an additional package could be integrated into the homologation process to perform a check based on the behavioral difference between humans and automated systems. Homologation should only be granted if a vehicle behaves similarly to a human, according to the ELOS concept.

Figure 87: Illustration of an extended homologation for passenger cars by the Shadow System framework.

8.2 Delivering an Enhanced Validation Approach

The findings of this research give a new understanding that has implications for the discipline. The identification of problems in a production vehicle with automated functions that are approved for public road traffic reveals the need for better validation. This finding has an impact on certification organizations, as better methods need to be established as part of the homologation process. Safety-critical issues need to be identified and assessed as early as possible to avoid serious problems on public roads. In a similar way, this also affects the manufacturers of the systems, as current validation methods obviously have gaps and thus the developed systems pose a potential risk.

Another implication of the research concerns the communication of functional limitations to end consumers. In the manual of the vehicle used, no information is given about the limitations and hazards of using the automated functions. Increasing levels of automation in vehicles and a vehicle's ability to take on a passive role will likely increase the risk of accidents in the future. These circumstances make a more robust development of the functions and better safeguarding of the systems necessary.

The validation of automated vehicles is an extensive and complex topic and one that still has many gaps and requires further research and development activities. Current methods in the automotive industry are not completely adequate in the validation of automated vehicles. On the one hand, the complexity of the systems is increasing due to the development of new hardware and software technologies. On the other hand, validation involves immense challenges since a check must consider a theoretically infinite number of scenarios. In reality, however, this is not possible due to time and budget constraints. For this reason, simulation technologies are increasingly used in development today to achieve theoretically unlimited

scaling of tests and repeatability of scenarios during validation. Since a simulation is an abstraction of reality, complete validation cannot be achieved through this method. This limitation implies that today's systems must also be tested on public roads. The safety and robustness of automated systems is the most important aspect to gain acceptance by consumers and legislators in the future. Only if the systems reach an acceptable level of safety, a wide-spread distribution will take place. Automobile manufacturers, development companies and legislators must develop and continuously apply new methods to ensure the best possible system safety. For this reason, it is essential that system manufacturers and certification organizations continue to develop validation methods in order to offer solutions providing better assurance that are executable in a scalable and cost-effective manner. Otherwise, without proper validation and robustness of the vehicles, accidents related to new generations of vehicles could increase.

8.3 Performance Assessment and Framework Validation

The results of this research show an alternative to scenario-based testing on closed proving grounds to objectively assess the performance of automated vehicles in the homologation process. Through the developed SS framework, a new standardized approach based on the detection of behavioral differences between a human driver and an automated system was established to perform validations on public roads. The results of the test drives have shown that detection of critical and uncomfortable scenarios is possible with the approach. By continuously including a qualified driver as a benchmark, larger distances and thus more scenarios can be covered in a shorter time and with less effort. This allows for a better assessment of the safety, reliability and robustness of an automated system. The measurement results were used to demonstrate how a takeover of a critical scenario by a human driver can occur within milliseconds. This safety mechanism makes an application on public roads possible; furthermore, the developed measuring device for the independent detection of steering movements up to a defined safety level is a further improvement. Due to the generic design of the SSW component, an application in vehicles of different manufacturers and models is possible.

Many problems may be identified and resolved using today's validation methods, such as simulation technology and safeguards on proving grounds. Still, there are gaps and weaknesses in current approaches for which no solution exists to date. Due to increasing complexity, advancing automation, and fast actuation of systems, new challenges will continue to arise. Until fully automated vehicles are operating on roads in different regions of the world, the automotive industry, as well as all the involved development companies and legislators, will have to pay special attention to safeguarding. Through the results of this research, a new alternative to existing test methods solves some known limitations of current approaches and thereby achieves better test coverage. Due to the complexity of the topic, there is currently no single solution that can be used for all challenges. For this reason, the result of this research is a supplement or extension to existing approaches in order to have an objective decision basis for the assessment of safety in a standardized form, especially in the context of the homologation of a system.

Conclusions

Demonstrating Testing of Automated Vehicles on Public Roads

Automated vehicles can be tested on public roads in a safe way as part of the homologation process. The developed SS framework provides a new way to obtain an objective assessment of the performance of a vehicle based on a human driver. By continuously comparing the behavior of the human driver and the automated system, critical events can be automatically identified and corrected by the driver. Due to the standardized approach and the simple installation of a measurement device, an application on different makes and models of vehicles is possible. This allows independent use in the homologation process. In addition, no integration into the vehicle system is required, which means that the behavior of the vehicle is not affected and no additional safety risks arise from external interference. Due to the validation on public roads without consideration of predefined scenarios, larger distances with more scenarios can be tested. This fact allows a better statement about the robustness and safety of the automated system.

Effectively Assessing Automated Vehicles and Drivers' Comfort Zones as Part of the Homologation Process

An objective assessment of safety and well-being when using an automated system can be achieved by classifying behavioral differences into three zones. Minor deviations between humans and the system are classified in the first zone and represent normal behavior. The second zone represents larger deviations in which the driver would act differently from the vehicle. This type of deviation does not represent a safety risk but has an impact on the driver's well-being. In the third zone, large deviations are classified, which represent a safety risk and lead to an automatic takeover of the vehicle by the driver. In the future, the number of deviations in zones two and three could be used for the assessment and associated approval as part of the homologation process.

The hypothesis of this research can be confirmed by the test drives conducted and the scenarios described. By comparing human behavior with an automated system, critical scenarios can be identified, and consequences can be derived. Harmless traffic scenarios can lead to hazardous scenarios within seconds without active monitoring and intervention by a human driver. The method to detect the difference between the performance of a human and a machine can be used to identify safety-critical and problematic scenarios on public roads. With the help of the developed SSW component and associated SA software, the difference at the steering wheel can be measured and visualized in real-time. In addition, the SSW component also offers safety-related functions to automatically transfer the driver's action to the vehicle once a defined limit is reached. The limits for assigning the behavioral differences to the individual zones for evaluating a scenario can be set dynamically based on the vehicle speed, enabling scenario-dependent adaptation. The so-called "warning" zone can be used to determine the comfort and confidence factor of the human driver in the automated system.

Addressed Aims and Objectives

The first aim of this research was addressed by developing an alternative approach to the classical scenario-based testing of automated vehicles on closed proving grounds. To perform tests on public roads, an approach was developed based on a holistic validation framework that compares the behavior of a human driver with that of an automated vehicle. For safety-first assurance, a method was developed in which a test driver is kept in the loop at all times and can intervene within milliseconds in case of a critical event. To measure the differences in behavior, a device was developed, which is installed in the vehicle and records the movements of the human and vehicle independently of each other up to a safety-critical level. The driver only intervenes if a dynamic threshold value, which depends on the speed of the vehicle, is exceeded. In this way, critical traffic scenarios can be taken over and resolved by an expert.

For the achievement of the second aim, test drives were conducted using a production vehicle with automated functions on public roads using the developed framework and test method to identify safety-critical and uncomfortable driving scenarios. Through a series of standardized test drives, several scenarios were identified that could have led to serious consequences if the driver had not intervened. According to this research, vehicles approved for use on public roads require the immediate intervention of a human driver under certain circumstances.

Significance and Implications of Findings

The most significant result of this research is the safety-critical scenarios identified when using a production vehicle with automated functions on public roads. A relatively short test distance of only 650 km was used to record the scenarios, and these results are the first indication of the system's performance and capability. Without the intervention of a human driver, certain scenarios could have led to serious consequences for the driver and other road participants. The test drives were used to demonstrate that validation of automated vehicles can be performed in a safe manner on public roads. By comparing behavioral differences between a human driver and an automated system, an objective evaluation of a system's performance is possible. The independent consideration of human behavior in comparison to the vehicle without mutual influence up to a certain point in time represents a new and reliable validation alternative for automated vehicles. In certain scenarios, it has been shown that driver takeover must occur within seconds to perform de-escalation actions and avoid serious consequences.

The implication of the results based on the identified problems showed that although the current homologation process systems have been approved, there are certain conditions limited in functionality that pose a safety risk. Good robustness and associated safety of the automated functions of the tested vehicle were observed under good road conditions; nevertheless, significant gaps were revealed in more complex scenarios, which required the driver to take over. By means of the test drives, it was demonstrated how the criticality of a traffic scenario could change from a normal to a dangerous scenario within a few seconds. A human driver with appropriate experience is a good benchmark to evaluate the performance of an automated vehicle continuously during a drive, as systems must have at least the same level of safety to be

accepted. There are currently gaps in the validation of automated systems, which need to be better addressed by system manufacturers and certification organizations to enable the successful introduction of these systems into public roads. More testing on public roads under a wide range of traffic conditions is needed to provide a complete picture of a system's performance.

Contributions

Holistic Validation Framework

We now have an addition to the current state of knowledge by a novel approach for safe and objective validation of automated vehicles on public roads based on continuous assessment by a human driver. Using the holistic framework, a validation of an automated system on public roads was possible by detecting behavioral differences between a human driver and an automated system.

Generic and Scalable Solution

Due to the generic and scalable solution, better test coverage can be achieved in less time and effort compared to scenario-based approaches on closed proving grounds; furthermore, the informative value about the performance was higher since the validation was performed on public roads.

New Measurement Device

The design and implementation of a new measurement device for the independent recording of behavioral differences in steering movements with integrated safety mechanisms for use on public roads were achieved. By recording the steering movements of the driver and the automated vehicle, it was possible to identify safety-critical and uncomfortable traffic scenarios.

Identification of Safety-Critical Events

The identification of safety-critical events in a production vehicle based on test drives conducted on public roads was achieved using the developed framework. Based on the results of this research, automated functions do not appear to be safe, reliable and robust in more complex traffic scenarios. Additionally, the criticality of the identified scenarios, as well as their potential consequences, was highlighted.

Overall, the results of this research demonstrate that there is a need for improvement in the homologation process on the part of certification organizations and system manufacturers. Moreover, the research demonstrated the necessity of continuous monitoring by the driver in order to take immediate action in the event of a problem.

Recommendations for Future Research

The validation of automated vehicles is a comprehensive topic with many unsolved problems due to the safety aspects and complexity. In the following, individual limitations arising during the development and the test results are presented; furthermore, research questions are defined to answer in further research activities in order to achieve an improvement of the developed framework. The complete and continuous validation of automated systems by system manufacturers and certification organizations is an unsolved problem to date and thus offers enormous potential for future research activities.

Shadow System Framework

The developed SS framework for the holistic validation of the performance of an automated system includes a number of different components to capture all behavioral differences. In addition, the framework provides other components to capture the context of a drive with detail. In this research, one component for measuring behavioral differences at the steering wheel was developed and tested to validate the fundamental idea of the framework. In further research activities, the remaining components should be developed that the SS framework envisages. This should clarify whether it is possible to perform an overall validation of an automated vehicle in a safe and scalable way based on the detection of behavioral differences.

Extended Test Drives

Another limitation of this research is the short test distance since the focus was on the development of the SS framework and the validation of the concept. The test drives on public roads covered about 650 km. This distance is not sufficient for a meaningful performance assessment. In addition, the tests were conducted only during good weather conditions in the daytime. Through further research activities, additional factors should be taken into account during validation in the context of extensive test drives in order to obtain a better statement regarding the performance of an automated vehicle. These factors include the use of different vehicles and configurations; regional differences in different traffic regulations; including difficult environmental conditions such as snow and rain, as well as different lighting conditions (day vs. night, street vs. countryside, etc.). Additionally, other factors to test would be considering varying degrees of human drivers' experience and capacity, as well as different driver profiles (i.e., conservative, nervous, anxious, relaxed, average, aggressive). In order to evaluate performance as part of the homologation process using the SS framework, additional test drives may provide insight into the distance to be covered on public roads, taking various environmental conditions into account.

Vehicle Position and Environment

The determination of the vehicle position in the lane was performed in this research by means of relative classifications based on the recorded video. Quantitative measurement cannot be made with this type of determination due to its limited accuracy. In the analysis of the critical scenarios, this missing information led to limitations because no objective statement about the influence of the positioning or the distance to other objects was possible. The exact determination of the vehicle position and orientation/header plays an important role in the post-data analysis process since the deviation from the ideal line (trajectory in 4D) would be known and could be compared with the behavior of a human driver. Further research activities should address this current limitation and would be able to provide an answer to determine the exact position of a vehicle in the lane independently, and the distance to surrounding vehicles or objects, taking into account complex environmental conditions such as rain, snow and low light conditions.

Trigger of an Event

The realized SSW component for the detection of behavioral differences at the steering wheel has a limitation in its realized form. There is no function integrated into the component that detects the trigger for a critical event. Exceeding the safety limit can be triggered by a driver's correction or by a fast and unexpected steering movement by the automated system. The origin of the trigger should be identified and collected in further research activities in order to consider this information in the analysis of critical scenarios. This would answer whether a critical event was actively triggered by the intervention of a human driver or a movement of the automated vehicle that led to the safety limit being exceeded.

Takeover Signals

Automated systems with functions at SAE levels 1 to 3 require a human driver to intervene and take control in the event of a problem. A necessary handover is communicated to the driver by visual and acoustic signals. This data was not collected in this research and is a limitation that should be considered in the future. The additional data would be relevant for the overall assessment of individual functions, as it would assess the activity or inactivity of different automated systems. In addition, the SS framework could be used to determine how long it took for the driver to take over. Further research based on the findings of this research should address how to collect the signals in the event of a handover of control of an automated vehicle to the driver; this could be used to evaluate the availability of individual functions using the SS framework.

Differences in Human Behavior

The individual behavior of a driver, which is influenced by various factors such as experience and personal driving style, was not considered within the scope of this research. This is a limitation since the identification of critical events and uncomfortable scenarios is influenced by the uniform use of limit values. In further research, behavioral factors of human drivers should be identified and considered in the use of the SS framework. In this context, further research may indicate how the personal behavior factors of human

drivers can be identified and harmonized in the validation of an automated system to allow comparability between identified scenarios across different drivers.

References

- 42HOW (2021) The REAL L4 Autonomous Driving brought by Chinese tech giant Huawei, demonstrated in Shanghai. [Online]. Available: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8BoE21o8rfw&ab_channel=42%E5%8F%B7%E8%BD%A6%E5%BA%93 [Accessed 14 Aug 2021].
- AG, A. (2018) Audi A5 2018 - Owner's Manual.
- Akamatsu, M. (2019) Handbook of Automotive Human Factors. Handbook of Automotive Human Factors.
- Alawadhi, M., Almazrouie, J., Kamil, M. and Khalil, K. A. (2020) Review and analysis of the importance of autonomous vehicles liability: a systematic literature review. International Journal of Systems Assurance Engineering and Management.
- Al-Nuaimi, M., Qu, H. and Veres, S. M. (2018) Towards a verifiable decision making framework for self-driving vehicles. [Online]. Available: <http://t-news.cn/Floc2018/FLoC2018-pages/paper2701.html> [Accessed 12 Mar 2021].
- American Automobile Association, Inc. (2020) Evaluating Active Driving Assistance Systems [Online]. Available: <file:///C:/Users/manue/Downloads/E.1.-Research-Report-Evaluating-ADA-FINAL-7-13-20.pdf> [Accessed 6 Nov 2020].
- Arend, R. J. (2020) Strategic decision-making under ambiguity: a new problem space and a proposed optimization approach. Business Research.
- Badue, C., Guidolini, R., Carneiro, R. V., Azevedo, P., Cardoso, V. B., Forechi, A., Jesus, L., Berriel, R., Paixão, T., Mutz, F., Veronese, L., Oliveira-Santos, T. and de Souza, A. F. (2019) Self-Driving Cars: A Survey. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1901.04407>.
- Bagloee, S. A., Tavana, M., Asadi, M. and Oliver, T. (2016) Autonomous vehicles: challenges, opportunities, and future implications for transportation policies. Journal of Modern Transportation.
- Ballingall, S., Sarvi, M. and Sweatman, P. (2020) Safety Assurance Concepts for Automated Driving Systems. SAE Technical Papers.
- Bertram, T. (2019) Automatisiertes Fahren 2019.
- Bhaskaran, B. (2022) The Importance of Homologation in an Evolving US Automotive Market [Online]. Available: <https://www.tuvsud.com/en/-/media/global/pdf-files/whitepaper-report-e-books/tuvsud-vehicle-homologation-us-market.pdf> [Accessed 7 Dec 2022].
- Bizon, N., Dascalescu, L. and Tabatabaei, N. M. (2014) Autonomous Vehicles: Intelligent Transport Systems and Smart Technologies.
- Boulanger Jean-Louis (2015) CENELEC 50128 and IEC 62279 Standards.
- Bradley, C. and Preston, V. (2020) A self driving license : Ensuring autonomous vehicles deliver on the promise of safer roads.
- Bradley, R. (2017) Decision Theory with a Human Face.
- Bundy, A. (2019) Criminal Law [Online]. The Oklahoma Bar Journal. Available: <https://www.okbar.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/OBJ2019March.pdf> [Accessed 2 Dec 2020].
- Tiulkin, B. and Kulabukhova, N. (2018) Convolutional Neural Networks for Self-Driving Cars on GPU.
- Cavoli, C., Phillips, B., Cohen, T. and Jones, P. (2017) Social and Behavioural Questions Associated with Automated Vehicles: A Literature Review [Online]. Available: <https://www.ucl.ac.uk/transport/sites/transport/files/social-and-behavioural-literature-review.pdf> [Accessed 6 Nov 2022].
- Chen, Y., Palanisamy, P., Mudalige, P., Muelling, K. and Dolan, J. M. (2018) Learning On-Road Visual Control for Self-Driving Vehicles with Auxiliary Tasks. In: [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1812.07760.pdf>.
- Chikaraishi, M., Khan, D., Yasuda, B. and Fujiwara, A. (2020) Risk perception and social acceptability of autonomous vehicles: A case study in Hiroshima, Japan. Transport Policy.
- Chmielewski, C. (2019) Self-Driving Cars and Rural Areas: The Potential for a Symbiotic Relationship. Journal of Law and Commerce.
- Cleij, D. (2021) European Road Safety Observatory - Road Safety Thematic Report [Online]. Available: https://road-safety.transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-04/Road_Safety_Thematic_Report_ADAS_2021.pdf [Accessed 14 Dec 2021].
- Coelingh, E. and Nilsson, J. (2018) Driving tests for self-driving cars. IEEE Spectrum.

- Concas, F., Nurminen, J. K., Mikkonen, T. and Tarkoma, S. (2020) Validation Frameworks for Self-Driving Vehicles: A Survey. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/2007.11347>.
- Cook, D. J. and Krishnan, N. C. (2015) Activity learning: Discovering, recognizing, and predicting human behavior from sensor data.
- Coppola, P. and Esztergár-Kiss, D. (2019) Autonomous vehicles and future mobility solutions. Autonomous Vehicles and Future Mobility.
- DaSilva, S. (2023) Human Drivers Avoid Crashes 99.999819% of the Time, Self-Driving Cars Need to Be Even Safer [Online]. Available: <https://jalopnik.com/self-driving-car-vs-human-99-percent-safe-crash-data-1850170268> [Accessed 10 Mar 2023].
- David, J. (2019) Machine Learning vs Traditional Programming [Online]. Available: <https://morioh.com/p/1063d43ef15e> [Accessed 3 Aug 2020].
- Denton, T. (2020) Automated Driving and Driver Assistance Systems. Automated Driving and Driver Assistance Systems.
- Deruyttere, T., Vandenhende, S., Grujicic, D., van Gool, L. and Moens, M.-F. (2019) Talk2Car: Taking Control of Your Self-Driving Car.
- Deshpande, A. and Kumar, M. (2018) Artificial Intelligence for Big Data: Complete guide to automating Big Data solutions using Artificial Intelligence techniques.
- desmos.com (2020) Sigmoid Function [Online]. Available: <https://www.desmos.com/calculator/vaekei4ewp> [Accessed 9 Feb 2020].
- Dow, J. (2019) Tesla updates Autopilot safety numbers; almost 9x safer than average driving [Online]. Available: <https://electrek.co/2019/10/23/tesla-autopilot-safety-9x-safer-than-average-driving/> [Accessed 4 Jan 2020].
- Eliot, L. (2018a) Top Trends in AI Self-Driving Cars: Practical Advances in AI and Machine Learning.
- Eliot, L. (2018b) AI Self-Driving Cars Breakthroughs: Practical Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.
- Eliot, L. (2018c) Introduction to Driverless Self-Driving Cars: The Best of the AI Insider.
- Eliot, L. (2018d) Revolutionary Innovations of AI Self-Driving Cars: Practical Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.
- Eliot, L. (2019a) AI Self-Driving Cars Prognosis: Practical Advances In Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.
- Eliot, L. (2019b) AI Self-Driving Cars Evolvement: Practical Advances in Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning.
- Engholm, A., Pernestål, A. and Kristoffersson, I. (2017) System-level impacts of self-driving vehicles: terminology, impact frameworks and existing literature syntheses.
- Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A. (2017) Takeover Time in Highly Automated Vehicles: Noncritical Transitions to and from Manual Control. Human Factors.
- Eriksson, A. and Stanton, N. A. (2018) Driver Reactions to Automated Vehicles.
- Favarò, F., Eurich, S. and Nader, N. (2017) Autonomous vehicles' disengagements: Trends, triggers, and regulatory limitations. Accident Analysis and Prevention.
- Feth, P., Adler, R., Fukuda, T., Ishigooka, T., Otsuka, S., Schneider, D., Uecker, D. and Yoshimura, K. (2018) Multi-aspect Safety Engineering for Highly Automated Driving. In: .
- Fischhoff, B. (2012) Risk Analysis and Human Behavior.
- Forster, Y., Hergeth, S., Naujoks, F., Krems, J. F. and Keinath, A. (2019) Self-report measures for the assessment of human-machine interfaces in automated driving. Cognition, Technology and Work.
- Getahun, T., Karimodini, A., Beni, L. H. and Mudalige, P. (2018) A Robust Lane Marking Extraction Algorithm for Self-driving Vehicles. In: .
- Giang, P. H. (2014) Decision making under ignorance. In: .
- Greene, T. (2021) Why the dream of truly driverless cars is slowly dying [Online]. Available: <https://thenextweb.com/news/why-truly-driverless-cars-may-never-happen> [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].
- Grimes, R. A. (2019) Cryptography Apocalypse: Preparing for the Day When Quantum Computing Breaks Today's Crypto.
- Gupta, N., Prakash, A. and Tripathi, R. (2011) Internet of Vehicles and its Applications in Autonomous Driving. Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical.
- Hamilton, R. (2016) How You Decide: The Science of Human Decision Making.
- Hanna, P. (2020) On Global Journeys & Markets (pre-Covid) [Online]. Available: [https://movotiv.com/statistics#:~:text=Every%20day%2C%20there%20are%20some,\(M\)%20worldwide%20driving%20trips](https://movotiv.com/statistics#:~:text=Every%20day%2C%20there%20are%20some,(M)%20worldwide%20driving%20trips). [Accessed 17 Apr 2021].

- Hennessy, B. (2019) An Introduction to J1939 and DBC files [Online]. Available: <https://www.kvaser.com/developer-blog/an-introduction-j1939-and-dbc-files/> [Accessed 17 Aug 2020].
- Herrmann, A., Brenner, W. and Stadler, R. (2018) Autonomous Driving: How the Driverless Revolution will Change the World.
- Huang, C., Li, L., Liu, Y. and Xiao, L. (2020) Robust Observer Based Intermittent Forces Estimation for Driver Intervention Identification.
- Inga, J., Flad, M. and Hohmann, S. (2019) Validation of a human cooperative steering behavior model based on differential games. Conference Proceedings - IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man and Cybernetics.
- International Air Transport Association (2015) Safety Report 2014.
- International Transport Forum (2015) Automated and Autonomous Driving: Regulation under Uncertainty.
- Isabel, M., Ferreira, A., Silva, J., Gurvinder, S. and Virk, S. (2019) Robotics and Well-Being.
- Isermann, R. (2017) Fahrerassistenzsysteme 2017: Von der Assistenz zum automatisierten Fahren.
- Jahan, F., Sun, W., Niyaz, Q. and Alam, M. (2019) Security modeling of autonomous systems: A survey. ACM Computing Surveys.
- Jha, A. R. (2017) Theory, Design, and Applications of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles.
- Jurgen, R. K. (2013) Autonomous Vehicles for Safer Driving. Autonomous Vehicles for Safer Driving.
- Kalra, N. and Paddock, S. M. (2016) Driving to safety: How many miles of driving would it take to demonstrate autonomous vehicle reliability? Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice.
- Kang, Y., Yin, H. and Berger, C. (2019) Test your self-driving algorithm: An overview of publicly available driving datasets and virtual testing environments. IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles.
- Kazi, T. A., Stanton, N. A., Walker, G. H. and Young, M. S. (2007) Designer driving: drivers' conceptual models and level of trust in adaptive cruise control. International Journal of Vehicle Design.
- Kerschbaum, P., Lorenz, L. and Bengler, K. (2014) Highly automated driving with a decoupled steering wheel. In: .
- Khajepour, A. (2020) Autonomous Vehicles and the Law: How Each Field is Shaping the Other. Synthesis Lectures on Advances in Automotive Technology.
- Kochova, K. and Felipe, M. (2018) Self-Driving Vehicles in Urban Environments. [Online]. Available: <https://insis.vse.cz/zp/63993/podrobnosti> [Accessed 13 Feb 2020].
- Koopman, P. and Wagner, M. (2017) Autonomous Vehicle Safety: An Interdisciplinary Challenge. IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine.
- Koustanaï, A., Cavallo, V., Delhomme, P. and Mas, A. (2012) Simulator Training With a Forward Collision Warning System. Human Factors: The Journal of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society.
- Krömker, H. (2019) HCI in Mobility, Transport, and Automotive Systems.
- Kurzweil, R. (2012) How to Create a Mind: The Secret of Human Thought Revealed.
- kvaser.com (2019) Kvaser Memorator Pro 2xHS v2 [Online]. Available: <https://www.kvaser.com/product/kvaser-memorator-pro-2xhs-v2/> [Accessed 14 Jul 2019].
- Lambert, F. (2021) TikTok star criminally uses Tesla Autopilot and posts video evidence TikTok user misuses Tesla Autopilot and posts the evidence [Online]. Available: <https://electrek.co/2021/01/20/tiktok-star-criminally-tesla-autopilot-posts-video-evidence/> [Accessed 22 Apr 2021].
- Lawrenz, W. (2013) CAN System Engineering: From Theory to Practical Applications.
- Leitner, A. (2019) Testing & Validation of highly automated systems [Online]. Available: https://www.tugraz.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Institute/IHF/Projekte/ENABLE-S3_SummaryofResults_May2019.pdf [Accessed 18 Dec 2020].
- Leitner, A., Watzenig, D. and Ibanez-Guzman, J. (2020) Validation and Verification of Automated Systems.
- Liu, P., Zhang, Y. and He, Z. (2019) The effect of population age on the acceptable safety of self-driving vehicles. Reliability Engineering & System Safety. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0951832018308305>.
- Liu, S., Li, L., Tang, J., Wu, S. and Gaudiot, J.-L. (2018) Creating Autonomous Vehicle Systems.
- Loro, A. (2018) A modest proposal for an alternative or adjunct to the SAE levels of automation [Online]. Available: <http://antonioloro.com/index.php/2018/04/18/a-modest-proposal-for-an-alternative-or-adjunct-to-the-sae-levels-of-automation/> [Accessed 25 Nov 2018].
- Loveday, S. (2021) How Does Tesla's Full Self-Driving Beta Fare In Construction Zones? [Online]. Available: <https://insideevs.com/news/460678/tesla-fsd-beta-difficult-construction-zones> [Accessed 8 Sep 2021].
- Ma, Y., Li, Z. and Sotelo, M. A. (2020) Testing and Evaluating Driverless Vehicles' Intelligence: The Tsinghua Lion Case Study. IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Magazine.

- Marcano, M., Diaz, S., Perez, J. and Irigoyen, E. (2020) A Review of Shared Control for Automated Vehicles: Theory and Applications. *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9203972/>.
- Maurer, M., Gerdes, C., Lenz, B. and Winner, H. (2016) Autonomous Driving: Technical, Legal and Social Aspects.
- Mcfarland, M. (2019) Self-driving cars : Hype-filled decade ends on sobering note. [Online]. Available: <https://edition.cnn.com/2019/12/18/tech/self-driving-cars-decade/index.html> [Accessed 3 Aug 2020].
- McQueen, B. (2019) Unsettled Topics Concerning the Field Testing of Automated Driving Systems [Online]. Available: <https://saemobilus.sae.org/content/EPR2019009/>.
- Michon, J. A. (1985) A Critical View of Driver Behavior Models: What Do We Know, What Should We Do? In: Human Behavior and Traffic Safety.
- Milford, M., Anthony, S. and Scheirer, W. (2020) Self-driving vehicles: Key technical challenges and progress off the road.
- MIT Technology Review Insights (2019) Autonomous driving: Safety first. [Online]. Available: <https://s3-ap-southeast-1.amazonaws.com/mittr-intl/US/AV.pdf> [Accessed 4 Feb 2020].
- motor1.com (2019) 2020 Audi A5 Coupé [Online]. Available: <https://de.motor1.com/photo/4340154/2020-audi-a5-coupe/> [Accessed 10 Nov 2020].
- Mueller, A. S., Cicchino, J. B. and Zuby, D. S. (2020) What humanlike errors do autonomous vehicles need to avoid to maximize safety? *Journal of Safety Research*. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0022437520301262>.
- National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (2019) Target Crash Population For Crash Avoidance Technologies in Passenger Vehicles [Online]. Available: <https://crashstats.nhtsa.dot.gov/Api/Public/Publication/812653> [Accessed 7 Feb 2020].
- National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (2022) Summary Report: Standing General Order on Crash Reporting for Automated Driving Systems [Online]. Available: <https://www.nhtsa.gov/sites/nhtsa.gov/files/2022-06/ADS-SGO-Report-June-2022.pdf> [Accessed 6 Nov 2022].
- National Transportation Safety Board (NTSB) (2018) Preliminary Report HWY18MH010 [Online]. Available: <https://www.ntsb.gov/investigations/AccidentReports/Reports/HWY18MH010-prelim.pdf> [Accessed 14 May 2020].
- Pathrose, P. (2022) ADAS and Automated Driving: A Practical Approach to Verification and Validation.
- Pek, C., Koschi, M. and Althoff, M. (2019) An Online Verification Framework for Motion Planning of Self-driving Vehicles with Safety Guarantees An Online Verification Framework for Motion Planning of Self-driving Vehicles with Safety Guarantees. [Online]. Available: <http://mediatum.ub.tum.de/doc/1470247/911637157399.pdf> [Accessed 5 Apr 2021].
- Plaza, P. M. (2018) Software Architecture for Self-Driving Navigation. [Online]. Available: https://e-archivo.uc3m.es/bitstream/10016/28141/1/tesis_pablo_marin_plaza_2018.pdf [Accessed 7 Dec 2018].
- Qudrat-Ullah, H. (2014) Better Decision Making in Complex, Dynamic Tasks: Training with Human-Facilitated Interactive Learning Environments.
- Rajabli, N., Flammini, F., Nardone, R. and Vittorini, V. (2020) Software Verification and Validation of Safe Autonomous Cars: A Systematic Literature Review. *IEEE Access*.
- Reddy, N., Farah, H., Huang, Y., Dekker, T. and Van Arem, B. (2020) Operational Design Domain Requirements for Improved Performance of Lane Assistance Systems: A Field Test Study in The Netherlands. *IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transportation Systems*.
- Rosenblatt, K. (2019) Video shows motorist asleep behind wheel of self-driving Tesla [Online]. Available: <https://www.nbcnews.com/news/us-news/video-shows-motorist-asleep-behind-wheel-self-driving-tesla-n1051486> [Accessed 13 Nov 2019].
- Rosenfeld, A. and Kraus, S. (2018) Predicting Human Decision-Making: From Prediction to Action. Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. [Online]. Available: <http://www.morganclaypool.com/doi/10.2200/S00820ED1V01Y201712AIM036>.
- Ross, H.-L. (2016) Functional Safety for Road Vehicles [Online]. Available: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-319-33361-8>.
- SAE (2016) Diagnostic Trouble Code Definitions J2012_201612 [Online]. SAE. Available: https://www.sae.org/standards/content/j2012_201612/ [Accessed 5 Oct 2018].
- Schaub, A. (2018) Robust Perception from Optical Sensors for Reactive Behaviors in Autonomous Robotic Vehicles [Online]. Available: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-3-658-19087-3>.
- Schinkel, W. S., van der Sande, T. P. J. and Nijmeijer, H. (2020) Driver Intervention Detection via Real-Time Transfer Function Estimation. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*.

- Schneider, N., Purucker, C. and Neukum, A. (2015) Comparison of steering interventions in time-critical scenarios. Procedia Manufacturing.
- Shinar, D. (2017) Traffic Safety and Human Behavior [Online]. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/publication/doi/10.1108/9781786352217>.
- Singh, H. and Kathuria, A. (2021) Analyzing driver behavior under naturalistic driving conditions: A review. Accident Analysis & Prevention. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0001457520317280>.
- Sjafrie, H. (2020) Introduction to Self-Driving Vehicle Technology.
- Smith, B. (2019) Personality facets and ethics positions as directives for self-driving vehicles. Technology in Society. [Online]. Available: <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0160791X1830109X>.
- softing.com (2021) Bus Systems - CAN, CAN FD, FlexRay, Ethernet, K-Line, LIN and MOST in use [Online]. Available: <https://automotive.softing.com/standards/bus-systems.html> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Stumpf, R. (2020) Autopilot Blamed for Tesla's Crash Into Overturned Truck [Online]. Available: <https://www.thedrive.com/news/33789/autopilot-blamed-for-teslas-crash-into-overturned-truck> [Accessed 25 Sep 2020].
- Szymkowski, S. (2021) Tesla interior cameras threaten driver privacy, Consumer Reports says [Online]. Available: <https://www.cnet.com/roadshow/news/tesla-interior-cameras-driver-privacy-consumer-reports/> [Accessed 2 Jun 2021].
- Takacs, A., Rudas, I., Bösl, D. and Haidegger, T. (2018) Highly Automated Vehicles and Self-Driving Cars. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8574003/>.
- Takemura, K. (2014) Behavioral Decision Theory [Online]. Available: <http://link.springer.com/10.1007/978-4-431-54580-4>.
- Tan, H., Zhao, F., Hao, H., Liu, Z., Amer, A. A. and Babiker, H. (2020) Automatic Emergency Braking (AEB) System Impact on Fatality and Injury Reduction in China. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/17/3/917>.
- Tesla Raj (2020) Tesla FSD beta vs Construction [Online]. Available: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=blhiE5LVgDE&t=366s> [Accessed 17 Dec 2020].
- TeslaDeaths.com (2021) Tesla Deaths is a record of Tesla accidents.pdf [Online]. Available: <https://www.tesladeaths.com/> [Accessed 6 Sep 2021].
- The Ford Motor Company (2021) Ford Co-Pilot360™: Most Advanced Suite Of Standard Driver-Assist Technologies Includes Automatic Emergency Braking [Online]. Available: <https://media.ford.com/content/fordmedia/fna/ca/en/news/2018/03/15/ford-co-pilot360.html> [Accessed 19 Jan 2021].
- Tian, Y., Pei, K., Jana, S. and Ray, B. (2017) DeepTest: Automated Testing of Deep-Neural-Network-driven Autonomous Cars. arXiv. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1708.08559>.
- Topham, G. (2021) Peak hype: why the driverless car revolution has stalled [Online]. Available: <https://amp.theguardian.com/technology/2021/jan/03/peak-hype-driverless-car-revolution-uber-robotaxis-autonomous-vehicle> [Accessed 23 May 2021].
- Utriainen, R., Pollanen, M. and Liimatainen, H. (2020) The Safety Potential of Lane Keeping Assistance and Possible Actions to Improve the Potential. IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Vehicles.
- Valdes-Dapena, P. (2017) GM: Self-driving cars are our next big thing [Online]. Available: <https://money.cnn.com/2017/11/30/technology/gm-autonomous-cars-2019/index.html> [Accessed 11 Mar 2020].
- Wadhwa, V. and Salkever, A. (2017) The Driver in the Driverless Car.
- Wang, H. (2019) Inertial detection of unusual driving events for self-driving.
- Wang, X., Guo, L. and Jia, Y. (2018a) Human Intervention Detection on a Steering Actuation System in Autonomous Vehicles. In: SAE Technical Papers. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sae.org/content/2018-01-0767/>.
- Wang, X., Guo, L. and Jia, Y. (2018b) Online Sensing of Human Steering Intervention Torque for Autonomous Driving Actuation Systems. IEEE Sensors Journal. [Online]. Available: <http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8307236/>.
- Wang, X., Wu, J., Gu, Y., Sun, H., Xu, L., Kamijo, S. and Zheng, N. (2018) Human-Like Maneuver Decision Using LSTM-CRF Model for On-Road Self-Driving. In: 2018 21st International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC). [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/8569524/>.
- Waymo (2020) Waymo Safety Report - September 2020 [Online]. Available: <https://waymo.com/safety> [Accessed 9 Aug 2021].

- Wien, J. (2019) An assessment of the willingness to choose a self-driving bus for an urban trip: A public transport user's perspective. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/An-assessment-of-the-willingness-to-choose-a-bus-an-Wien/1ce20932c916795dc1b32e2030ad3238322041cc> [Accessed 30 Oct 2020].
- Williams, C. (2016) Stop lights, sunsets, junctions are tough work for Google's robo-cars [Online]. Available: https://www.theregister.com/2016/08/24/google_self_driving_car_problems/ [Accessed 17 Dec 2018].
- Winkle, T., Erbsmehl, C. and Bengler, K. (2018) Area-wide real-world test scenarios of poor visibility for safe development of automated vehicles. European Transport Research Review. [Online]. Available: <https://etr.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s12544-018-0304-x>.
- World Health Organization (2020) Road traffic injuries [Online]. Available: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/road-traffic-injuries> [Accessed 2 Aug 2021].
- Xia, Z.-X., Lai, W.-C., Tsao, L.-W., Hsu, L.-F., Hu Yu, C.-C., Shuai, H.-H. and Cheng, W.-H. (2021) A Human-Like Traffic Scene Understanding System: A Survey. IEEE Industrial Electronics Magazine. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9293109/>.
- Xu, J. and Howard, A. (2020) How much do you Trust your Self-Driving Car? Exploring Human-Robot Trust in High-Risk Scenarios. IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems.
- Yadron, D. and Tynan, D. (2016) Tesla driver dies in first fatal crash while using autopilot mode [Online]. Available: <https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2016/jun/30/tesla-autopilot-death-self-driving-car-elon-musk> [Accessed 2 Mar 2019].
- Young, M. S. and Stanton, N. A. (2023) Driving Automation: A Human Factors Perspective (Human Factors, Simulation and Performance Assessment).
- Zhang, Y., Ma, J., Pan, C. and Chang, R. (2021) Effects of automation trust in drivers' visual distraction during automation. PLOS ONE.

Appendix I. Electronic Components of the Shadow Steering Wheel

Table 34: Electronic components of the Shadow Steering Wheel.

Name & Total units	Image	Specification
<p>RP-C7.6-LT Thin Film Force Sensor (Total units: 4)</p>	<p>The image shows a thin film force sensor, which is a small, rectangular component with a yellow circular top and two long, thin, silver-colored leads extending downwards. The top surface has a grid-like pattern.</p>	<p>Model: Rp C7.6 Lt Manufacturing Process: Thin Film Output Signal: Analog Force Induction Range: 20G 1.5 kg Trigger: 20 g, Default Resistance < 200 kΩ, Trigger Thickness: 0.4 mm Not Trigger Resistance: < 10 mw Activation Time: < 0.01 s Delay: +10%, (Rf+ Rf)/Fr+,1000G Force Response Time: << 10 ms Size: 4.3 X 7.8 mm / 1.69 X 3.07In Weight: 5G</p> <p>The curve of the resistance for the sensor is shown in Figure 70.</p>
<p>TCRT5000 IR Line Following Sensor (Total units: 2)</p>	<p>The image shows a blue PCB-mounted TCRT5000 IR line following sensor. It features a central lens and several pins on the left side. The text 'MH-Sensor-Series' is visible on the board.</p>	<p>Voltage: 5V Current: 15 mA Frequency Hz: 50 Hz Model: TCRT5000 Output Form: Digital Switch Output</p> <p>The measuring distance range from 1mm to 8mm, and the central point is about 2.5mm</p>

<p>Feetech FT90M Metall Digital Robo Servo 270° (Total units: 2)</p>		<p>Voltage: 4.8V-6V Actuating time(sec/60°): 4.8V: 0.09sec/60° 6V: 0.07ec/60° actuating force(kg/cm): 4.8V: 1.9kg/cm 6V: 2.2kg/cm Weight: approx. 13g Cable length: approx. 25cm Gear: metal Control: Digital Operating angle: 270 degrees (1000us-2000us)</p>
<p>Guangcailun NEO-6M GPS- Modul EEPROM (Total units: 1)</p>		<p>3V to 5V power supply Destined module with ceramic can antenna, be used signal super There is a LED signal indicator Default Baud Rate: 9600 (Configurable from 4800 Baud to 115200 Baud rates) 5Hz position update rate Operating temperature range: -40 TO 85°C UART TTL socket EEPROM to save configuration settings Rechargeable battery for Backup The cold start time of 38 s and Hot start time of 1 s SuperSense ® Indoor GPS: -162 dBm tracking sensitivity Support SBAS (WAAS, EGNOS, MSAS, GAGAN) Can Antenna size 27 * 27 mm Module size 26 mm * 37 mm Installation aperture 3 mm</p>

<p>Joy-IT Entwicklungsplatine NodeMCU mit ESP32 (Total units: 1)</p>		<p>ESP32-based NodeMCU board in 30-pin DIL plug-in format</p> <p>Processor: Tensilica LX6 Dual Core, 240 MHz, 512 kB SRAM, 4 MB RAM</p> <p>2.4 GHz WLAN (802.11b/g/n), Bluetooth Classic/LE</p> <p>Data interfaces UART/I2C/SPI, USB, DAC/ADC, total 19 GPIOs</p> <p>Operating voltage 3.3 V, operation via 5 V USB port possible</p>
<p>USB Battery Pack (Total units: 1)</p>		<p>5 Volt</p> <p>2200 mAh Capacity</p> <p>1A Output</p>
<p>Trimpot Variable Resistor (103) (Total units: 2)</p>		<p>10kΩ</p> <p>Size: 6 mm</p>

Sledge

In the center of the SSW component is the Sledge for detecting the force movement from the driver via two sensors, and then executes the movement via a DC motor. In addition, a sensor detects the driver's hand.

Technical drawing of the Sledge component.

Pusher

The Pusher is used for the transmission of the driver's movement to the force sensor. One Pusher is integrated into the lower part of the Handle component. Due to the assembly of the complete system, the represented Pusher must be attached after the complete assembly.

Technical drawing of the Pusher component.

Fastener 1

The component is used in the Sledge for positioning and mounting the force sensor. Very precise positioning of the sensor is necessary for accurate pressing of the sensor by the Pusher. This can result in the recorded value of the force not being correct.

Technical drawing of the Fastener 1 component.

Fastener 2

The Fastener 2 has the same functionality as the Fastener 1 with the small difference that a recess is necessary due to the cable channel.

Technical drawing of the Fastener 2 component.

Cover 1

Cover 1 is used for closing the SSW on the bottom side so that all electronic components are well protected.

Technical drawing of the Cover 1 component.

Cover 2

Cover 2 protects all electronic components.

Technical drawing of the Cover 2 component.

Gear

This component is used for the transmission of the movement of the DC motor, which is mounted in the Sledge and is used in the gear shown. This transmits the movement to the toothed belt of the Handle component. The radius of the Gear is 13 mm.

Technical drawing of the Gear component.

GPS Block

For separate positioning of the receiver unit for the GPS module, the GPS Block shown was developed to ensure sufficient space between the other electronic components and thus prevent overheating.

Technical drawing of the GPS Block component.

Lid

The purpose of this component is to close the Data Collection Box in order to protect the electronic components. The Lid can be quickly closed and opened by using an integrated magnet.

Technical drawing of the Lid component.

Appendix III. Shadow Application Usage Documentation

After starting the SA, three options appear on the dashboard. By selecting the “Test Drive” option (see marker 1 in Figure 88), a new test drive can be started. When this function is executed, corresponding structures for recording the data are automatically created in the background. The “Application Settings” (marker 2) can be used to define the storage location of the collected data on the local system and a Microsoft Azure Blob Storage. The last menu item, “Equipment Settings” (marker 3), is used to define different parameters for the data collection devices. For the SSW component, for example, the device name, thresholds, and recording rate can be defined. SA can also define camera settings, i.e., which device is to be used for recording which view (front, rear, and side).

Figure 88: Screenshot of the Dashboard view in the Shadow Application.

Vehicle Selection

After selecting the “Test Drive” option on the dashboard, a vehicle must be selected to perform the test drive. The displayed data is taken from the Vehicle.json file, which was described in Section 5.2. Only the essential data for identifying the vehicle is displayed on the UI. In the background, more data is available for data analysis. By clicking on “Select” (marker 1 in Figure 89), the corresponding vehicle gets selected.

Figure 89: Screenshot of the Vehicle Selection view in the Shadow Application.

Test Parameter

In the next step, basic parameters need to be defined at the beginning of a test drive, as shown in Figure 90. These include context data such as the driver or the road conditions. Selected data can be adapted during a test drive; for example, weather information can change. All data that is selected via the dropdowns are filled from the JSON files behind them, which were described in Section 5.2.2.

Figure 90: Screenshot of the Test Parameter view in the Shadow Application.

Test Equipment

In the last configuration window, before the test drive starts, the devices used, as shown in Figure 91, must be selected. By selecting the corresponding checkboxes, the devices are activated and taken into account during data recording. All entered parameters are confirmed via the “Start” button; this way, the basic configuration of a test drive is completed.

Figure 91: Screenshot of the Test Equipment view in the Shadow Application.

SSW - Main view

After successful configuration, data recording may start. Figure 92 shows the UI with individual markers on the elements described briefly below to explain the function.

Figure 92: Screenshot of the Main view in the Shadow Application for the Shadow Steering Wheel component.

A) Legend

The first marker shows a summary of the different signals that are displayed in the main area of the screen. When data recording is active, the signals from the SSW component are displayed in the diagram.

B) Primary y-axis

On this axis, the value measured in degrees from the SSW component is displayed by means of a blue line. This signal represents the difference between the real steering wheel of the vehicle and the steering movement of the human driver via the SSW system. The two horizontal lines (yellow and violet) indicate the limit ranges for the difference deviation. If the deviation exceeds the upper limit (violet line), the SSW component is locked and the driver's movement is transferred to the real steering wheel. The area between the yellow and violet lines serves as information that there is already a strong deviation and that the human driver would react significantly differently in the current scenario; however, a deviation in this range does not yet lead to a lockout of the SSW component. The limits for the threshold values can be set depending on defined speed ranges.

C) x-axis

On the x-axis, the duration of the recording is displayed in mm:ss format. The axis shifts automatically to the left when data recording is active.

D) Secondary y-axis

The secondary y-axis on the right side is used to visualize the limit values for the force. Due to different limit values compared to the primary y-axis, this form of representation was used. Similar to the primary y-axis,

there is also a limit value here, which is shown in Figure 92 as a red horizontal line. If this limit is crossed, the SSW component gets locked.

E) Control panel

This highlights the buttons that can be used to control the recording of a test drive. Clicking on the red circle starts data recording. The buttons next to it can be used to continue, pause, stop or repeat the recording. The last symbol facilitates a reset function, which deletes all previously recorded data of a test drive and starts from the beginning.

F) Views

In Figure 92, view options for the SSW component are shown. By clicking on one of the buttons, you can switch to OBD II data, GPS position information or log information of the application.

G) Metadata

If metadata changes during a drive, it can be flexibly adjusted via the icons in the lower area of the application. A click on an icon opens a corresponding view where the values of the corresponding category, for example, weather conditions, can be selected. Each change leads to an entry in the logbook behind it. In this way, all changes can be traced during data analysis.

H) Test Drive Data Storage

A successfully completed test drive may be ended by clicking the "Finish" button. This action ends all active data streams and finalizes data storage. All data are primarily stored on the local system. Depending on the configuration in the application settings, data can also be automatically synchronized to a Microsoft Azure Blob Storage for further processing and backup.

Appendix IV. On-Board Diagnostics Data Gathering Procedure

For the acquisition of data via the OBD interface, this section shows an example of how this can be done using a data logger and its associated software. The logic explained below has been integrated into the SA software to collect and synchronize all data centrally. This allows a direct comparison in post-data analysis activities. Figure 93 shows the result for an OBD II request with the HEX PID code "0C" and the CAN ID "7F" as request messages. The red-marked area shows the raw value that is returned via the OBD interface. In the example, this is extracted based on the OBD II PID specification, converted to decimal format and multiplied by a factor of 0.25. Through this translation, the real engine speed of 878.5 rpm is obtained, as can be seen, for example, on the speedometer of the vehicle in Figure 93.

Figure 93: Screenshot of an OBD II example for the engine speed signal.

When using diagnostic tools, the translation of raw values can be performed automatically by using a DBC file. Figure 94 shows an example of the translation for the engine speed measured value. The specification of the translation values is defined in the OBD II PID definition. A specification for a certain value, such as the engine speed, can be determined by the SAE organization (SAE, 2016). This conversion is performed automatically by the CanKing tool if the corresponding DBC file is stored. When defining the DBC specification, special attention must be paid to the "byte order." If this value is set incorrectly, the raw data is read in reverse order, resulting in an incorrect result.

Figure 94: Screenshot of a DBC example for the engine speed signal.

The DBC translation files for all other values available on the vehicle bus systems are usually proprietary and not disclosed by an OEM. The OBD interface only provides a partial view of the data; for example, only basic values defined in the international specification can be retrieved via an OBD interface. The remaining vehicle data is manufacturer-specific and is not subject to regulation. The additional signals and data are usually a secret of each manufacturer since the structure of the signals involves specific know-how. For complete data extraction, access to the bus system of the vehicle is necessary. Modern vehicles use, for example, Controller Area Network (CAN) or FlexRay (softing.com, 2021) as a bus system. Data extraction from these systems is not possible without interfering with the vehicle system and should only be carried out by experts, as any intervention can affect the vehicle. By directly accessing the vehicle's bus system, faulty or invalid signals can be imported, which can influence the entire vehicle system and lead to uncontrollable results. An example could be the sudden acceleration of the vehicle because a command was interpreted by the cruise control system. In this word, the OBD interface was used to determine the vehicle's speed, accelerator position, and brake pedal position. Further, a data logger from Kvaser was used for the readout. Figure 95 shows an image of the logger.

Content redacted due to copyright restrictions. Please contact the author for further information.

Figure 95: Photograph of Kvaser Memorator Pro 2xhs data logger (kvaser.com, 2019).

Kvaser offers an application called CanKing to read out data via the data logger. Figure 96 presents the components that are necessary for data determination.

Figure 96: Screenshot of Kvaser CanKing with engine revolutions per minute example.

In Figure 96, the two left windows represent the configuration of the request and response channels. The bus speed is particularly important to ensure that the logger can record data correctly. In the right window, called "CAN Message 1", the values that are to be queried by the OBD interface can be defined. In the example shown, the HEX value 12 is used for the engine speed query. The result is shown in the middle area. The tool displays the raw value, which was provided via the interface. In addition, the translated value can also be displayed automatically if a DBC file is stored.

OBD signals can be requested by sending a request message with the corresponding values. Figure 97 shows an example of the query of the engine speed by means of the HEX PID value "0C" and the CAN ID "7DF". The individual values of the message must be entered in the 8 fields for the byte values. This information is then sent to the interface by the data logger after clicking on "Send." By utilizing a DBC translation, Figure 93 and Figure 94 demonstrated how a CAN message can be returned and converted into a human-readable format.

Figure 97: Screenshot of an OBD example with CAN request message for engine speed signal.

Data Logging of On-Board Diagnostics Data

To record the OBD data of a vehicle, a separate module for the SA was developed to read out certain data via the interface at regular intervals. The application follows the same logic as the Kvaser tool. Within the scope of this research, a fixed set of signals was defined, which were collected during the test drives. Table 35 lists the essential signals that were recorded from the OBD II vehicle interface during the test drives as part of the data acquisition via the SA software. A uniformly synchronized time stamp in the format yyyy-mm-ddTHH:mm:ss.fff (e.g., 2019-04-06T14:33:12.214+01:00) with timezone information is used for all signals. This harmonization facilitates the superimposition of signals from different sources for evaluation.

Table 35: On-board diagnostics II data gathered by the Shadow Application.

Signals

Sampling Rate: 100ms for all signals by default

Common

Name	Unique Id	Unique Name	Default Unit	Source	Example	Comment
Timestamp	76ec7b6a-aaf4-4a73-815f-8472c8e30c6f	Common.Timestamp	default date/time	System	2019-04-06T14:33:12.214+01:00	The timestamp is generated by the Data Logger software

Vehicle

Name	Unique Id	Unique Name	Default Unit	Source	Example	Comment
Vehicle Speed	7336cb9f-e5c4-457f-a94b-cb4b7eb751ac	Vehicle.Speed	km/h	OBD II	134 km/h	OBD II: 0D (hex)
Throttle Position Absolut (Gas Pedal)	d1c914b0-2316-4edf-85e6-34a12bed5345	Vehicle.ThrottlePositionAbsolut	number	OBD II	0,78 → 78%	OBD II: 11 (hex)
Relative throttle position	a12297a4-7272-42c6-9823-2190d3cdd955	Vehicle.ThrottlePositionRelativ	number	OBD II	0,33 → 33%	OBD II: 45 (hex) 47, 48, 49, 4A, 4B, 4C
Relative accelerator pedal position	e09ee820-d791-4ed1-bf00-7a9a697522bc	Vehicle.AcceleratorPedal PositionRelative	number	OBD II	0,33 → 33%	5A
Throttle Position G	075e4957-2458-4b5a-9073-22c4e8f98b39	Vehicle.ThrottlePositionG	number	OBD II	0,12 → 12%	8D
Transmission Actual Gear	5f6fbc92-d463-4c0c-84d4-46d741f09123	Vehicle.Transmission.ActualGear	number	OBD II	5	A4
Intake air temperature	181a1167-5297-41ec-90b5-ae13b87a68f2	Vehicle.IntakeAirTemperature	C°	OBD II	23,4 > 23,4 C°	0F

The functionality of the OBD interface is based on the fact that a value such as a vehicle speed must be actively requested, and then the interface returns a value; this value is converted into a human-readable value by a DBC file. Figure 98 shows the basic concept of enabling a data readout. The ID attribute is used to establish uniqueness between the request and the response. This allows the correct assignments to be made between the messages. The Data Length Code (DLC) value must be set to 8 to simplify the length of the CAN message. In the “Data” attributes 1 to 8, the byte values must be entered as decimal values of the required signal. For the signal “Engine Speed” the CAN ID "7DF" from the OBD specification is entered as byte 0 = 2, byte 1=1, byte 2=12. The value “Channel” defines which channel is to be used by the data logger.

Initialize library ID: 2015 DLC: 8 Channel: 0

Open Channel

Data: 2 1 12

Set Bittate 500 kb/s

On Bus

Send Message

Flags: Remote STD EXT WakeUp
 NERR Error TXACK TXRQ
 Delay EDL BRS ESI

Test Drive: -

● Status: DBC File Vehicle Speed: **0 km/h**
● Status: Data Logger Directory Engine Speed: **0 rpm**

Figure 98: Screenshot of a data logger configuration to request vehicle speed signal.

This application requests vehicle data during a test drive from the OBD II interface and stores the values for post-data analysis processes. After the raw data is stored, a DBC file is used to translate the proprietary format that describes the data over a CAN bus. The request interval to obtain data from the interface is 100 ms. The human-readable values (e.g., vehicle speed) are stored in a CSV file. The first column of Figure 99 shows the unique time stamp of data acquisition with date, time and time zone. The second column shows the value read from the OBD interface. The graph shows the time history of the measured values.

Figure 99: Screenshot of a data logger output for vehicle speed signal.